

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Current rural Bioeconomy status

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Executive Summary

This study provides a review of the current status of the European Bioeconomy, containing all the main 5 themes (agriculture, water systems, forestry, bioenergy, biomaterials), as well as the existing bioeconomy national strategies, trends and opportunities that exist in the EU together with successful small-scale biobased solutions.

The information presented in this report illustrates the diversity and complexity of the EU bioeconomy. There are a number of important trends occurring in the EU bioeconomy: overall employment in the bioeconomy is decreasing while the overall value of the bioeconomy is increasing. Certain sectors, including the bioenergy and biomaterials sectors that are still relatively small as compared to their fossil-based equivalents, are experiencing rapid growth, these sectors are expected to continue to grow rapidly in the medium and long-term supporting sustainable transitions across the economy.

Data indicates that most of bioeconomy feedstocks are produced within the EU, in particular the agricultural sector with a relative weight of approximately 65% followed by forestry at 34% of dry matter with considerable variations on a country level. On the other hand, biomass supply from water systems is still relatively limited but shows considerable potential, especially in the biotechnology sector. Across the EU the largest consumption of biomass is for food and feed, followed by bioenergy and biomaterials. It is clear that a sustainable transition away from an economy based on fossil resources will require the significant growth in the bioenergy and biomaterials sector while maintaining the food and feed sector. In this context, it is important to consider trade-offs and to highlight that biomass is a finite resource and it is important that ongoing efforts directed at shifting existing biomass supply production systems transition towards more sustainable production methods are continued, that bio-waste collection and use systems are optimized and that new value chains for the sustainable production of biomass, such as BPC, are developed.

The EU economy is transforming from an economy based on linear economic models to circular economic models however, this transformation is still at its early stages and will require the transformation of existing production systems and value chains as well as the creation of new innovative value chains. This report illustrates the potential of small-scale biobased solutions on a country level across the EU and that these have the potential to scale and support a sustainable transformation across the entire EU economy. In this context, it is crucial that significant funds continue to support research and innovation in this sector.

In recent years EU policy has become very supportive of the development of a sustainable EU bioeconomy and the updated EU bioeconomy strategy operates in parallel to multiple other policy initiatives such as the new CAP, Green Deal, Farm to Fork strategy and the Circular economy action plan. In the short term, the further development of national strategies dedicated to the bioeconomy will strengthen the policy environment. In addition, the development of the bioeconomy has a crucial environmental dimension and current policy is supportive of efforts that support and strengthen environmental services and biodiversity. In addition, recent geopolitical developments and the associated increase in energy, fossil-based products and raw material prices have highlighted the importance of further developing local EU biobased value chains that replace energy and products from fossil sources.

This study identifies a number of key areas for future research including more detailed overviews of the bioeconomy for all EU member states; an in-depth analyses of specific bio-based value chains; the relationship between economy, society and the environment; the relationship between the bioeconomy, other sectors and the circular economy; indicators that measure the impact and potentials of the bioeconomy and its sectors are being developed and need to be strengthened further; and future research providing projections and scenario analyses on the future state of the bioeconomy in the medium and long-term.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	10
1.1	Context	10
1.2	Literature review	12
2	Methodology	15
2.1	Conceptual Framework	15
2.2	Data Sources, Selection Criteria, Search Strategy and Data Collection	16
2.3	Limitations	16
3	Policy	17
3.1	EU Policy	17
3.2	National Strategies	18
3.3	Regional Bioeconomy strategies	19
4	Status of the EU Bioeconomy	21
4.1	EU Bioeconomy	21
4.1.1	Overview	21
4.1.2	Employment and Value added.	21
4.1.3	Biomass Flows	24
4.2	National Bioeconomies	33
4.2.1	Greece	33
4.2.2	Italy	38
4.2.3	North Macedonia	42
4.2.4	Slovenia	45
4.2.5	Romania	52
4.2.6	Lithuania	61
4.2.7	France	67
4.2.8	Spain	71
4.2.9	Portugal	81
4.2.10	Denmark	88
4.2.11	Poland	93
4.2.12	Latvia	99
4.2.13	Germany	101
4.2.14	The Netherlands	107
5	Discussion/Analysis	110
6	Conclusions	112
7	References	113
8	Annex	120

List of Figures

Figure 1. The objectives of the CAP. Source: EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)	11
Figure 2. Bioeconomy trendline. Source: (Scopus)	12
Figure 3. The transition to a circular Bioeconomy. Source: (BioRural)	15
Figure 4. Conceptual diagram of a thematic circular Bioeconomy. Source: (BioRural)	16
Figure 5. EU Bioeconomy strategies. Source European Commission.....	18
Figure 6. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al)	19
Figure 7. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source (Haarich et al)	19
Figure 8. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al.)	20

Figure 9. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al.)	20
Figure 10. Employment by bioeconomy sector in EU27 (2019) (number of people employed). Source: (JRC)	21
Figure 11. Development of the number of people employed in selected sectors (EU27, 2008-2019). Source: JRC	22
Figure 12. Changes in employment between 2008 and 2019 EU 27. Source: JRC	22
Figure 13. Value added by sector in EU27 (2019) (million €) Source: JRC.	23
Figure 14. Development of value added in the bioeconomy (EU27, 2008-2019) (million €). Source: JRC.....	23
Figure 15. Changes in value added between 2008 and 2019 in EU 27. Source: (JRC).....	24
Figure 16. Biomass flows in EU. Source: (Biomass Flows).....	25
Figure 17. Biomass flows in Europe.	25
Figure 18. Biomass flows for agriculture, EU27, net trade, 2018 (1000 tdm).....	26
Figure 19. Sources of agricultural biomass, EU27, net trade, 2018.	26
Figure 20. Biomass supply from agriculture, net trade, 2018 (1000 tdm). Source: (DataM).....	27
Figure 21. Biomass flows for fisheries and aquaculture, EU27, net trade, 2016 (1000 tdm). Source: (DataM, 2022).....	27
Figure 22. Evolution of total forest area. Source: (Eurostat)	28
Figure 23. Woody biomass flows EU27, 2017 (1000 tdm). Source: (DataM, 2022).....	29
Figure 24. Domestic EU Energy Supply. Source: (DataM, 2022)	29
Figure 25. Share of renewables and bioenergy in gross EU energy consumption. Source: (Eurostat 2018b and NREAP Progress Reports)	30
Figure 26. EU Bioenergy consumption and projections until 2050. Source: (Eurostat 2018b) (European Commission, 2018b)	30
Figure 27. Bio-based value pyramid. Source: (Stegmann et al., 2020)	31
Figure 28. Biorefineries distribution in the EU as of March 2018 Source: (Joint Research Centre (European Commission), 2020).....	32
Figure 29. Biobased industries and biorefineries by Category in EU27.	33
Figure 30. Biomass flows in Greece (Gurria et al., 2017)	34
Figure 31. Biomass flows in Italy.....	39
Figure 32. Structure of employment in bioeconomy sectors in Slovenia in 2017. Source: (Ronzon et al., 2020).....	45
Figure 33. Structure of value added in bioeconomy sectors in Slovenia in 2017. Source: (Ronzon et al., 2020)	46
Figure 34. Biomass flows in Slovenia. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017)	46
Figure 35. Small-scale biobased solution for rural farms converting waste substrates into valuable algae biomass.....	51
Figure 36. Employment by sector in Romania, 2019. Source: (JRC)	53
Figure 37. Turnover by sector in Romania, 2019 in million euros. Source: (JRC).....	53
Figure 38. Value-added by sector (2019) in million euros.	54
Figure 39. Biomass flows in Romania. Source: BIOMASS project, European Commission. Source: (JRC).....	54
Figure 40. Agricultural Biomass flows. Source: (JRC)	55
Figure 41. Forestry biomass flows Romania. Source: (JRC).....	56
Figure 42. Biomass flows in Romania. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b)	57
Figure 43. Employment in Romania. Source: (JRC)	58
Figure 44. Turnover by sector. Source: (JRC)	58
Figure 45. Biomass flows in Lithuania. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b).....	61
Figure 46. Biomass flows in France. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b).....	68
Figure 47. Bioenergy use, 2019.....	69
Figure 48. Bioenergy production, 2019	69
Figure 49. Employment in bioeconomy sector in Spain, 2019, Source: (JRC)	71
Figure 50. Turnover in bioeconomy sector, Spain 2019. Source: (JRC).....	72
Figure 51. Value added in bioeconomy sector, Spain 2019. Source: (JRC)	72

Figure 52. Biomass flows in Spain. Source: (JRC)	73
Figure 53. Agricultural biomass flows, Spain. Source: (JRC).....	73
Figure 54. Biomass sourcing for Spain 2019. Source: (JRC)	74
Figure 55. Biomass sourcing, Spain 2019 Source: JRC	74
Figure 56. Biomass flows in forestry in Spain. Source: BIOMASS project: JRC.....	75
Figure 57. Biomass final use, Spain. Source: JRC	75
Figure 58. Evolution of employment (left) and turnover (right) in bioeconomy from 2008 to 2019 in Spain. Source: JRC.....	76
Figure 59. Rates of employment (left) and turnover (right) in bioeconomy from 2008 to 2019 in Spain. Source: JRC	77
Figure 60. Biomass flows in Denmark, (Gurría et al., 2017).....	88
Figure 61. Agricultural biomass flow in Denmark. Source: BIOMASS project: JRC	89
Figure 62. Forestry biomass flows in Denmark. Source: JRC.	89
Figure 63. Aquaculture biomass flows. Source: JRC	90
Figure 64. Biomass flows in Poland.....	94
Figure 65. Biomass flows in Latvia.	99
Figure 66. Biomass Flows.....	99
Figure 67. Employment by sector.	100
Figure 68. Value added by sector.	100
Figure 69. Biomass Flow Overview for Germany. Source: by Szarska et. al. 2021.....	102
Figure 70. Sankey Diagram of main biomass flows in Germany.	102
Figure 71. Biomass flows in The Netherlands.	108

List of Tables

Table 1. Estimated production of secondary agricultural residues (S2Biom, AgroBioHeat)	35
Table 2. Secondary Agricultural residues prices. Source: (Karampinis , 2020)	36
Table 3. Biomass potential 2020. Source: S2BIOM project.....	36
Table 4. Biomass potential 2020, S2Biom project	36
Table 5. Energy production in 2020. Source: (RAPPORTO STATISTICO 2020 ENERGIA.).....	40
Table 6. Primary agricultural production of 2021, Republic of Macedonia.	42
Table 7. Area (ha) and shares (%) of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by land categories (Source: SORS, 2021).	46
Table 8. Structure of agricultural holdings in Slovenia with respect to the production types (Source: SORS, 2021).	47
Table 9. The structure of the production of forest wood assortments in Slovenia in 2017	48
Table 10. Current national bioeconomy-related strategies and programming documents in Slovenia. Source: University of Ljubljana.	50
Table 11. The major concerns of the bioeconomy in France.	70
Table 12. Biomass trends. Source: (Biomass Flows)	78
Table 13. Cultivated area and feedstocks produced of the main crops in 2021.Source: (AFIA, 2021)	82
Table 14. Meat produced in 2021.Source: (AFIA, 2021)	82
Table 15. Products derived from animals produced in 2021.Source: (AFIA, 2021).....	83
Table 16. Production sales value of the food industries in 2020. Source: INE,2021	83
Table 17. Production sales value of the beverages industries in 2020. Source: INE,2021	84
Table 18. Employment and production sales value of forestry and wood-based industries in 2020. Source: (Eurostat,).....	84
Table 19. Final consumption destination of the wood-based industries in 2020. Source: (Lima, 2020)	85
Table 20. Distribution of fisheries captures by NUTS2.	85
Table 21. Production sales value, employment and final consumption destination of four selected sectors in 2020.	86

Table 22. Selected biomass value chains.	91
Table 23. Current national Bioeconomy related strategies in Poland. Source: (BIOEAST,)	96
Table 24. Current status of national bioeconomy strategy actors involved Source: (BIOEAST).	97
Table 25. Employment by sector. Source: (Biomass Flows,).....	100
Table 26. Value added by sector. Source:(Biomass Flows)	101
Table 27. Overview Of Feedstock. Source: (Szarka et al., 2021a)	103
Table 28. Value of each sector. Source: (Bundestag,).....	104
Table 29. Cluster and Initiatives. Source: (Clusterplattform Deutschland)	106

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used.

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1
EC	European Commission
CBE	Circular Bioeconomy
tdm	Total dry matter
CAP	Common Agriculture Policy
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
RRP	Recovery Resilience Plans
JRC	Joint Research Center
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
MWe	megawatt electrical
GWe	Gigawatt electrical
HABIO	Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
GDP	Gross domestic product
Mtoe	Million Tons of Oil Equivalent
toe	Tons of oil equivalent
DME	Dimethyl ether
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
UAA	Utilized Agricultural Area
SME	Small Medium Enterprises
RDI	Research development innovation
MADR	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
VDU	Vytautas Magnus University

GFC	Global Financial Crisis
MAPA	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fishery and Food
NECP	Spanish National Energy Climate Plan
SBR	Spanish Biogas Roadmap
GVA	Gross Value Added
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SBAP	Sustainable Biomass Action Plan
UTAD	University Tras-os-Montes Alto Douro
DKK	Danish Krone
PJ	Petajoule

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

Bioeconomy is an emerging field in the wider economy, as well as in research and policymaking which covers all the sectors and systems that rely on biological resources and supports the transition towards a sustainable European Economy. It comprises the parts of the economy that utilize renewable biological resources in order to produce food, materials and energy and can be defined as the “production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added product (European Commission). Its sectors and industries have strong innovation potential due to their use of a wide range of sciences, enabling and industrial technologies, along with local and tacit knowledge. It is this concept that manages the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value-added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products, and bioenergy (European Commission, 2018a).

One of the main and fundamental pillars of bioeconomy is the global industrial transition of sustainably utilizing renewable resources (aquatic and terrestrial biomass) in energy, intermediate and final products for economic, environmental, social, and national security (Biomass Research Development Board, BRDB). The current bioeconomy continues to rely on non-renewable energy and fossil-based raw materials in all the five sectors, such as nitrogen fertilizers, organic chemicals and polymers which are predominantly derived from petroleum and gas. However, as a concept bioeconomy is closely related to sustainability but also to circular economy, which are basic pillars in order to have a successful transition towards a sustainable economy. A sustainable bioeconomy is not just about substituting fossil resources with renewable ones, but also it requires sustainable biomass feedstock production, biomass conversion processes and products. This can be achieved by integrating with other areas such as circular economy which has seen great development during the last decade and considerable policy interest.

A circular bioeconomy is also interpreted as an idea to stimulate the economic growth of developed economies that combines the ‘what’ (circular economy) with a feasible, viable ‘how’ (bioeconomy) (Giampietro, 2019). Alternatively, a circular bioeconomy is simply interpreted as a more efficient resource management of bio-based renewable resources by integrating circular economy principles into the bioeconomy (Dalia D’Amato et al., 2020). It is also a framework for an economic model which aims to create economic, natural, and social capital based on three core principles:

- Design out of waste and pollution
- Keep products and materials in use and carbon products in the loop.
- Regenerate natural systems.

The European bioeconomy is one of the EU’s largest and most important sectors encompassing agriculture, forestry, fisheries, food, bioenergy, and bio-based products with an annual turnover of around 2 trillion euros and employing around 18 million people. The first EU bioeconomy strategy ‘Innovating for sustainable growth: A bioeconomy in Europe’, was adopted in 2012 and took actions through existing policies in the sectors (Common Agriculture Policy, Common Fishery Policy). The main goals of this action were:

- Ensure food and nutrition security.
- Manage our natural resources sustainably.
- Reduce the dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources.
- Mitigate and adapt to climate change.
- Create jobs across Europe.

Although it is a field that it is developed the last 3 decades, bioeconomy can contribute to restore ecosystems achieving the sustainable development goals set. The last strategy that the European Commission has developed is ‘A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe, strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment’ which is an update of the 2012 bioeconomy strategy.

As an organization the European Commission has put considerable efforts, funding and policies towards facilitating the development of a sustainable bioeconomy. The EU Green Deal which was released in December 2019 as a plan for tackling the environmental and climate challenges was one of the latest's European strategies. This plan was one of the main guidelines in which all the European Partners should organize their actions in a common aim to reduce by 2050 their emissions of greenhouse gases through modern, resource-efficient and competitive economies. This strategy will provide a series of actions that will restore biodiversity, reduce pollution and will boost the communities in a more efficient and clear circular economy.

European Commission's efforts have multiplied in the name of this transition. For this reason, the Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) was modernized, emphasizing in ensuring a sustainable future for the European farmers. Agriculture and rural areas are in the center of interest of the new CAP and the Green Deal, providing target support and solutions in smaller farms. The new CAP will be active in ten key objectives.

Figure 1. The objectives of the CAP. Source: EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

In this context, this study provides an overview and evaluates the current status of the bioeconomy in Europe with a particular focus on the state of the bioeconomy in 14 European countries. In addition, this study provides an overview of relevant national and European policies related to the Bioeconomy, highlights important trends along 5 bioeconomy themes. This is particularly relevant as it provides information on important trends in the bioeconomy supporting the work of policymakers and associated stakeholders. The improvement of circularity in the production has changed through the year and has been developed since more EU countries adopted a bioeconomy strategy. Different residual biomass streams which were sufficient to produce bioenergy, biochemicals on commercial levels, were some circular trends that first developed. Biorefineries using also these agricultural and forestry-based feedstock managed to produce chemicals composites and fibers. Additionally, the bioeconomy sector is now growing rapidly gaining more and more adopters making trends in order to change the production from the traditional linear one to a circular and more efficient one.

This report is structured as follows, the rest of this section provides a literature review, section 2 provides an overview of the methodology used in this study, section 3 presents an overview of relevant EU and national policies related to the bioeconomy, section 4 provides an overview of the EU bioeconomy and a more in-depth analysis for 14 European countries, section 5 discusses the main themes in this report and looks at future trends in the bioeconomy.

1.2 Literature review

The Bioeconomy is a relatively new concept in policymaking and can trace its roots to the 1982 EU framework programs in Biotechnology and life sciences (Patermann & Aguilar, 2018) which has led towards the conceptual development of the bioeconomy sector (Aguilar et al., 2012). Although there were some related bioeconomy publications before 2004, the first time that bioeconomy was mentioned as a meaning was in an OECD meeting (OECD, 2004). In 2012 with the release of the first EU bioeconomy strategy, the term became an important issue in the agenda of all the European research, energy and agricultural policies (Lühmann, 2020). In addition, many strategies in European but also in national level were developed supporting bioeconomy. Strategies like the ‘Green Deal’, the ‘Circular Economy Action Plan’ and the ‘Farm to Fork’ were some of the most important ones in recent years. These developments have led to a substantial increase in bioeconomy related research and the graph below shows the increase in publications related to the bioeconomy.

Figure 2. Bioeconomy trendline. Source: (Scopus)

Most of the publications around the theme of Bioeconomy appear to have an extended reference in the relationship between the meanings of bioeconomy and circular economy. Leipold & Petit-Boix, (2018) mentioned the importance between these terms. Circular economy including the meaning of bioeconomy, aims to the transition the current, linear economy system to a more sustainable one (Tan & Lamers, 2021). Also, this relationship is based in the same guidelines and developed in the ‘4R’ framework (reduce, reuse, recycle, recovery) (Lieder & Rashid, 2016). The meaning of bioeconomy as D’Amato et al., (2017) described is rooted in the idea that the industrial inputs should be derived from renewable biological resources. D’Amato et al., (2020), in looking for a theoretical approach of bioeconomy find that it is characterized by a dependency on provisioning services, specifically biomass but also resources and information based on ecosystem services.

As suggested by Aguilar et al., (2012) the development of the bioeconomy requires a combination of actions from the EU but also on a national level. It is important to note that the Bioeconomy has to do with the use of renewable biological resources to produce renewable biofuels, bioproducts and biopower for economic, environmental and social benefits (Tan & Lamers, 2021) and that the impact of sustainability in bioeconomy should not only refer to a shift from fossil resources to renewable ones, but to the widespread development and use of sustainable renewable biological resources (Aguilar et al., 2019). In recent years there is a clear increasing focus in a wide range of national and European actions/strategies for the development of the bioeconomy. Associated with this there is a clear need

for considerable research and indicators to measure the development of the bioeconomy. Currently, the European Commission supports this with considerable research and innovation funding for the bioeconomy, with more than 3.85 billion invested under Horizon 2020(2014-2020) and a proposed 10 billion for food and natural resources under Horizon Europe (European Commission, 2018c).

Bioeconomy is a broad term and is relevant to many economic sectors which complicates monitoring and evaluation of its development. In response, in 2017 the European Commission launched the Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy with the aim of bringing together the different policy areas related to the bioeconomy (European Commission, 2018c). Through this Knowledge center the monitoring of the current situation, research results, data analysis and policy developments are catalogued and made accessible, especially for policy makers and academia. More specifically, the monitoring of bioeconomy related policy and strategies provides a detailed overview of economic as well as social and environmental trends.

In 2018 the European Commission expanded the definition of the bioeconomy to cover the creation of different renewable biological resources and its conversion to various high-value bio-based products such as food, feed, bio chemicals and bioenergy. The goal was to mitigate the effects of climate change providing a renewable carbon source (biomass). The increasing demand for energy as well as the growing greenhouse gas (GHG) emission and the depleting fossil fuels, makes the biomass a renewable energy source to overcome the current and future energy needs. Bioeconomy is trying to utilize biomass as an integral component to generate various bio-products, bio-chemicals and bioenergy using biorefinery (European Commission, 2018). Cherubini, (2010) proposed the concept of biorefinery aiming to the utilization of biomass and minimize the waste and emissions associated with the conversion of bioenergy products. The concept was employed to efficiently produce high-value products from different feedstocks. The relationship between bioeconomy and biorefinery was described by Amulya et al., (2015), bioeconomy demands on renewable feedstocks which have potential to generate a spectrum of biobased products. For instance, biorefineries using a novel hydrothermal conversion method that can provide energy efficient products using lignocellulosic biomass (Zhang et al., 2007)(Sawatdeenarunat et al., 2018).

The biorefinery as a concept can use different feedstocks such as biomass, algae and food waste. Lignocellulosic biomass includes mainly agricultural waste and forest residues which can be used to create a large amount of products. In recent years, considerable interest has been placed on Algal feedstocks due to its fast growth rate and the high biomass yield per acre of cultivation. The advantage of this feedstock is that can also produce higher biomass than fast growing terrestrial plant (A.B. Ross J.M.Jones M.L.Kubacki T.Bridgeman, 2008). Interest in food waste as a feedstock also appears to be increasing due to its circular nature and availability (Bastidas-Oyanedel & Schmidt, 2018).

Several studies investigate the bioeconomy across themes and also along entire value chains trying to describe the transition of the already existing fossil value chain to a bio based one. Fossil fuel like coal, oil and gas are responsible for the energy use in the EU, up to 96% of these resources are used in the energy sector (Kircher, 2021). One of the main goals of the bioeconomy is the transition to feasible alternative materials, this biomass is mainly produced by agriculture, forestry, fishery, and marine sources. The better the biomass quality can be tailored to the needs of the conversion technology the less energy and material inputs are required and the higher the yields (Lewandowski et al., 2019).

There are a variety of relevant bioeconomy related publications to the current status of the bioeconomy published by Eurostat (*Home - Eurostat*, n.d.) These publications focus on the different material flows that exist in the EU, giving the opportunity to develop a database for all the available information that all the Member States can extract every year. Using this, the JRC has developed a Sankey Biomass tool that depicts biomass flows according to bioeconomy sector from supply to use (Gurria et al., 2017a) . Other studies, take a different approach, Hamelin et al (2019) investigates the residual biomass potential in the EU finding that around 8500 PJ y⁻¹ residual biomass is available, equivalent to the combined primary energy consumption of Italy and Belgium (Hamelin et al., 2019). Popp et al. (2021) investigate biomass supply and demand in the EU highlighting the complex interrelations between the demand of biobased products and land use and also advocating for a transformation towards the production of

biobased chemicals (Popp et al., 2021). This highlights the complexity of dealing with biobased value chains and encompassing them under one term. While, Antar et al (Antar et al., 2021) provide a global overview of biomass production and utilization (Antar et al., 2021). A number of studies have been conducted that investigate the development of the bioeconomy on a national level. Hayek et al. (Hájek et al., 2021) for the Czech Republic, Wozniak and Twardowski (Woźniak & Twardowski, 2018) and Szarka et al. (Szarka et al., 2021a) in Germany, Ahlqvist and Sirvio (Ahlqvist & Sirviö, 2019) in Finland.

A range of European projects are focused on supporting the transition to a more sustainable bioeconomy and circular economy. These projects conduct research and also design transition pathways towards a sustainable bioeconomy. These projects include: bioeconomy research projects like [BioMonitor](#) and [TECH4BIOWASTE](#), Business pathways/model development like [BIOEAST](#) and [MAINSTREAM BIO](#). Pilot projects like [P2GreeN](#) and [BIOMODEL4REGIONS](#), and network related projects like [BioRural](#) and [CELEBio](#).

2 Methodology

2.1 Conceptual Framework

This study adopts the European Commission definition of the bioeconomy as “using renewable biological resources from land and sea, like crops, forests, fish, animals and micro-organisms to produce food, materials and energy”. (European Commission, 2018a). More specifically, the Bioeconomy encompasses multiple and sectors; and an overall definition includes all systems that are dependent on biological resources (biomass, animals, plants and organisms) their functions and principles. This definition includes the primary production sector (agriculture, forestry, fishery and aquaculture) and all the economic and industrial sectors using biological resources to produce food, feed, biobased products, energy and services (European Commission, 2018a). The Bioeconomy is interdisciplinary and transcends and interlinks between these themes (food/agriculture, forestry/natural habitats and aquatic/water system bioenergy and biomaterials) sectors (primary, secondary, tertiary) and the wider economy.

Considering the definition, the bioeconomy can be conceptually categorized along 5 themes, line with the EU bioeconomy strategy:

- **Food/agriculture systems** which encompass all value chains related to farming, the production of food and biological feedstocks within the 10.5 million farms in the EU.
- **Forestry/natural habitats systems**, which are a source of environmental public goods, raw materials and services, and refer to processes of managing and utilizing the EU’s 182 million ha of forests.
- **Water systems** which refer to all aquatic systems and respective economic activities (such as fisheries, aquaculture, aquatic biomass production, etc.).
- **Bioenergy** which refers to all energy derived from organic sources, being the largest RES in the EU (12% of total energy demand).
- **Biomaterials/bio-based products** which are derived from renewable biological feedstocks and are processed creating conventional products (e.g., timber and textiles) and advanced products (bioplastics and pharmaceuticals).

It is important to note that according to the current definition the Bioeconomy is to a large extent based on unsustainable and linear production systems, as illustrated by the high dependence on fossil energy and inputs in Bioeconomy production systems. There are various interpretations as to the relationship between the circular economy and Bioeconomy, ranging from definitions that see them as distinct but overlapping concepts, to synonymous concepts, to the placement of the Bioeconomy within the circular economy. According to the EC, a circular Bioeconomy (CBE) is the application of the circular economy concepts to biological resources, products and materials.

Figure 3. The transition to a circular Bioeconomy. Source: (BioRural)

It is clear that EU policy supports the transition from current Bioeconomy production systems towards a CBE. In such a circular Bioeconomy, all inputs are renewable organic resources (complemented by inputs from the wider circular economy), while all outputs are either consumed sustainably or become productive inputs for other economic processes (Figure 3). Growth and transformation of Bioeconomy towards circular (renewable, waste-free) production models is underpinned by bio-based innovation (Figure 4), which broadly refers to innovation

processes that lead to increased energy or material efficiency, new properties of produced material or product, ability to use and valorize waste, and elimination of pollution (European Commission, 2018a). Bio-based innovation stimulates the development of alternatives to fossil products and/or entirely new products. Considering this our approach is to provide an overview of the entire bioeconomy while attempting to place an emphasis on identifying circular developments and trends (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Conceptual diagram of a thematic circular Bioeconomy. Source: (BioRural)

2.2 Data Sources, Selection Criteria, Search Strategy and Data Collection

This study conducts an overview of the current rural situation in the European Bioeconomy including the 14 countries represented in the Horizon Europe project BioRural. A combined data collection strategy was implemented. On the one hand, first relevant studies were identified through keyword searches using SCOPUS and google scholar. These were then assessed for their relevance and applicability based on a number of criteria. Only studies published in peer-reviewed journals or widely cited reports were included. This process was complemented by data searches in national and EU databases. This process provided data and trends on the bioeconomy status in the EU and on a country level. In parallel, a data request providing clear guidelines was sent to all the partners of the BioRural consortium (Annex 1) to identify country specific information on the status of the bioeconomy in each specific country including policies and trends.

2.3 Limitations

There are a number of key limitations to the present study. On the one hand, the Bioeconomy is a relatively new concept for which there are few studies and approaches available that focus solely on the Bioeconomy. In this sense, while considerable data exists on a macro level it is likely that considerable data gaps exist. These data gaps were partly addresses by incorporating keyword searches along the specific bioeconomy themes (agriculture, aquatic systems, forestry, bioenergy and biomaterials) in our data collection strategy. In addition, due to the general nature of the bioeconomy as a concept with different interpretations/definitions there is a risk of losing specific answers and results when discussing the bioeconomy. Due to the scale and complexity of the bioeconomy this study focused on the bioeconomy and its associated 5 themes mainly focusing on identifying biomass production and use trends as well as future trends. Considerable further research is needed within each theme and country to provide a more detailed overview of the bioeconomy. Important areas for future research that were beyond the scope of the present study are: in-depth analyses of specific bio-based value chains; the relationship between economy, society and the environment.

3 Policy

3.1 EU Policy

The first EU Bioeconomy strategy was launched in 2012, “Innovating for sustainable growth – A bioeconomy for Europe” (European Commission, 2012) with a main goal to accelerate the deployment of a sustainable bioeconomy and to transform the EU’s approach to the production, consumption, processing, storage, recycling, and disposal of biological resources. The latest EU Bioeconomy strategy was updated in 2018 and in 2022 a report was released that assesses the progress made in the implementation of the Bioeconomy strategy (European Commission, 2022).

Bioeconomy policies take a cross-sectoral perspective to improve policy coherence, identify and resolve trade-offs like land and biomass demand. These policies are designed around 3 sustainability dimensions. According to the latest EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report (EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report, n.d.), there are actions on track to enhance the main objectives of Bioeconomy strategy. Increasing number of national and regional bioeconomy strategies promoting cross-sectoral cooperation and sustainability principles and invest in bioeconomy innovations. The EU bioeconomy strategy enables a green transition covering all the 3 dimensions of sustainability (environment, society, economy)

- **Environmental sustainability:** By optimizing the use of biological resource from land and sea, the bioeconomy maximizes co-benefits. Production of biomass, mitigating the climate change and enhancing the biodiversity are some factors that safeguard and benefit the ecosystem services.
- **Economic sustainability:** Bioeconomy policies boost sustainable innovation and create solutions for sustainable food and bio-based products, bio-based and bioderived chemicals, advanced biofuels, and the bioenergy for the future.
- **Societal sustainability:** Bioeconomy policies enables a green transition developing sustainable business models based on the principles of diligence, and by promoting sustainable trade and social fairness in Europe.

The updated Bioeconomy strategy builds upon and stresses the continued importance of the goals of the 2012 bioeconomy strategy to ensure food and nutrition security; manage natural resources sustainably; reduce dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources; and limit and adapt to climate change; strengthen European competitiveness and create jobs. The associated bioeconomy action plan outlines 14 actions to accelerate the development of the EU Bioeconomy including:

- “Strengthen and scale up the biobased sectors, unlock investments and markets.”
 - mobilize stakeholders in developing and deploying sustainable biobased solutions.
 - launch a €100 million circular bioeconomy thematic investment platform.
 - analyze enablers and bottlenecks for the deployment of biobased innovations.
 - promote and develop standards.
 - facilitate the deployment of new sustainable biorefineries.
 - develop substitutes to fossil-based materials that are biobased, recyclable and marine biodegradable.
- Deploy local bioeconomies rapidly across the whole of Europe.
 - launch a strategic deployment agenda for sustainable food and farming systems, forestry and biobased products.
 - launch pilot actions for the deployment of bioeconomies in rural, coastal and urban areas.
 - support regions and EU countries to develop bioeconomy strategies.
 - promote education, training and skills across the bioeconomy.
- Understand the ecological boundaries of the bioeconomy.
 - enhance knowledge on biodiversity and ecosystems.
 - monitor progress towards a sustainable bioeconomy.
 - promote good practices to operate the bioeconomy within safe ecological limits.

- o enhance the benefits of biodiversity in primary production.” (European Commission, 2018a)

The 2022 EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report highlights a number of key important trends in the development of the EU Bioeconomy. These include that national bioeconomy strategies are developing across Europe, the main use of biomass continues to be for food and feed while biomass sourced from wood is increasingly utilized, important innovations are happening across the EU bioeconomy, in particular in food and bio-based industries, that research and innovation results have shown considerable promise and should continue to be strengthened (European Commission, 2022).

3.2 National Strategies

One of the main actions highlighted in the 2018 updated strategy was the necessity to develop detailed national policies, enabling countries and regions to design transition pathways according to their specific challenges and opportunities benefiting a non-prescriptive integrated and systemic framework (*EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report*, n.d.) supporting the development of strong societies, a resilient environment and sustainable economy.

Currently, multiple EU members have already developed multiple strategies, while others have strategies under development. Finland, France, Italy, Poland, Spain, and Sweden have developed an intense, regional strategic actions to deploy bioeconomy. Additionally, there are 15 countries having at least one region with bioeconomy relevant strategy in regional level (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, and Slovakia). In this countries the number of the regional strategies vary between 1 and 17. A few member states have yet to develop their national strategies (Bulgaria, Cyprus, Estonia, Luxemburg, Malta, Slovenia).

Figure 5. EU Bioeconomy strategies. Source European Commission.

Source: (*Bioeconomy Strategy | Knowledge for Policy*)

Figure 5 illustrates the members states according to the status of their strategies. Other have already developed strategies, other are under development but some others have strategies related to bioeconomy. Austria, Germany, Denmark, Latvia, Netherlands, France, Portugal, Spain, Finland, Ireland, and Italy are some of the members that have a developed strategy for bioeconomy having it updated lately. In addition, some others like Greece have national strategies for energy, climate, agriculture referring to bioeconomy.

3.3 Regional Bioeconomy strategies

Regional bioeconomy strategies are especially important in the EU members, these strategies are either dedicated to the bioeconomy solely, sectoral or embedded (the topic of bioeconomy is covered as an embedded topic within a wider strategic framework). The graph below indicates that there are many EU countries that have multiple strategies in place or under development. The latest research revealed that more than 359 strategies have been published or under development at regional level. This means that are fully or partially dedicated to bioeconomy or contribute to its development across EU. Of the 359 strategies the 345 are based on sub-national regional or local level, 15 are multi-regional and are identified covering more than one specific region. Additionally, not all of them are fully dedicated to bioeconomy, some cover the topic of bioeconomy within a sectoral topic and others as an embedded one.

Figure 6. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al)

The sectoral strategies that covers bioeconomy (83) are addressed in different topics like forestry, waste plans, energy, agriculture and food, aquaculture, fishery, algae as well as constructions.

Figure 7. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al)

Out of the 209 regional strategic frameworks bioeconomy is embedded through different topics. Regional and rural development, smart specialization strategies, circular economy strategies, strategies for economic and industrial development, sustainable development strategies, climate and low-carbon plans, regional research-innovation strategies. Also, in some cases bioeconomy is embedded in green or blue transition strategies or in recent recovery and resilience plans (RRP).

Figure 8. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al.)

All these strategies that are developed in regional level focus on some objectives and goals that want to be achieved. The main strategic objectives are analyzed in ensuring food and nutrition security, management of natural resources, mitigation and adaptation to climate change and strengthening the European competitiveness as well as the creation of new job opportunities. The number of strategies that emphasize in the sustainable management of the natural resources is 270 out of the overall 349. Additionally, an important number of strategies are focusing on the reduction of the dependence on the non-renewable sources (236). Many strategies refer to aim strength the competitiveness of the region and create new jobs (220). An important goal is the mitigation and adaptation of these strategies to the climate change where about two hundred strategies aiming to this goal. Also, about one hundred regional strategies have the food and nutrition security as a goal.

Figure 9. Regional Bioeconomy Strategies. Source: (Haarich et al.)

4 Status of the EU Bioeconomy

4.1 EU Bioeconomy

4.1.1 Overview

This section provides an overview of the status of the EU Bioeconomy Overview, in particular this section highlights employment and value added, and biomass flows according to the main bioeconomy themes.

4.1.2 Employment and Value added.

Overall, currently, based on the latest data from the JRC around 17.42 million people are employed in the EU Bioeconomy, representing around 9% of the entire EU workforce. Around 50% of these are employed in agriculture, 26.4% in food beverage and tobacco production, 7.6% in wood products and furniture, 4.5% in bio-based textiles, 3.6 in paper production, 3% in forestry, 2.7% in biobased chemicals, plastics and rubber, 0.9% in fishing and agriculture, 0.1% in bio-based electricity and 0.1% in liquid biofuels (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Employment by bioeconomy sector in EU27 (2019) (number of people employed). Source: (JRC)

The number of people employed in the bioeconomy sector as a whole has been steadily decreasing from 20.15 million people in 2008 to 17.42 in 2019. The largest decreases are observed in the agricultural and textile sectors. By contrast large increases are observed, from a low base, in biobased electricity and biofuels sectors, and to a lesser extent in the biobased-chemicals sector (Figure 10).

Figure 11. Development of the number of people employed in selected sectors (EU27, 2008-2019). Source: JRC

Figure 12. Changes in employment between 2008 and 2019 EU 27. Source: JRC

The entire EU Bioeconomy has an annual turnover of around €2.2 trillion with an added value of 657 billion euros. The food, beverage and tobacco sector accounts for 36.2%, followed by agriculture at 29.4%, biobased chemicals, plastics and rubber at 9.8%, wood products and furniture at 7.6%, paper at 7.3%, bio-based textiles at 3.9%, forestry at 3.8%, fishing and aquaculture at 0.9%, bio-based electricity at 0.8% and liquid biofuels at 0.5% (Figure 12).

Figure 13. Value added by sector in EU27 (2019) (million €) Source: JRC.

Figure 14. Development of value added in the bioeconomy (EU27, 2008-2019) (million €). Source: JRC

In contrast to the trends in employment all sectors have experience gains in the total valued added by the bioeconomy increasing from 515 billion euros in 2008 to 657 billion euros in 2018. In particular the liquid biofuels and biobased electricity sectors have seen rapid growth over a 100%. This contrast between a decrease in employment but increase in value added suggests considerable improvements in productivity in the bioeconomy in recent years.

Figure 15. Changes in value added between 2008 and 2019 in EU 27. Source: (JRC)

4.1.3 Biomass Flows

The following section provides an overview of the biomass flows according to the 5 bioeconomy themes; these flows are particularly useful in providing an overview of biomass supply, processing and consumption. There is considerable variation in the types and geographic availability of biomass across the EU, the main biomass supply types originate from the following sources, including: forests (thinning, logging residues), by-products of the wood industry, energy crops, agricultural by-products, biomass from waste streams, by-products from agro-food industry, aquatics biomass. The EC's JRC produces regular overviews in their EU Biomass Flows tool, more detailed data is available there (Gurria et al., 2017b).

Overall, the total production of biomass in the EU consisted of around 1.1 billion tons of dry matter of which 95% is produced locally and 5% imported. Agriculture is the biggest supply sector (65% dry matter). The level of contribution in this biomass flow differs according to the country and their potentials for example countries like Greece, Malta, Hungary and Cyprus have a number of 90% because of the agricultural and field areas but on the other hand Finland has only 13% because instead of agricultural areas the country is covered by forests, and this is the reason why the forestry contribution numbers 87%. On the other hand, the fishery sector is not so well developed and numbers less than 1% where the agriculture and forestry sectors play the most important role. Although the agriculture and forestry sector are in high levels, Europe faces a problem with the unused and

Figure 16. Biomass flows in EU. Source: (Biomass Flows)

abandoned areas which represents about 15.8% of the total land use in EU 28. This problem is more detailed in some countries (Greece, Croatia, Spain, UK) with more that 25% of abandoned and unused areas.

EU-28, Net trade

Figure 17. Biomass flows in Europe. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017a)

4.1.3.1 Agriculture

According to the estimates produced by the JRC (*Biomass Flows*, n.d.-b) agriculture amounts to approximately 713 million tons of dry vegetal biomass equivalents. It is composed of crop harvested production, collected crop residues, grazed biomass and imports of biobased products. The crop harvested production is estimated at 485 million tdm of biomass in the EU-27 (i.e., approximately 2 billion tons of fresh biomass). Collected crop residues constitute around 88 100 million Tdm of biomass. 95 million Tdm of biomass are grazed in pastures and meadows. Around 10 million additional tons of dry matter of crop residues could be collected without hampering the production of ecosystem services such as soil carbon conservation, fertility maintenance, water retention, etc. Around 44 million Tdm of biomass are imported, 53% in the form of crop products (non-manufactured), 25% in the form of food products and the rest in the form of biomaterial products (ca. 22%). In terms of uses, the vast majority goes to feed and food products with a relatively small amount for bioenergy and unknown uses.

Figure 18. Biomass flows for agriculture, EU27, net trade, 2018 (1000 tdm)

Source: (DataM)

Figure 19. Sources of agricultural biomass, EU27, net trade, 2018.

Source: (DataM)

On a geographical level France and Germany have the highest supply of Biomass followed by Italy and Spain. For most countries crop production accounts for the majority of biomass. Notably, a number of countries import a significant amount of biomass (Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Belgium) and re-export them.

Figure 20. Biomass supply from agriculture, net trade, 2018 (1000 tdm). Source: (DataM)

4.1.3.2 Water Systems

The total supply in the EU27 for fisheries and aquaculture was 3.296 million tdm in 2016. The EU production of fisheries and aquaculture was around 1.4 million tdm with 1.1 million tdm coming from capture fisheries and 0.3 million tdm from aquaculture. EU net imports of seafood products are significant, reaching 1.555 million tdm in 2016. The vast majority of the total supply is used for aquatic-based food (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Biomass flows for fisheries and aquaculture, EU27, net trade, 2016 (1000 tdm). Source: (DataM, 2022)

In terms of important trends, increases of seafood production, and consequently of seafood biomass production, could be obtained if fish stocks were managed to produce the Maximum Sustainable Yield. The status of fish stocks has been improving in the Northeast Atlantic and Baltic waters over the period 2003-2014, where most fish in the EU is caught STECF, 2016 (Carvalho et al., 2016).

Nevertheless, in 2014, the number of overfished stocks (i.e., fishing pressure levels above Maximum Sustainable Yield) in these waters is about 50% of the total number of stocks which were assessed (Carvalho et al., 2016).

In the Mediterranean and Black Sea, the trend of overfishing is opposite to that in the northern seas of Europe since it has been rising since 2003-2005 for those stocks that were assessed (2016). The current situation of Mediterranean and Black Sea's stocks is considered critical with more than 90% of the assessed stocks being overexploited (2016). Guillen et al, (2018) reported worldwide discards to be about 30 million tons, accounting for 23% of the world-wide catches. The establishment of landing obligation (discard ban) is one of the main aspects in the new EU Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), which aims for a gradual elimination of discards of commercially exploited stocks on a case-by-case basis EU (Patermann & Aguilar, 2018). In fact, the extended practice of discarding has been identified as one of the reasons for the failure of the past CFP. Discarding has prevented several fish stock from recovering, despite of the low quotas (EC, 2009). Moreover, the obligation to land all catches and a better use of marine resources are in line with the EU's Europe 2020 Strategy objective of a more resource efficient economy (EC, 2010).

In the Multiannual National Strategic Plans (European Commission, 2016a) for the promotion of sustainable aquaculture, EU Member States quantify objectives (e.g., production growth) for their domestic aquaculture sector based on addressing the strategic priorities and the EMFF funds received. According to the figures presented in MS' Strategic Plans, the estimated projection for aquaculture production in 2020 is an increase of over 300,000 tons (25%) to a total of more than 1.5 million tons (European Commission, 2016b).

4.1.3.3 Forestry and natural habitats

In 2020 the EU28 is estimated to have approximately 183 million hectares of forest and other wooded land corresponding to the 43% of its land area (Bioenergy Europe, 2020), this area has seen steady increases in recent decades (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Evolution of total forest area. Source: (Eurostat)

EU-27 woody sources are estimated in total at almost 284 million tdm, around 87% of which comes from local sources. Sweden, Germany and Finland are the largest producers. The forestry sector apart from the stemwood which has an important contribution in the wood supply, there are other woody tree components that increase the primary supply in 25%. Additionally, very important are the removals from the forests which is the main producer to industrial roundwood and also contributes to the fuelwood in 21,4 %. This number depends on the country level decomposition of biomass. The two main uses of woody biomass are for the material industry and for

energy production. It is important to note that there are some notable circular flows visible in woody biomass flows with woody biomass often undergoing multiple rounds of use and processing before disposal (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Woody biomass flows EU27, 2017 (1000 tdm). Source: (DataM, 2022)

4.1.3.4 Bioenergy

Biomass for energy remains the main source of renewable energy in the EU, accounting for around 60% of all renewable energy. The main sources of supply of bioenergy are from the wood supply (direct and indirect) including logging residues, wood processing residues, fuelwood and wood pellets, followed by agricultural crops and by-products and waste. Regarding consumption and energy carriers, the largest consuming sector is for heating and cooling accounting for around 75% of all bioenergy, 12% for transport biofuels, 13.4% for bioelectricity (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Domestic EU Energy Supply. Source: (DataM, 2022)

Germany, France, Italy and Sweden are the largest bioenergy consumers while Scandinavian countries have the highest bioenergy consumption per capita. In terms of trends, the role of bioenergy has been growing steadily. There are various scenarios for the future, but the amount of bioenergy produced is expected to continue to grow. It is important to note that biomass for energy needs to be sustainably produced while supporting the wider ecosystem.

Figure 25. Share of renewables and bioenergy in gross EU energy consumption. Source: (Eurostat 2018b and NREAP Progress Reports)

Figure 26. EU Bioenergy consumption and projections until 2050. Source: (Eurostat 2018b) (European Commission, 2018b)

Biogas has played a very important role in providing a source of heat and power and is expected to continue playing a vital role in the next years. In the EU more than half (56%) of the gross final energy consumption is for electrical generation.

4.1.3.5 Biomaterials

Biomaterials are derived from renewable biological feedstocks and are processed creating conventional products (e.g., timber and textiles) and advanced products (bioplastics and pharmaceuticals). Biomaterials are a relatively new concept in policy making and currently relatively little data is available on the exact scale of the relevant value chains. In the EU currently, wood-based materials, polymers, textiles, biocomposites are the main biomaterials currently used in the EU.

The most developed biomaterial sector in the EU is based around woody biomass and produces a range of products including materials for construction, furniture, paper/cardboard and cork, in 2013, 189.9 million tons of dry matter of wood were used for biomaterials. In addition, production processes often use materials multiple times where they are downcycled for numerous applications. The production of biopolymers has developed in recent years, but production and consumption levels remain low as compared to fossil-based alternatives. Considerable innovations are taking place through the biorefining of renewable feedstocks for biopolymers as are key to the EU policy and research. For instance, regarding bioplastics, the main current feedstocks are agricultural feedstocks such as maize, sugarcane and wheat. However, the potential of other feedstocks, such as crop residues and algae are being explored. The current main use for bioplastics is in packaging though it is very relevant to other sectors. The most dominant bioplastic currently produced is bio-PET, cellulose acetate, and packaging materials. Bio composites combine two properties yielding a new material. Bio composites, WPCs and NFCs currently account for around 15% of EU composite production and are mainly used in construction and the furniture sector. Fibres are traditionally sourced from cotton, hemp, wool, leather, or natural polymers.

Regarding future trends, in recent years innovations, research and funding in biomaterials have accelerated considerably, in particular for materials that directly replace fossil-based materials such as bioplastics and bio composites. By contrast it is expected that the production of wood-based materials will stay relatively stable.

Figure 27. Bio-based value pyramid. Source: (Stegmann et al., 2020)

Biorefining refers to the processing of biomass into a variety of products including food, fibers, chemicals, fertilizers and biofuels. In recent years advanced biorefineries have been developed that transform feedstocks such as crops, forest resources and algae into chemicals to be used for bio composites, bioplastic and energy. These advanced biorefineries represent a small sector of all biorefineries but are expected to grow rapidly. The below figure represents the 2,362 bio-based industries and biorefineries facilities in the EU which cover the production of: bio-chemicals, biofuels, bio-based composites and fibers, biomethane, pulp and paper, sugar, starch and timber. Bio-based industries employ 3.6 million people and have an annual turnover of €700 billion. (De Schoenmakere et al.,).

Figure 8. Biorefineries distribution in the EU as of March 2018. Purple dots indicate all biorefineries (803 in total) Blue dots indicate the 507 biorefineries producing bio-based chemicals, yellow dots indicate the 363 biorefineries producing liquid biofuels and the green dots indicate the 141 biorefineries producing bio-based composites and fibres. It has to be noted that some biorefineries produce more than one product category and are thus shown in more than one map. Dots in lighter colour in the three last figures indicate facilities that are currently inactive (but not necessarily as permanent status). Most biorefineries correspond with location of chemical industry clusters and location of ports. Highest density of facilities is in Belgium, Netherlands and some highly industrialised regions of Germany, France and Italy. Source: Parisi, C. 2018. Research Brief on biorefineries distribution in the EU. Joint Research Centre.

Figure 28. Biorefineries distribution in the EU as of March 2018 Source: (Joint Research Centre (European Commission), 2020).

Figure 29. Biobased industries and biorefineries by Category in EU27.

Source: (Bio-Based Industry, .)

4.2 National Bioeconomies

4.2.1 Greece

4.2.1.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

Greece's geographical position offers unique prospects for the development of the bioeconomy and circular economy activities, but also there some already existed challenges that the country is facing. Important part on the bioeconomy framework seems to be the agricultural sector, as well as the food processing and the waste management. Additionally, despite the large area that the forestry sector covers in the country, the lack of policy together with the lack of funding have left this sector in a grounded level of impact that was expected higher. Although there are several activities enhancing the bio-based framework from research centers and academic institutions, all the enterprises seem to operate on a small scale. As for the policy section there are some regional policies and strategies that have embedded bioeconomy, but the lack of a national bioeconomy strategy has a clear impact on the Greek bioeconomy development. With a surface of 131,957 km² the 56,31% represents forest and semi-natural areas according to the CORINE land cover data series and another 38,81% is represented by agricultural areas. Although the 80% of the country (terrain) is covered by mountains there is a long coastlines and numerous islands.

Greece, Full trade

Figure 30. Biomass flows in Greece (Gurria et al., 2017)

From the last Sankey diagram that was published by JRC, are captured all the imports, the biomass flows and the exports for Greece. Additionally, biomass supply is directly linked with agriculture with over 90% and relates to the production of food and feed. Smaller quantities of primary woody biomass from forests and smaller quantities are diverted into bio-based market. Bioenergy comes third in terms of biomass use, fueled from woody biomass (logwood) and in lesser extent by imported products, crop residues and crop harvesting residues.

4.2.1.1.1 Food & agriculture

The biomass flows in Greece are mainly based on the agricultural residues divided in primary and secondary residues. In the primary residues we have arable crops, prunings and manure of the livestock production. According to S2Biom, a European project that covered the biomass delivery chain and has been running from 2013 until 2016 together with AgroBioHeat that managed to compare the biomass potential of the agricultural residues in the EU they came to a result that indicates a volume of arable agricultural residues that are produced in annual basis in Greece exceeding in 3 million tons of dry matter. As for the pruning production the estimation from permanent crops is much more complicated than arable crops. There are major difficulties in pruning productivity, depending on multiple factors like varieties, climate, soil conditions and agronomic references. However, the technical pruning potential in Greece it is clearly very high compared to arable crop residues. A major issue for agricultural prunings is that the main management method continues to be open field burning, a technique that is very well known in all the EU region contributing to the local air pollution and potential fire hazard. The volume of this residues is about 450,000 tons per year including large pieces for pruning like branches which may be in the level of 19% of total firewood annually consumption in Greece. Additionally, according to Scarlat et al., (2018) from the spatial analysis that they published they came to the following outcomes:

- Total manure production at 16.9 million tons per year while the collectable volume was about 9.3 million tons.
- The theoretical potential of biogas was 558 million m³ of CH₄.

- The biogas plant capacity in Greece has a potential of 241 MW, with a more realistic estimation around 120 MW which can produce 898 GWh of electricity annually.

According to the Hellenic Association of biogas producers (HABIO) there are 41 biogas plants in Greece operating with agricultural feedstock meaning manure, silage, and other residues, with a capacity of 47.9 Mwe.

Also, another biomass potential residue is the marginal land, which are unused or abandoned land, where according to ELSTAT there are about 355,13 thousand hectares all over the country. According to Gerwin et al., (2018) the estimated capacity of the 14,6% of the marginal lands in Greece correspond to 1,9 million ha which is suitable for biomass cultivation for bioenergy. The energy crops are mainly poplar and switchgrass. Based on the platform that H2020 MAGIC has developed for the marginal lands in Greece the 45% seems to be in Larissa, Achaia, most Epirus, Evritania, Fokida and major parts of Crete and Aegean Island. Although the main factor to consider is that the farmers refuse to cultivate forest species in agricultural land even in marginal land due to the risk to be considered as “forest” land in which there are limitations for exploitations that may apply.

The olive oil sector industries are the most important in the purpose of biomass production from secondary agricultural residues. Most of them are already valorized in energetic or other applications. In the sector of olive oil by-products there are two industries, the olive oil mills that perform the first pressing of olives (2,500 facilities in Greece) and the pomace mills of which there are about 35 in the country where the olive pomace is dried and extract the residual oil with hexane. By this method we have the production of “pirinoxilo”, a mixture of the crushed olive stone and the exhausted olive fruit flesh and skin. According to AgroBioHeat project the technical potential for 2017 was 170 kton of dry matter for olive stones and 403,5 kton of dry matter for exhausted olive cake. Also, the estimation of S2Biom project for 2020 was 182 kton of dry matter.

The by-product of “pirinoxilo” is also self-consumed by the pomace mills in a large volume in order to dry out the pomace they receive and to produce the steam for the secondary oil extraction. According to the Association of Olive Kernel Oil Producers of Greece it was estimated that for an annual production of olive oil that reaches the 250,000 tons, the total quantities of “pirinoxilo” available for the market are about 130,000 tons and can be used for various applications including greenhouses, agro-industries and domestic heating.

Table 1. Estimated production of secondary agricultural residues (S2Biom, AgroBioHeat)

Pressed grape drags	S2Biom estimated on 2020 10 kton, AgroBioHeat 42,5 kton dry matter, and mainly produced from wineries (1000 in Greece)
Rice husks	AgroBioHeat estimated production of 46 kton dry matter in 2017
Peach stones	AgroBioHeat estimated production 19,7 kton dry matter in 2017
Nut shells	AgroBioHeat estimates that the nutshell production in 2017 amounted to 25.1 kton dry matter
Sunflower husks	AgroBioHeat estimates that the technical potential may be around 36.5 kton dry matter
Cotton ginning residues	AgroBioHeat estimates that the cotton ginning residues for 2017 are 70.4 kton dry matter
Cereal brain	S2Biom estimates that the technical potential for cereal bran in Greece / 2020 is 394 kton dry matter

A limitation about the cost estimation of the primary agricultural biomass residues is the fact that no commodity market has been developed in Greece. Additionally, Secondary agricultural residues already have established markets and after a survey AgroBioHeat project made presents some indicative price range below:

Table 2. Secondary Agricultural residues prices. Source: (Karampinis , 2020)

Exhausted olive cake	50 – 80 €/ton
Sunflower husk pellets (imported)	80 – 120 €/ton
Olive stone	50 €/ton
Rice husks:	60 – 80 €/ton
Nut shells:	65 – 120 €/ton
Peach stones	60 – 80 €/ton

4.2.1.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

Another biomass supply in Greek state is the forestry, but although the country has a significant coverage of forests in their territory the direct economic impact is limited to only 0.2% to the national GDP. Additionally, there are primary and secondary biomass resources, but in general it is clear that the current biomass production from forests is not the expected one. This sector is facing some limitation like the lack of modern means and the absence of updated forest management plans.

Table 3. Biomass potential 2020. Source: S2BIOM project.

Final fellings from non-conifer trees	610 kton dry matter
Final fellings from conifer trees	453 kton dry matter
Thinnings from non-conifer trees	601 kton dry matter
Thinnings from conifer trees	447 kton dry matter
Logging residues from final fellings of non-conifer trees	68 kton dry matter
Logging residues from final fellings of conifer trees	81 kton dry matter
Logging residues from thinnings of non-conifer trees	36 kton dry matter
Logging residues from thinnings of conifer trees	46 kton dry matter
Total	2,339 kton dry matter

Secondary biomass resources are from wood processing industries, wood processing by-products which are mostly already utilized for energy production through their upgrade to pellet or by external biomass end-users. According S2Biom project the potential of the secondary biomass resources are presented in the table below.

Table 4. Biomass potential 2020, S2Biom project

Sawdust (conifers)	15 kton d.m
Saw dust (non-conifers)	19 kton d.m
Other residues (conifers)	28 kton d.m
Other residues (non-conifers)	41 kton d.m
Residues from industries producing semi-finished wood-based panels	14 kton d.m
Residues from further wood processing	167 kton d.m
Total	284 kton d.m

4.2.1.2 Innovations and small scale- solutions

- [Procos](#) Sa is a plastic converter producing disposable tableware from paper with bio polymer. The products are certified with “OK compost home” and “OK compost industries” labels as well as a range of disposable wooden tableware.
- [Matric Pack](#) since 2018 produces eco-friendly straws from natural resources and from 2019 also developed paper straws produced only for Greece.
- [PHEE](#) from 2015 this company uses seagrass to produce boards used for furniture, packing, interior decoration, and accessories. Was awarded as one of the most successful start-up with various awards.
- [Staramaki](#) is a social cooperative based in Kilkis, producing drinking straws made from local cereal straw residues. Also, they are working together with a food treasure team on Kafsimo project aiming to collect spend coffee grounds from cafeteria and transform into solid biomass fuel.
- [KIZI STUDIO](#) has launched a series of furniture with panels made from cardoon fibers and natural resins.
- [CHIMAR](#) Hellas is a specialized company that in 1998 patented its first bio-based binder technology and currently provide both chemical binder as well as engineering solutions and R and D services for the production of binders and particle boards.

Very important in the agricultural sector are the cotton ginning plants, because of the fact that Greece is the major cotton producer in EU with more than the 805 of the production. Some of the main ginning plants in Greece are [VIOLAR](#) S.A., [EPILEKTOS](#) S.A. , [Ekkokkistiria Serron](#), [Siarkos](#) S.A..

- [PolyHealth](#) S.A is a company with patented technology, organic and plant originated raw materials without any involvement of organic solvents to product natural phytochemical products.
- [Coffeco](#) is a start-up working on isolation of phenolic compounds from coffee waste, using the extracted phenols as food supplement and to produce pharmaceuticals and cosmetic.
- [Prosper](#) is a spin of company from researchers based in Agricultural University of Athens, aiming to produce 1200 tons per year of ‘fish powder’ from by-products of fish processing. This material has a high nutritional value and flavour.

At the current situation in Greece there is no production of advanced biofuels from cellulosic or lignocellulosic feedstocks. There are only liquid biofuels produced and the main feedstock used for its production are oil seed crops (sunflower and rapeseed) cotton seed and used vegetable cooking oil. Glycerol is the main by-product of biodiesel product and mostly sold to companies for the production of pharmaceuticals or cosmetics.

The JRC “Map for Bio-based industry and biorefineries” 52 currently lists 37 biorefineries facilities in Greece, distributed as follows:

- 19 facilities for liquid biofuels production
- 13 facilities for pulp and paper
- 7 facilities for chemicals
- 5 starch and sugar refineries

Also, apart from the biorefineries that the JRC listed above, there are some regional level bio-based initiatives that have been developed though previous project like FP7 project BIOCLUS, BERST creating the (CLuBe) cluster and the recent example of BIOREGIO. Additionally, there is a list of H2020 project in which there is Greek participation working on innovative solutions for biomass utilization.

- [BioCatPolymers](#)
- [BioSFerA](#)
- [CLARA](#)
- [BioMates](#)
- [Waste4Think](#)
- **BIOFUELS-2G**

- [BioWaste 2 BioPlastic](#)

4.2.1.3 Policy and national strategies

The state of Greece does not have a national bioeconomy strategy until now. However, there are some already existed national or regional strategies that in some topic related to bioeconomy and circular economy.

- **The Greek Smart Specialization Strategy (2014-2020)**
- **The National Energy and Climate Action Plan for 2030 and the 2050 roadmap**
- **The National Strategy on circular Economy and the upcoming ban of single-used plastics.**

The strategies above include some policy measures related to the development of the bioeconomy are outlined in key policy and strategic documents. Additionally, policy document is the “**The National Action Plan for the Circular Economy in Greece**”, creating requirements for the country to accelerate the implementation of actions for the transition to a circular economy framework. In this national plan are included actions focused on the new framework for biofuels products (biomethane), recovery of the biowaste and also, the creation of a National Action Plan for the Bioeconomy. In the 2018 “**National Circular Economy Strategy**” was related to the bioeconomy mentioning to the action plans the need of a circular consumption and a resource management. Another related strategy was the “**National Forestry strategy**”, where one of the main goals recognize the value and enhance the contribution of forest ecosystems to the bioeconomy and circular economy. Also, in “**The National Waste Management Plan 2020-2030**” the strategy was setting goals for waste reduction and recycling which are related to bioeconomy, as well as goals for separate collection biomass from different municipalities increasing the collected amount of biomass to use for energy and biomaterial production. Apart from the national strategies in some regions of Greece the municipalities of Central Macedonia and Crete have developed regional action plans for the promotion of bioeconomy and circular economy. These strategies were developed on terms of the EU projects BIOREGIO and CESME.

4.2.2 Italy

The Italian Bioeconomy relies on all major production (including agriculture, forestry, fisheries, food and beverages production, paper, pulp and tobacco industries, textiles from natural fibers, leather, biopharmaceuticals, green chemistry, biochemicals and bioenergy). The Bioeconomy activities in Italy make a total turnover of EUR 330 billion, and around 2 million employees (*BIT Bioeconomy in Italy*, n.d.). The annual deployed biomass for bioeconomy in Italy stands at 121,725.00 kt in 2015. Of this biomass, 61,226 kt (50%) are imported and 60,499 kt are produced. The most important use of biomass is the food and feed sector with a global consumption of 61,623.00 kt of the total deployed biomass. Second most important sector is represented by losses which alone accounts for more than 30% of total deployed biomass (39,447.00 kt). The third output of the bioeconomy is represented by the bioenergy sector which amounts for 19.646 kt of biomass (15% of the total), mostly represented by consumption of wooden biomass for domestic heating. The fourth and final by biomaterials which only represents 8% of the total deployed biomass (11.078 kt) in 2015 (Kilsedar et al., 2021). The export is negligible in terms of mass but is certainly crucial in terms of turnover for the agri-food sector. Namely, the turnover of food exports in 2020 amounted to EUR 44.9 billion (*7°Censimento Generale Dell’agricoltura: Primi Risultati Meno Aziende Agricole (Ma Più Grandi) e Nuove Forme Di Gestione Dei Terreni*, n.d.). According to the latest JRC technical report the biomass flows for the country of Italy can be depicted in the following Sankey diagram.

Italy, Full trade

Figure 31. Biomass flows in Italy.

(Gurria et al., 2017b)

4.2.2.1 General data on bioeconomy for each sector

1. Agriculture for food and feed production is the most important sector of the bioeconomy, the total turnover is EUR 55.7 billion in 2020, of which 29.5 billion related to crop cultivation, 16 billion to livestock and livestock related products and 16 billion to secondary activities (aquaculture, bioenergy, etc.) (*7°Censimento Generale Dell'agricoltura: Primi Risultati Meno Aziende Agricole (Ma Più Grandi) e Nuove Forme Di Gestione Dei Terreni*, n.d.). Total employment of the sector amounts to 2.755.341, half of which is composed of owners and their families and half by workers and employees.

4.2.2.1.1 Forestry & natural habitats

Forestry sector in Italy is not especially important in terms of turnover (EUR 4.4 billion) but forests cover approximately one third (36%) of the total national surface area and in the last 50 years the total surface area has doubled to reach the current 11 Mio Ha [5]. Total employment of the sector amounts to 0.4 Mio people (of which around 50 thousands forestry workers), and main products are biofuels (above all wood logs and wood chips) with a total annual production of 5 Mio tons per year and 1.5 Mio of m3 of timber (*RaFITALIA Rapporto Sullo Stato Delle Foreste e Del Settore Forestale in Italia*, 2017).

4.2.2.1.2 Aquatic & water systems

Water systems in Italy are mostly related to food and feed production from fishery and aquaculture. In 2018 Italy produced 0.3 million of tons of fish, with a value of EUR 2 billion, mostly resulting from fishery (68%) and to a lesser extent from aquaculture (32%). The whole seafood sector, including processing in 2018 gave jobs to 36,363.00 people OECD, Fisheries and Aquaculture in Italy,(2021). Seaweed production in Italy is still a niche sector, although both food and feed, and pharmaceutical industries already exploits seaweed mostly from import.

4.2.2.1.3 Bioenergy

Bioenergy in Italy is mostly applied to thermal use. For bioenergy we mostly refer to solid and liquid biofuels, biogas, and waste biodegradable fraction. For electric production bioenergy have generated 1.7 Mtoe in 2020 (16.8% of total electric renewable energy production) with a 0.4% growth compared to 2019. In thermal sector bioenergy generate 6.6 Mtoe in 2020 (69% of total thermal renewable energy production) the production (and therefore consumption) falls by 3% compared to 2019 [(RAPPORTO STATISTICO 2020 ENERGIA DA FONTI RINNOVABILI IN ITALIA, n.d.)].

Table 5. Energy production in 2020. Source: (RAPPORTO STATISTICO 2020 ENERGIA.)

Sources	Electrical energy in 2020	Thermal energy in 2020
	Ktoe	Ktoe
Total renewables	Ktoe	9,396
Bioenergy	1,688	6,564
Solid biofuels	585	6,528
Biogas	702	36
Liquid biofuels	401	-

4.2.2.1.4 Biomaterials & bio-based products

Biobased industry in Italy it is still at his preliminary stages of development. The most important market is the biodegradable and compostable packaging and mulch films. In 2021 the industry produced 125 Mio tons of bioplastics, with a turnover of EUR 1 billion and around 3 thousand related jobs. The industry is growing and compared to 2020 it registers a growth of 30% on turnover, 13% on production and around 5% on jobs (Assobioplastics, n.d.).

4.2.2.2 Bioeconomy potential and trends

Agriculture sector is widely developed and rooted in the Italian economy, so is not expected to grow much in the nearest future but to specialize in the production of specialties by exploiting the exposure of the “made in Italy” brand. Nevertheless, the agriculture sector in Italy was historically based on family-run small business (average size of a farm in Italy is 10 ha) and this aspect makes it difficult to develop an economically sustainable exploitation of residues. In the last 20 years however, the number of businesses has fallen from 1,6 Mio to 1,1 Mio and average size has grown from 4,9 to 10 (STRATEGY FOR ENERGY DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA UP TO 2040 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY, n.d.). This trend will make possible higher investments for the residue’s transformation and development of an extensive marketing chain. Considering the significant and traditional presence of olives (approximately 1 Mio. Ha) Vineyards (approximately 0.6 Mio. Ha) and other stone fruits and pome fruit cultivations (approximately 0.5 Mio. Ha), wooden residues will have a great potential to develop (Istituto nazionale di statistica, 2022). Residues from livestock and non-lignified secondary crops, biodegradable fraction of waste are widely exploited for biogas production in fact in Italy there are 1.400 active biogas plants with a production of 2,5 Billion of SCM, about 26 TWh (CIB - Consorzio Italiano Biogas| Consorziobiogas.It, n.d.).

In the near future most of the biogas plants should end the incentive period and potentially be key facilities for biofuels production or block chemicals such as methanol or DME. Forests in Italy have grown in the last 50 years as wood lost importance in the building and energy sector from 1960 to the early 2000 and marginal areas were abandoned by farmers. Logging rate is far from reaching the full potential of a sustainable managed forest as the annual amount of logged wood is only 18% to 34% of the annual wood increment compared to the European average which stands at 62% (Antonio Pepe, Luca Caverni, 2022). The low amount of harvested wood compared to the potential is mostly related to the low profitability of a supply chain lacking a proper processing industry and the characteristics of wooded property that is often unavailable for the timber industry. Trends should evolve in the near future as in 2022 for the first time since 1923 Italy has adopted a consolidated forestry law which should hold to account forest owners for the active sustainable management of forests. Moreover, the recent geopolitical crisis revealed the dependency of the Italian economy for timber and biofuels and both policy makers and companies are now evaluating the possibility to further improve investments in national production. Bioenergy is not expected to grow in terms of energy consumption. The Integrated national energy and climate plan published by the ministry

of economic development foresee a stable trend for bioenergy with a slight reduction. Decarbonization relies only on development of solar and wind power (Ministry of Economic Development & Protection of Natural Resources and the Sea, 2019).

Fishery and aquaculture reach a high level of exploitation in Mediterranean Sea, those sectors are not expected to grow in the coming years, while microalgae and cyanobacteria cultivation in inland bioreactors could grow in the next years especially if synergistically developed with industrial districts with high availability of thermal energy for dehydration.

4.2.2.3 Policies and national strategies

Italy has a bioeconomy strategy even though outdated (last update was in 2017 with objectives set for 2030), (*BIT Bioeconomy in Italy*, n.d.). The Italian Bioeconomy strategy is promoted by the e Italian Presidency of Council of Ministers involving all the relevant government departments (“Economic development”, “Agriculture, Food and Forestry”, “Education, University and Research”, former “Environment, Land and Sea”, now “Ecological transition”) the committee of the Italian Regions, the agency for territorial cohesion and the Italian Technology Clusters for Green Chemistry Agrifood and Blue growth.

The priorities of the action plan are focused on:

- Sustainable agriculture and forestry.
- Sustainable and competitive agri-food sector for a safe and healthy diet.
- Bio-based industries.
- Aquatic living resources and marine and maritime bioeconomy.

Priorities are pursued through a complex R&I agenda flanked by accompanying measures aimed at creating the framework conditions to boost the sector in order to reach the objectives to reach a 20% increase in turnover and employees within 2030, from a total turnover of EUR 250 billion, and around 1.6 million employees to a total turnover of EUR 300 billion, and around 2 million employees in 15 years.

The strategy is well defined and with bold objectives. Moreover, all the relevant stakeholders were involved, and that is a critical factor in a multidisciplinary topic such as the bioeconomy growth plan. However, although an implementation and monitoring plan has been provided with consistent criteria and indicators, more frequent updates would have been useful, and a 2050 target is needed in order to adjust the course and adapt to a sector with such rapid growth and with evolving environmental and geopolitical scenarios (*BIT Bioeconomy in Italy*, n.d.).

4.2.2.4 Small scale biobased solutions

Based on the current state of the economy in Italy, available technologies potential and trends, the most interesting biobased solutions are related to the bioenergy sector, bio-based materials production and biochemicals building block production.

For what concern bioenergy there are three major solutions that could grow in the near future:

1. small district heating (< 5 MWth), cooling and process heat production from local woody biomass obtained from agricultural and forest residues.
2. high-efficiency cogeneration (< 1 MWel) from gasification of agricultural and forest residues and biochar production for soil carbon fixation and fertilization.
3. Bio-methane or Bio-DME production from conversion of biogas plants.

For what concern biobased materials and biochemicals:

1. Bioplastics and BIO-PET production from herbaceous residues and dedicated secondary crops.
2. Bio-DME or Bio-methanol production from conversion of biogas plants.

4.2.3 North Macedonia

4.2.3.1 Food & agriculture

North Macedonia is an agricultural oriented country. This sector has most significant impact on Macedonian's economy. Agribusiness contributes with 7.6% to the country's GDP and with 11.5% in overall employment, including agriculture, forestry, and fisheries (2021). 9.6 % of North Macedonia's total exports in 2021 are made up of agricultural and food products. The EU (50.6 %) and CEFTA countries (32%) are the primary export markets for agricultural and food products. Tobacco (20% of agriculture exports), biscuits and waffles (10% of total exports), canned vegetables (9.5%), wine (9%) and fresh vegetables (8 %) are North Macedonia's top export products. In addition, 47.5 % of North Macedonia's total agricultural imports come from the EU, with the remaining 17.6 % coming from the UK. The main imported products are chocolates and confectionary (9 %), sunflower oil (4.9 %), meat (poultry 5 %, pork 3.5 %, beef 3.1 %), cheese, processed foods, and wheat and flour (Republic of North Macedonia, n.d.). According to the State Statistical Office, total employment in the Agriculture, Forestry and Water management for 2020 was 86 879 employees (Financethink.Mk, 2022)

Table 6. Primary agricultural production of 2021, Republic of Macedonia.

Crop production	Tons
Wheat	243676
Corn	130769
Tobacco	24329
Potato	178233
Onion	63861
Tomato	154164
Pepper	222926
Sweet cherry	4716
Cherry	8372
Apricot	2584
Apple	92863
Pear	6631
Plum	27031
Peach	6205
Walnut	4667
Grape	269131

The most significant biomass sources from Macedonian agriculture are straw, stalks, maize stover, manure, and prunings from permanent crops. The total potential of agricultural plant-based residues is approximately 54 thousand metric tons, delineated from the S2BIOM project study (S2biom.Eu,). These residues are often left on the agricultural plots to degrade under influence of the natural processes, or they are plowed into the soil in order to enrich the soil's organic properties. Furthermore, some of the farmers with the help of small and medium processing equipment for the abovementioned agriculture residues started to produce pellets and briquettes in order to compact the residues for transport and further use as feedstock for heat generators.

In the food-processing segment in North Macedonia, the secondary residues are the following: husks, animal tissue, oilcakes, peelings, etc. These residues come from the mill and bakery industry, confectionery industry, oil processing and production industry, fruit and vegetable processing industry, dairy industry, fish canning industry, meat processing industry and alcohol industry. All of the residues can have further commercial uses as animal feed or bioproducts. Some of the residues, mainly plant-based, are reused in a similar way as the primary residues from agriculture, by incorporating the biomass in the agricultural plots or creating a suitable feed mix for cattle and other domestic animals. The most utilized secondary residue source for creating animal feed is the sunflower oilcake. In the case of North Macedonia, there is no available information about the quantity of secondary residues and further commercial uses of biomass from the food processing industry.

4.2.3.2 Forestry/natural habitats systems

In North Macedonia, there are roughly 1.1 million ha of forests and forestland, which are distinguished by a high species diversity, low quality, and slow yearly growth. 90% of the forests are deciduous, more than 70% are coppiced, and over 90% of the forestland is controlled by the state. The public company "Macedonian Forests," which is made up of regional divisions that encompass the entire territory of the Republic of North Macedonia, is in charge of managing the state-owned portion. 11% of the total forest area is made up of private forests. Beech is the dominating species, followed by a number of oak species. The estimated total wood reserve is 70 million m³, and the expected yearly growth is 1 million m³. A very substantial portion of the area that is classified as a forest is a Mediterranean-style forest with smaller trees and plants (MACEDONIAN SECOND BIENNIAL UPDATE REPORT ON CLIMATE CHANGE, 2017). During agroforestry activities (deforestation, cutting off dead or diseased trees, clearing pathways, etc.), the residues come in form of small branches, barks, roots, and lower parts of the trees, woodchips, etc. In 2021, the total volume of sawn wood is 700,000 m³, from which 120,000 m³ is technical wood, 549,000 m³ is firewood and 31,000 m³ is waste (residues). About 130 thousand m³ of industrial wood are treated annually in North Macedonia. The processing of wood is done by more than 100 entities. The majority of them are small sawmills. Many large businesses specialize in the manufacture of furniture and carpentry, while others work with the main and secondary processing of wood.

Woodchips, sawdust, bark, cutouts from the ends of logs, splinters, fine wood dust, and other byproducts are among the wastes produced during the processing of wood. Larger businesses that deal with primary and secondary wood processing are thought to process around 40.000 m³ of technical wood annually. As a result, they generate roughly 15,000 m³ of wood residue (S2biom.Eu)

4.2.3.3 Aquatic & water systems

According to State Statistical Office of North Macedonia, the total catch of fish in 2021 was 2 171 537 kg and compared to 2020 it increased by 4.1%. Of the total catch in 2021, 65.6% were cold-water fish, and the share of warmwater fish was 34.4%. Compared to 2020, the catch of cold-water fish was higher by 1.8%, and the catch of warmwater fish increased by 7.9%. Fish production and catch are based on aquaculture production (92.9%), commercial fishing 5.8%, and recreational fishing only 1.3%. In 2021, compared to 2020, an increase in fish catch was observed in all types of fishing. In 2021, 1 815 million fish eggs were produced and juvenile fish with a total weight of 132 403 kg. Production of fish eggs in a controlled environment in 2021 decreased by 14.2%, while the weight of juvenile fish increased by 21.2%. Of the fish species, rainbow trout is the most bred. According to the method of fish farming, fishponds, tanks, raceways and cages are the most used facilities. The number of employees in fish production in 2021 was 415, of which 315 were men. In 2021, 12 582 people were engaged in recreational fishing, of which only 412 were women. The methodology for fisheries and aquaculture statistics is in accordance with Regulation No. 762/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union. The area of fish farming methods in 2021 is the following: Ponds – 10655 hectares; Tanks and raceways – 9980 m³; Enclosures – 310 hectares; and Cages – 6625 m³ (Republic of North Macedonia)

The Law for Fisheries and Aquaculture in Chapter 3.13 regulates the area of fisheries in the context of the blue economy but taking into account the fact that North Macedonia is landlocked, much of the European legislation is not applicable. The implementation of the fisheries legislation will prepare the administration and operators for

participation in the common fisheries policy, which includes market policy, resource and fleet management, inspection and control, structural activities and state aid control. Adaptation to the Common Fisheries Policy of the European Union includes the application of various technical measures and the establishment of an appropriate system for inspection, supervision and control, a system for dealing with illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, as well as co-financing mechanisms. The goal is to ensure greater control and sustainability of fish and water resources, easier placement on the European market, utilization of funds from the European Maritime Fund and the Fisheries Fund by fishermen and fish processors, as well as protection of endangered fish species (European Commission).

4.2.3.4 Bioenergy

Biomass is usually a domestic product in North Macedonia, which does not depend on the movement of prices at the global level, and thus represents an independent way of supplying energy. According to the energy balance, biomass accounts for 6% of the total primary energy in North Macedonia, i.e., 9.5% of the total energy consumption. The most used biomass resource in North Macedonia is wood. Biomass, in the form of wood or coal, is almost exclusively used in the domestic sector. North Macedonia has great potential for using biogas from animal manure for energy purposes, as well as the production of biofuel from vegetable crops.

The largest company for fuel distribution in Macedonia in 2007 opened a facility for biodiesel production with a maximum capacity of 20,000 tons of B100 (pure biodiesel) meant for diesel engines and combustion chambers. The biodiesel is made from oilseed rape (Biodiesel Plant - Makpetrol, 2022).

Regarding the heating systems and energy consumption in households, in 2019 the Macedonian households used 23,309 m³ of wood residual from orchards and other agricultural activities, 1,452 tons of wood residuals and 77,250 tons of wood formed as pellets and briquettes (Republic of North Macedonia). In this context, one of the most reliable and most occurring sources for generation bioenergy is the plant-based residuals from agroforestry.

4.2.3.5 Biomaterials & bio-based products

These are derived from renewable biological feedstocks are processed creating conventional products (e.g., timber and textiles) and advanced products (bioplastics and pharmaceuticals). North Macedonia bio-based industry is in its very early stage of development. The bio-based industries are either small-scale, focused on a specific product with low production quantity or they are in the stage of planning.

List of existing bio-based products from North Macedonia: (S2biom.Eu, n.d.)

- [Diesel fuel from residues](#)
- Edible packaging films for food packaging (Милосављева et al., n.d.).
- [Soaps from cold pressed flaxseed/pumpkin/sesame/black cumin chia seeds oil](#)
- [Reed briquettes](#)
- [Bio-hygienic aloe tights](#)

Biomass utilization initiatives

- Utilization of wood residues from local private forest owners for school heating system in Berovo municipality (Domac et al., n.d.)
- Utilization of agricultural residues (cereal straws) for school heating system in Mogila municipality (*The Municipal Building and Schools Are Heated with Pellets from Waste Straw Evening ...1963 | Yesterday MK,*)

4.2.3.6 National policies

The principal entities and regulatory agencies in North Macedonia that adopt and carry out the country's policy framework related to bioeconomy themes are:

1. Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy (*Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of North Macedonia*, n.d.)

2. Agency for Financial Support of Agriculture and Rural Development (*Agency for Financial Support of Agriculture and Rural Development, n.d.*)
3. The IPARD Program 2021-2027 (*IPARD Programme 2021-2027, 2017*)
4. National Extension Agency (*Агенција За Поттикнување На Развојот На Земјоделството | Агенција За Поттикнување На Развојот На Земјоделството, n.d.*)
5. Agricultural Market Information System(*Agricultural Market Information System, n.d.*)

The main document for guidance of the agriculture production and rural development is the National strategy for agriculture and rural development for the period 2021-2027 (“National Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development for the Period 2021-2027 ,” n.d.). The main objectives of the strategy are to ensure the sustainable development of rural areas and boost the international competitiveness of agricultural production and the agro-food industry. The Strategy represents the country’s ongoing efforts to promote agricultural development, help the agricultural industry in achieving a level of competitiveness that would enable it to meet the demands of an open and fluid market, and enhance rural area development. Concerning energy, the Energy Development Strategy was adopted in December 2019 aligned with the five dimensions of the EU Energy Union as it outlines six strategic goals for North Macedonia that are mapped along five energy pillars (*Energy Development Strategy for the Republic of North Macedonia until 2040, 2022*)

4.2.4 Slovenia

4.2.4.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

In 2017, 131,719 people were employed in the bioeconomy in Slovenia. More than half (58.1%) were employed in agriculture, 14.1% in food production, 7.6% in wood processing and processing and 6.3% in forestry. All other industries employ three percent or less of people, which is a total of less than 14% of all employees in the bioeconomy (31).

Figure 32. Structure of employment in bioeconomy sectors in Slovenia in 2017. Source: (Ronzon et al., 2020)

The added value of the bioeconomy in Slovenia amounted to €2,333 million in 2017, which represents approximately 0.5% of the added value of the bioeconomy in the EU27. Figure 32 shows the structure of added value in the bioeconomy in Slovenia by sectors. From the point of view of added value, agriculture and food production have the greatest importance in the bioeconomy, each contributing a fifth of the added value to the total added value (20% and 19.5%). Production of pharmaceutical raw materials and preparations (17%), forestry (13%) and processing and processing of wood (10%) also have a more pronounced importance in the (potential)

bioeconomy sectors. Paper production contributes slightly less than 6% to the total added value of the bioeconomy, the contribution of the remaining industries is less than 4% and amounts to approximately 10% in total.

Figure 33. Structure of value added in bioeconomy sectors in Slovenia in 2017. Source: (Ronzon et al., 2020)

Slovenia, Full trade

Figure 34. Biomass flows in Slovenia. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017)

4.2.4.1.1 Food & agriculture

Natural limitations (58% of utilized agricultural area is dominated by grassland, three quarters of agricultural land is located in areas with natural and other restrictions) determine the scope and structure of primary agricultural production.

Table 7. Area (ha) and shares (%) of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by land categories (Source: SORS, 2021).

Use of agricultural land	Farm Structural Survey 2016	
	Area (ha)	Share (%)

Arable land	176.518	36,8
Nurseries and mother plants	288	0,1
Intensive orchards	3.856	0,8
Extensive orchards	6.405	1,3
Olive groves	1.037	0,2
Vines	15.241	3,2
Permanent grasslands and meadows	276.244	57,6
Total Utilised Agricultural Area	479.589	100,0

Two-thirds of agricultural holdings are engaged in livestock production, where (increasingly specialized) cattle breeding for meat and milk production dominate. Animal production, together with own feed production, contributes the largest share (56%) to the value of agricultural production. In terms of the role of agriculture as a key link in the food supply chain and the utilization of the added value potential, it is worth noting that in the above-mentioned branches of agriculture, almost a third of the total production is exported as a basic raw material (raw milk or live animals). On the other hand, even in the sectors facing steep growth in demand (e.g., fresh vegetables, organic food), the supply-side is struggling to establish systems suitable for that would be able to supply the most frequent retail formats. This observation can be extended to the entire agri-food sector in Slovenia: weak vertical integration along the food value chain, is a key obstacle in the operation of the Slovenian food system.

Table 8. Structure of agricultural holdings in Slovenia with respect to the production types (Source: SORS, 2021).

Production types	Farm Structural Survey 2016	
	Number of farms	Share (%)
Crop production	13.413	19,2
Vegetable production	432	0,6
Permanent plantations (orchards, vine)	9.189	13,1
Grazing livestock	24.983	35,7
Pig breeding and poultry	410	0,6
Mixed plant production	5.720	8,2
Mixed livestock production	3.793	5,4
Mixed arable & livestock production	11.962	17,1
Total	69.902	100,0

4.2.4.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

Slovenia is one of the most forested European countries, as the forest covers more than half of the area, the forest cover is as much as 58.2%. Most of the forests are located in the area of beech (44%), fir-beech (15%) and beech-oak forests (11%), all of which have a relatively strong production capacity. Slovenia ranks among the European countries with the lowest share of national forests. Today, 76% of forests in Slovenia are privately owned, 21% of forests are owned by the state and 3% of forests are owned by local communities. Private forest estates are small, the average area is only 2.9 ha. Only 11% of private owners in Slovenia own a forest larger than five hectares, and

they manage more than half of privately owned forest land. This is reflected in a relatively low utilization of wood potential (60-70%). In the last decade, Slovenian forests have been affected by a chain of intense weather events (large-scale ice breaks in 2014, storms in 2017), combined with intense attack of bark beetles, has irreversibly interfered with the species structure of the forests (drastically thinning the stands of conifers, especially spruce). Future projections, considering the combined impact of above events and climate change forecast increase of hardwood potential, particularly from the increasing share and faster growth of the beech forests. The structure of the production of forest wood assortments in Slovenia is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. The structure of the production of forest wood assortments in Slovenia in 2017

	Conifers (m3)	Deciduous trees (m3)	Total (m3)
Logs	2,200,000	295,000	2,495,000
Wood for pulp and boards	532,000	400,000	932,000
Another round industrial wood	20,000	50,000	70,000
Firewood	170,000	943,000	1,113,000
Total	2,922,000	1,688,000	4,610,000

The increase in felling from 2014 onwards (in 2014-2016, the annual felling at the annual level of 6 million m³ meant a 50% increase) was largely due to conifers, whose share in the felling structure was around 70%. Among conifers, logs dominate the production of forest wood assortments with a share of 75%, wood for pulp and boards represents a further 20%. More than half of hardwood wood (56%) is currently used for firewood, the rest is evenly divided between wood for pulp and boards and logs. The total share of round industrial wood amounts to around 2% of the total production.

The largest domestic consumer of round wood is the sawn wood industry (over 1 million m³), followed by the wood composites, mechanical pulp and chemical industries with a total processing volume of around 0.5 million m³. Large consumers of round wood are households, which annually consume over one million m³ of wood for firewood. With this, the domestic consumption of wood is more or less rounded up, while all the remaining part of forest and wood production is intended for export. With the annual volume of exports, Slovenia is at the level of 3 million. Slovenia is a prominent exporter of unprocessed round wood, which is particularly evident in the coniferous log category, the volume of which in 2017 amounted to 1.3 million m³. Looking from the viewpoint of the overall economic performance of the forest-wood related bioeconomy in Slovenia, the current situation is not favorable. Improvements are sought in particular in terms of a higher share of harvested round wood processed domestically, and in the strengthening of more technologically advanced alternatives to the current uses of round wood.

In order to assess the market potentials of the forest-timber chain, the information about the theoretical potential of forests needs to be subtracted by own consumption by forest owners for their own needs, such as construction wood and firewood). According to the assessments, (Mavsar et al., 2021), the largest differences between the estimated potentials and the quantities that actually entered the market are recorded for wood of lower quality. From the point of view of the long-term perspective, this is the category that will gain in importance with changes in forest stands (increasing proportion of beech). Unexploited possibilities are therefore especially in the categories of wood, which are a suitable input raw material for biorefining processes and the subsequent production of new bio-based materials.

Secondary sources of raw materials (waste biomass, wood, lignocellulosic fibers) that are produced in the processes of extraction, processing and consumption in the forest-wood-paper chain are also prospective raw materials for adding value in the cascade processing process. In 2017, the total amount of processed wood waste amounted to almost 119 thousand tons.

The processing consisted of incineration and co-incineration of waste as fuel (36%), recycling including composting of waste (10%), and the rest (54%) was intended for other preprocessing methods.

The potential of logging residues for collection and processing in industrially relevant quantities is limited, as the removal of logging residues in (predominant) tractor harvesting is not cost-efficient. In addition to this, most of the logging residues in mechanical logging and harvesting are used for soil protection. The greatest bio-economic potential in this category can be attributed to bark, which by volume represents around 20% of the cut.

It is an important category of raw materials for bio-based products due to its content (e.g., tannins) and is also a good structural material for composting biogenic waste. We also point out the (niche) commercial potential of logging residues, such as knots and bark of certain tree species, which, with their rich content of polyphenols, have wide applicability in the chemical and pharmaceutical industry, as well as nutritional supplements. The bio-economic potential of residues in wood processing is eloquently testified by the data on material yield, which in the primary processing of log wood into sawn assortments amounts to approximately 50%, while in the production of solid wood furniture it varies between 5 and 20%. When we add to this the discarded wood, we arrive at the current annual amount of processing of 40,000 tons. The predominant ways of using discarded wood and wood residues today are disposal in the form of inert waste and incineration in domestic boilers. In both cases, it is a questionable use in terms of harmful effects on the environment, low energy and practically no material utilization. Alternatives to the current use of wood residues and discarded wood have already been tested in practice: various processing procedures (physico-chemical, thermal and electrochemical procedures), production of composites, thermal processing into activated carbon or wood gas, biorefining (processing into methanol, ethanol), use in agriculture and environmental applications (bedding, mulch, greening of degraded areas), last but not least also energy use in specialized heating devices.

Considering the fact that more than half (57%) of the raw materials in the Slovenian paper industry come from paper for recycling, we can say that it is an industry that already works largely in line with the principle of circularity. In the production and processing of paper or cardboard, various wastes are generated, which represent a secondary source of biomass or cellulose fibers. The main sources of waste biomass are primary sludge (generated during the removal of printing ink from recycled fibers), secondary sludge (generated during the wastewater treatment process), wood waste (generated in paper mills with integrated wood production) and smaller amounts of paper dust (generated during paper cutting). Paper mills use part of the waste biomass as an energy source in their own production, while significant amounts of ash remain. The delivery of primary sludge to different consumers for further use is decreasing due to various reasons, so the need for cross-border disposal is increasing, which is an expensive and unsustainable solution. Primary sludges offer several more interesting alternatives depending on their physical, chemical and microbiological properties. Sludges with a high carbohydrate content are suitable for the production of biofuels and as fertilizers in agriculture, while sludges with a predominantly inorganic character can be used in the construction industry. Due to the higher content of organic matter, secondary sludge is interesting for the production of biogas and, in combination with waste ash, as a building material.

4.2.4.2 Policies and national strategies

The adoption of joint strategic guidelines in 2012 and its amendment in 2018, the bioeconomy represents strategic development priorities of the EU, combines the goals of the reduction of the society's dependence on fossil fuel and the development of sectors that produce and add value to the biomass based on knowledge and considering the environment and nature conservation goals. Slovenia in contrast with the other EU countries is one of the member states that are lagging behind. However as in most of the EU countries, Slovenia has many policies addressing the bioeconomy which are developed and structured by different actors. Because of the fact that bioeconomy covers a variety of sectors, we have more than one ministry that have developed a strategy plan.

Table 10. Current national bioeconomy-related strategies and programming documents in Slovenia. Source: University of Ljubljana.

Existing national Bioeconomy related strategy document (year of adoption)	Leading ministry	Bioeconomy related goals* addressed					
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	
Implementation plan for the decarbonisation of Slovenia through the transition to a circular economy (2022)	Ministry of the Environment and Spatial planning	+	+	+	(+)	(+)	
Draft Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan for Slovenia (2018)			+	+			
Framework Programme for the Transition to a Green Economy (2015)		(+)	+	+		(+)	
Roadmap towards the Circular Economy in Slovenia (2018)			+	+	(+)	(+)	
National Environment Protection Programme with programmes of measures until 2030 (2020)				+	+		+
Waste Management Program and Waste Prevention Program (2022)				+	+	+	
Slovenia's Smart Specialization Strategy 2030** (2021)	Ministry of Economic Development and Technology	+	+		+	(+)	
Slovenian Development Strategy 2030 (2017)		(+)	+	(+)	+	(+)	
Implementation document of measures for the development of the wood processing industry until 2030 (2022)		+	+			(+)	
Resolution: Our food, rural areas and natural resources after 2021 (2020)	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food	+	(+)	+	+	+	
Operational programme of the Resolution on National Forest Programme 2022-2026 (2022) **		+	+	+		+	
Strategy for less food losses and food waste in the food supply chain (2021)		+	+	+	+	+	
National CAP Strategic Plan for Slovenia 2023-2027** (2021)		+	(+)	+	+	+	
National research and innovation strategy 2021-2030** (2021)	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport						

*The matrix presents which EU bioeconomy strategy (2018) objectives are covered by the bioeconomy related strategy at national level: *Creating jobs and maintaining competitiveness in bioeconomy sectors (1); Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources (2); Mitigating and adapting climate change (3); Ensuring food security (4); Managing natural resources sustainably (5)*. Sign + denotes full compliance with the EU bioeconomy objective and (+) denote partial compliance.

** Draft document, public consultation undergoing

In the table above lists the current strategies and programs documents with implications for bioeconomy in Slovenia. Strategies and programming documents dealing with horizontal issues (e.g., decarbonization, energy,

circular economy) and topics dealing with the protection of the environment, climate change and nature are coordinated by the Ministry of environment and Spatial Planning. The Ministry of Economic Development and Technology is responsible for the coordination of the work on strategies and programs aimed at improving the technological level, and competitiveness of the national economy (smart specialization, industrial development). In Slovenian context, it is important to note that the supporting policies for wood industry is located at the same ministry. Strategic and programming work on agriculture- and (remaining) forestry-based value chains take place under the responsibility of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food. The list of bioeconomy-related strategies is augmented by the National research and innovation strategy, that falls under the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, Science and Sports.

4.2.4.3 Small scale biobased solutions

Public and private institutes specialized in the bioeconomy sectors are based in Slovenia providing research and development. The National institute of Chemistry, the Josef Stefan Institute, the Slovenian Forestry Institute, and the National Institute of Biology are some of the public institutions working on bioeconomy. Additionally, there are some private research institutes providing research like the Pulp and Paper institute, the Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering institute and departments of Universities (University of Ljubljana, University of Maribor, University of Primorska).

Figure 35. Small-scale biobased solution for rural farms converting waste substrates into valuable algae biomass.

Also, there are some already existing organizations specialized in bioeconomy representing different sectors:

1. Circular Change which is a non-profit organization with a strong international network servicing as the best entry point for circular economy projects across Europe.
2. InnoRenew CoE: Conducting research about renewable materials and sustainable building and they are transferring their scientific knowledge into industrial practice. They focus their research activities on innovative and interdisciplinary approaches of wood and its use.
3. SusChem Slovenia: Their mission is to initiate and inspire European chemicals and biochemicals innovation to respond effectively to societal's challenges by providing sustainable solutions.

4. AlgEn, algal technology centre: AlgEn is committed to be an active participant in the blooming area of algal technologies. Internal research and development activities are being complemented by components and know-how of partners into effective solutions.
5. Acies Bio,BIA Separations: Conducting research and innovation work in industrial biotechnology, strong accent of innovation work attributed in particular to biopharmaceuticals and functional food and feed ingredients.

Small scale biobased solution is based on cultivating algae in waste streams and utilizing the biomass for biofertilizers, biopesticides and biostimulants in agriculture. The solution can be used in farms or small biogas plants. In biogas plants, the utilisation of resulting liquid digestate represents many practical problems as it is very dilute, and this causes logistic problems (storage, transportation) and agrotechnical problems (flushing the soil nutrient holding capacity, leaching of nutrients to underground). While the solid phase of biogas digestate is generally utilised as a conventional fertiliser, liquid phase is consequentially more frequently treated as wastewater than used for fertilisation. Additional problems emerge from the fact that biogas feedstock is frequently brought-in from different locations and return of fertilizers to the same area is simply not possible.

We envisioned a solution by growing algae in the liquid phase of the biogas digestate to treat it to acceptable levels for re-use or safe release to the environment as well as stabilise nutrient content in biomass. Produced algal biomass can be used as biogas feedstock or valorised in feed, bioplastics, bio-stimulants, bio-fertilisers etc. Additionally, algae and cyanobacteria can be used as soil bioremediation and long-lasting source of macro- and microminerals that lack in the soil or are not available to the plants.

To produce algae biomass for food or animal feed, digestate or farm's waste streams can be pre-treated to achieve higher quality biomass complying with regulations as well as more stable production.

4.2.5 Romania

4.2.5.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

Romania's area covers a total of 238 400 km². Both agricultural land (more than 13.4 million ha) and forests land (nearly 6.9 million ha) covered more than 85% of the country's territory (56.3% and 29.1%, respectively) in 2019 (BIOEAST,). In 2017, the total supply of biomass in Romania added up to approximately 62,5 million tons of dry matter (tdm). The agriculture sector is the biggest producer of domestic biomass with 72% of the total, followed by forestry with 28% of the dry matter content.

- The bioeconomy in Romania employed around 2.31 million people in 2019 (*DataM - European Commission*). This represented 26.6% of total workplaces in Romania.
 - 80.9% in the Agricultural sector (1.87 million people)
 - 8.1% in the Food, beverage, and tobacco sector (0.18 million people)
 - 4% in the Wood products and furniture sector (0.09 million employees) + 2.5% in the Forestry sector (0.05 million people)
 - 3.1% in the Bio-based textile industry (0.07 million people)
 - 3.9% are represented by sectors such as Biobased chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber, paper industry and fishing and aquaculture.

Figure 36. Employment by sector in Romania, 2019. Source: (JRC)

Turnover of bioeconomy sectors: 43 billion EUR (in 2019)

In Romania, agriculture, the manufacture of food, beverage and tobacco, wood products and bio-based furniture were the largest bioeconomy turnover generators, altogether generating 83,5% of the total bioeconomy turnover in Romania.

In Romania the primary biomass production sector, i.e., agriculture, forestry, fishing, and aquaculture alone contributed to 43.2% of the overall bioeconomy turnover, 34.2% of overall bioeconomy turnover came from food processing industry. About 11% of turnover came from manufacture of wood products and bio-based furniture, 4.3% from manufacture of bio-based textiles and the rest 7.3% of the overall bioeconomy turnover was generated from other bio-based manufacturing industries (i.e., the manufacture of paper, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber, liquid biofuels as well as bio-based electricity).

Figure 37. Turnover by sector in Romania, 2019 in million euros. Source: (JRC)

Figure 38. Value-added by sector (2019) in million euros.

Source: (JRC)

Figure 39. Biomass flows in Romania. Source: BIOMASS project, European Commission. Source: (JRC)

4.2.5.1.1 Food & agriculture

In 2018, Romania’s agricultural biomass total supply (in net trade figures) amounted to approximately 62 million tons of dry vegetal biomass equivalents. This biomass is sourced in the form of crop production 58%, harvested crop residues (18%), grazed biomass (12%) and imports of agricultural products (11%). The crop production is estimated at 36 million tons of dry biomass and harvested crop residues provide an additional 11 million tdm of biomass. 7,7 million tons of biomass are grazed in pastures and meadows. (Market_Analysis_in_the_Romanian_Agricultural_Sector)

Figure 40. Agricultural Biomass flows. Source: (JRC)

Food and feed are the most important category in terms of biomass use, adding up to 29% of the biomass, 17% for energy use and only 8% as biomaterials. If losses or biomass for which a specific use cannot be estimated are not considered, approximately 44% of the available biomass is used for food and feed, with biomass for energy and biomaterials accounting for 26% and 12% of the identified biomass uses respectively.

The biomass used for food and feed products is almost entirely of agricultural origin. 39% of the total agricultural biomass supply (net trade, expressed in dry matter) was used as food and feed in 2018. Approximately 81% of the total biomass for food and feed uses is used as animal feed & bedding for the production of animal-based food, while approximately 18% is directly consumed as plant-based food or is food wasted before consumption. Only 1.6% of the biomass supply of agricultural origin is used for energy purposes (bioenergy), representing 12.4 million tdm.

Romania is one of the countries with the most pronounced agrarian profile in the EU. 53.11% of the population lives in predominantly rural regions (around 10 million inhabitants).

- Rural regions cover around 67.8% of the Romanian territory.
- The agricultural sector is characterized by low productivity.
- 99.24% of Romanian farms do not have legal status, operating mainly as individual agricultural producers.
- High number of very small non-commercial farms, with a very small economic size
- Out of the 3.4 million farms, there are only 0.5 million viable commercial farms: 93.7% of them are small farms (less than 20ha), 4.6% medium farms (20-100 ha), and 1.7% are large farms (>100 ha)
- Farmland is highly fragmented (average 3.65 ha/farm)
- Ageing population in Romanian's agriculture, low degree of openness to innovation and requalification
- 64.9% of the agricultural industry output value comes from crop production (mainly wheat, grain maize, vegetables, and horticultural products).
- Animals and animal products count for 24.1% of total agricultural production, with milk and pigs accounting for the greatest share of output value.
- High volatility of prices (both for products sold and inputs bought by farmers), weak negotiating power → more variable income for farmers.
- Agriculture income has been below the average income levels of other sectors of the economy.

4.2.5.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

The supply of roundwood was estimated at approximately 8,4 million tdm in 2017, of which at least 90% was sourced domestically. This supply was complemented with 1 million tdm of post-consumer wood, 12.6 million tdm uncategorized wood and 2 million tdm of by-products of unreported origin (*The Forest-Based Sector in Romania*).

Figure 41. Forestry biomass flows Romania. Source: (JRC)

- Wood is used by 4,4 million families in rural areas and the forest sector and associated wood processing industry represent up to 5% of the GDP, being the second most important employer in rural areas after agriculture.
- The Romanian forest-based industrial sector has short, classical value-added chains. Excepting some big industrial facilities producing highly processed wood products and furniture, the end of the supply chain is represented by small companies, mainly with domestic capital and rather modest economic performance, which uses classical technologies and activates in a very prescriptive and regulatory environment with limited access to credits and EU programs for innovation and technology.
- Wood products include sawn wood, lumber, pulp and paper, panel and veneer, and furniture.
- The primary wood processing industry, excluding furniture production, has about 7500 operational companies.
- Approximately 92% of all wood processing companies are SMEs.

4.2.5.1.3 Bioenergy, biomaterials & bio-based products.

Most of the biomass used as biofuels continues to be woody biomass. In 2017, 13 million tdm of directly or indirectly gathered woody biomass were estimated to have been used for energy, representing 15% usage from the total biomass. Almost all of the biomaterials also have an origin in forestry activities with the biggest component being solid wood products. In 2017, approximately 6 million tdm of biomass were used for biomaterials (Scarlat et al., 2011).

Romania, Full trade

Figure 42. Biomass flows in Romania. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b)

Romania, biomass is a promising source of renewable energy, given its high potential and its varied use. The biomass resources that can be used to produce energy are very diverse.

- The amount of agricultural and forest residues available for bioenergy in Romania was estimated at 228.1 PJ on average, of which 137.1 PJ was from annual crop residues, 17.3 PJ residues from permanent crops and 73.7 PJ/year from forestry residues, firewood, and wood processing by-products.
- A part of the biomass residues, mainly firewood, forestry and wood processing residues and residues from agriculture is currently used in Romania.
- Biomass plays an important role in the residential sector for space heating in households, tertiary sector-hotels, schools and other public buildings mainly in the mountain areas and to a lesser extent for district heating and for process heat in wood processing. Traditional wood heating is well developed, especially in rural areas, for direct burning (in stoves and ovens), for space heating, cooking and hot water preparation. Firewood is mainly used in the areas where is easily available, especially in the mountain and hilly areas.

Out of the total biomass consumption for energy in Romania of 116 PJ, about 64.5 PJ is derived from wood residues and 53.5 PJ from agricultural residues.

4.2.5.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

The number of employees in the bioeconomy sector decreased significantly between 2008 and 2019, mainly due to the significant decrease in the population employed in agriculture. The low incomes from agriculture have reduced the number of people employed in this sector, as part of the workforce migrated to other sectors in the country or to other countries in the European Union. The phenomenon of population aging also contributed to this phenomenon, as well as the tendency to concentrate the agricultural lands. In fact, this reduction in the population employed in agriculture is a normal phenomenon and it is expected to continue in the next period.

Reductions were also registered in other sectors of bioeconomy (food industry, textile industry). Only the pioneering sectors of bioeconomy recorded (insignificant) increases: biofuels and bioelectricity.

Between 2008 and 2019, there were no significant increases in employment in any of the sectors of the bioeconomy, only in the forestry, paper and biochemical, biopharmaceutical and bioplastics sectors, employment remained relatively constant. Instead, there were significant reductions in the following sectors: agriculture (977.000 people, respectively 34,4%), biobased textile (61.860 people, 46,6%), fishing and aquaculture (29,8%,

38.680 people) wood and furniture products (37.280 people, 28,8%) and food, beverages and tobacco (22.660 people, 10,9%).

Figure 43. Employment in Romania. Source: (JRC)

The turnover of the Romanian bioeconomy remained relatively constant in the period 2008- 2019, though registering slight fluctuations. The economic crisis of 2009 also had a negative impact on the bioeconomy, the sector recording its lowest value (31.55k million Euros, compared to 39.32k million Euros in the previous year, the decrease being about 20%). There have been declines in other years as well, but those could not be attributed to an economic crisis, but to some conjectural factors, such as the falling prices of some products on the world market (agricultural products, for example).

Romania's contribution to the total turnover of the EU bioeconomy was low due to the high share of agriculture in the total bioeconomy sector (low value-added activity). The analysis of the turnover of the Romanian bioeconomy by activity sectors indicates a much lower contribution of agriculture (38.3%), compared to the contribution of this sector to the employment in the bioeconomy sector (81%). Important contributions also had food, beverages and tobacco (34.2%) and wood and furniture products (11%). Obviously, the new sectors had the lowest contributions to the turnover of the bioeconomy sector: biofuels and bioelectricity (less than 4.2%).

Figure 44. Turnover by sector. Source: (JRC)

4.2.5.3 Policies and national strategies

In Romania, there is not yet a dedicated national bioeconomy strategy. It is the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADR) responsible for implementing the government program and strategy, with a role in developing and implementing the national sectoral strategy in the following areas: agriculture and food industry,

rural development, land reclamation and related fields, such as: specialized scientific research, conservation and sustainable management of soils and plant and animal genetic resources, as well as bioeconomy.

One of the government's objectives is to support agricultural research, agricultural information and advisory services in agriculture.

In the field of bioeconomy, MADR long-term and medium-term strategy for research, development and innovation (RDI) has the following main objectives: assessing the long-term and medium-term feasibility of the national bio-economic potential to produce non-food bio-resources under the impact of global climate change; eco-innovative approaches to the development of new agricultural technologies. MADR also provides grants for sectoral research projects, which bring together consortia of research and development units, universities, and professional organizations.

For the years 2022–2023, it is desired to achieve the following objectives:

- National Bioeconomy Strategy.
- SRIA for bioeconomy.
- Activation and use of the Electronic Stakeholder Platform in the field, both at national and macro-regional level.
- Development of research projects and attracting EU funds.
- Cooperation with other EU projects in the field of bioeconomy, in order to achieve an efficient experience exchange and interconnection of information at the level of EU and CEE countries.

In the context of the wider macro region, Romania is part of the **BIOEAST** initiative for knowledge-based agriculture and forestry in the bioeconomy. A concept paper for developing National Bioeconomy Strategy – promising / niche sectors – is under development (2022-2023): Co-shaping the future of promising sectors of bioeconomy through participatory approach.

Other national bioeconomy-related strategies:

- the recently adopted (July 2022) **National Strategy for Research, Innovation and Smart Specialization 2022-2027**, sets Bioeconomy as national smart specialization domain.
- the **Strategy for the development of the agri-food sector on medium and long-term 2020–2030**

According to this document, the strategic objectives of bioeconomy aim at assessing the national bio-economic potential to produce and capitalize non-food bio-resources, converting agricultural residues into biofuels, developing the knowledge base and introducing technical progress specific to the field, scientific support for policy decisions and implementing a strategy in the field of bioeconomy and long-term reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

- the **Romanian Strategy for Competitiveness 2021-2027**
- **National Energy Strategy**
- Research on the identification of bioeconomy development priorities in Romania for the period 2016-2030, developed by the National Institute of Research and Development for Biological Sciences.

Bioeconomy related strategies at regional level

- 7 regions (NUTS 2) have published strategies related to the bioeconomy.
- 1 region with a fully dedicated bioeconomy strategy.
- 2 regions have a strategy with a strong bioeconomy focus.
- 4 regions have strategies with minimum bioeconomy content.

The most relevant sectors related to the bioeconomy strategic frameworks are waste, agriculture, agri-food, forestry and fisheries. The biomass resources addressed are generally waste and agricultural residues. Covasna region (NUTS 3, RO123) published a bioeconomy roadmap within the framework of the BE-Rural project.

4.2.5.4 Small scale biobased solutions

- Agrofood
 - **Fibro+**: Soft drink resulted from the combination of bio chicory roots with mineral water from Vâlcele, Central region, Romania. gluten-free fibres enriched natural mineral water. Recommended for people suffering from gluten intolerance, as well as for those who adopted a healthy lifestyle, pointing out that the mineral water with fibres helps lower triglycerides, cholesterol, blood sugar level and speeds up intestinal transit.
 - **Revolve**: high protein level drink from whey - a solution for milk waste management in the dairy industry. Whey protein is derived from the process of making cheese from milk. The main protein of whey, beta-lactalbumin (whey protein), has a role in the transport of vitamin A. Through the content of branched amino acids (leucine) whey stimulates protein synthesis with a role in increasing muscle mass and cysteine content influences the increase in glutathione, which is an antioxidant. Whey amino acids are a real source of energy for those who do prolong physical exertion. Romanian local product (Ilieni, Covasna County), developed by Meotis LTD in collaboration with ICECHIM – (National Institute of Research-Development for Chemistry, Bucharest)
- Agriculture and Biomaterials
 - **NakedSheep**: Naked Sheep SRL comes with an innovative ecological fertilizer from Romania that can be used in eco farming. It is 100% organic, just made out of sheep wool. The sheep wool pellets are storing water, up to 4 times their own weight. After they are activated in the soil, nitrogen and potassium are constantly released to the roots. This effect lasts up to 6 months. It is a natural and biodegradable product, it is a product that comes from a historical region of Romania, being extremely well-known in Western Europe.
 - **LanaTerm**- Thermal insulation for buildings made of sheep's wool. Nature designed sheep's wool to be an effective insulator. The sheep produce it without any human intervention, so it really is renewable, not to mention 100% recyclable. This makes wool insulation ideal for low-impact green buildings such as passive or zero-carbon houses. LanaTerm wool insulation does not have a negative environmental footprint as it is biodegradable, does not damage the ozone layer and does not contribute to climate change. Growing wool is what sheep do, so the process involves a fraction of the energy required to produce equivalent artificial insulation. In fact, sheep's wool requires less than 15% of the energy used to make glass wool.
 - **Hempcrete**, Stonehemp – building material: an ecological building material, made of a mixture of hemp shives, hydrated lime SUPERCALCO S, a pozzolanic binder and water. The shives are the milled wooden core of the industrial hemp plant, with a sawdust texture, resulted after the fiber was extracted.
 - **Gekka Biochar**
 - **Bio Vegetal Charcoal** – Biochar is an organic fertilizer/amendment that is a carrier of nutrients and microorganisms. It can also be used mixed with manure. Manure efficiency can be increased because biochar binds and stores microorganisms, trace elements (Fe, Br, Cu, Ph, Mn, Mg) and water. In these conditions they enrich each other. The biochar later turns into humus. Bio Vegetal Charcoal – Biochar is a crystalline, black, odorless porous material.
 - **Pyrolytic Bio-Condensate** Bio-pyrolytic distillate, organic fertilizer solution – pyrolignosic acid – humic acid. A special nutrient for all types of soil. It helps plants grow healthier by improving their ability to defend themselves against disease or pests.
 - **GoBioHumus** - Biohumus (vermicompost) - is a natural organic fertilizer, resulting from mixing manure and biological waste produced by earthworms. The product contains the necessary set of nutrients, macro and micro, enzymes, soil antibiotics, vitamins, growth hormones and humic substances. (*Go Biohumus – Direct de La Natura*, n.d.)
- Bioenergy

- **Small-scale bioenergy systems:** plants of up to 1 MW of energy generating capacity. The use of wood waste and willow energy in biomass heating systems is a reliable solution for providing thermal comfort in public buildings in a locality. The concept foresees the following: identification of the sources of wood waste at local level (waste from felling of trees in forests, wood waste from pastures, green areas, orchards, gardens, parks, households, etc.), collection of woody biomass with the help of people from vulnerable groups (social aspect), cultivation of energy willow for the purpose of obtaining woody biomass, logistics segment (milling, storage, transport), boiler manufacturing, installation and commissioning of a biomass boiler plant and connection of users to this system (especially public buildings).

4.2.6 Lithuania

4.2.6.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

In 2018, the total supply of biomass in Lithuania added up to approximately 19.4 million tonnes of dry matter (tdm). Two-thirds of this biomass was produced domestically, while 18% of the biomass supply was imported and the origin of more than 15% of the total biomass could not be identified. The agriculture sector is the biggest producer of domestic biomass with 72% of the total, followed by forestry with almost 28% of the dry matter content. While the relative weight of the fishery and aquaculture sector is quite small (less than 0.2%), it is more important when considering nutritional values. In agriculture, crop production represents almost 70% of the domestic biomass harvest with grazed biomass and collected crop residues representing smaller portions (15% each). Almost a third (30%) of the total agricultural biomass supply was used as food and feed and nearly a fifth (17%) was exported in 2018 (*Biomass Flows*).

The cereals share in crop biomass harvest has been growing over the last decade, and recently accounts for 52%, followed by the fodder crops' biomass (almost 31%). While the relative weights of other crops such as oil, industrial, and fiber crops, as well as fruits and vegetables are quite small. At the same time, cereals exports are growing rapidly, and over 83% of cereals feedstocks were exported in recent years. Therefore, Lithuania is looking for ways to increase domestic consumption of cereals for the production of high-value-added products.

In the case of woody biomass, most of the available roundwood and woody biofuel (woody biomass used for heating and power generation) is harvested domestically. The supply of roundwood was at approximately 4 330 thousand tdm, of which at least 82% was sourced domestically in 2017. Although Lithuania is a net exporter of roundwood, the country is increasingly dependent on woody products imports. Approximately 1 927 thousand tdm of roundwood were used for industrial materials and 1095 thousand tdm were used for other unspecified needs. About one-tenth of roundwood supply was exported.

The domestic production of woody biofuel (2 977 thousand tdm) is mainly focused on domestic consumption, and

only about a tenth of

Figure 45. Biomass flows in Lithuania. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b)

solid biofuel is exported. Firewood and chips are consumed in the domestic market, while wood pellets are exported.

4.2.6.1.1 Food & agriculture

Food waste management.

Food waste in Lithuania is estimated to be approximately 228 thousand tonnes of dry matter (tdm) in 2018. The volume of food waste remained stable in the 2010-2018 period. More than half (53%) of food waste occurs at the consumption stage, followed by the retail and distribution stage, representing almost 40% of the total food waste. Food waste occurs at the processing and manufacturing stage, representing nearly 8%.

Most of the produced food waste is destined for disposal in landfills, sewage or incineration (52%). Composting and anaerobic digestion are the other two main destinations of food waste (21% in each case) and 6% of the waste is used in other ways. The fish processing company “Norvelita” recycles the waste from fish slaughter and processing into biogas. The processing products (digestate) are used for fish farming and fertilizing the fields where forage crops are grown, thus ensuring a closed cycle. All received energy is used in the company's production processes. The “Agaras” company processes cattle and pig slaughterhouse waste, cattle farm manure, and waste from other food industry companies into biogas, and uses the processing products to fertilize fields, thus ensuring a closed cycle. All received energy is used in the company's production processes.

As part of the national EIP project, in which six farmers and social and technological researchers from VDU Academy of Agriculture are participating, innovative solutions are being developed for managing berry seed residues in small farms. A new model of processing berry seed residues into products with high added value and commercialization of these products is being developed, combining small-scale solutions of the technological process and commercialization. Farmers grow raspberries, strawberries, gooseberries, honeysuckle berries and blueberries. They supply the market with fresh berries and juices and jams made from unsold berries. However, unused seed remain. As a result, farmers are interested in developing waste-free production and supplying the market not only with fresh berries, juices, and jams, but also with innovative products of high added value from berry seed residues. The main task of the project is to offer innovative solution model to farms, which combines the technological process of production of new bioproducts and the solutions for commercialization, organizing the co-operation of farmers in the production and marketing (sales) of new bioproducts.

Agriculture (open field, livestock, greenhouses, specific crops, etc)

The utilised agricultural area (UAA) was 2 938.2 thousand hectares and occupied 44.9% of Lithuania's territory in 2021. Since 2003, UAA has increased by 406.7 thousand hectares. Harvest of agricultural crops in Lithuania in the 2000-2020 period: harvest of grain crops increased twice (5 621.3 thousand tonnes in 2021), sugar beet (for industry) was almost stable (856.5 thousand tonnes in 2021), rape grew 11 times (904.4 thousand tonnes in 2021), vegetables (field and under glass) decreased by 25% (246.2 thousand tonnes in 2021), orchards and berry plantations experienced a decline by almost 50% (57 thousand tonnes in 2021), and potatoes decreased the most rapidly – by 89% (204.6 thousand tonnes in 2021). Lithuania is one of the European countries that grows the most hemp. Hemp areas in Lithuania expanded from 283 hectares in 2013 up to 5 thousand hectares in 2021. Milk yield in the 2000-2020 period decreased by 15% in Lithuania. In 2021, milk yield was 1476.9 tonnes in Lithuania.

In terms of live weight of animals and poultry raised, in the 2000-2020 period the total live weight of livestock and poultry increased by 64% in Lithuania. In 2021, the total live weight of livestock and poultry was 367.5 thousand tonnes in Lithuania. The most rapid growth was observed in the live weight of poultry – 4 times during the 2000-2020 period.

The most significant source of GHG emissions in Lithuania is energy sector with 58.5% share of the total emissions in 2020. Agriculture is the second source of source GHG emissions in Lithuania (accounted for 22.1% of the total national emissions) and the most significant source of CH₄ and N₂O emissions (accounting for 58.6% and 87.4% of the total national CH₄ and N₂O emissions, respectively). The total GHG emission from agriculture (excl. LULUCF)

amounted to 4 450.7 thousand tonnes CO₂ eq. in 2020 (*Lithuania's Greenhouse Gas Inventory Report (2022). Vilnius.*). Since 2000, GHG emissions from agriculture increased by 13%.

In Lithuania, the agriculture employed 70 thousand persons which accounts for 5% of total domestic employment (in 2020) or 41% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy (in 2019). Agriculture experienced a decline of employment by a compound average annual change rate of -3.6% during the 2010-2020 period. Value of the sector Lithuania's agriculture turnover was 2 585.8 million euro in 2019. In Lithuania, the agriculture is the second largest bioeconomy turnover generator, more than 25% of overall bioeconomy turnover came from agriculture in 2019. During the 2010-2019 period, a real growth of turnover was observed in this industry (compound average annual growth rate of +2.3%).

Food processing

Lithuania produced 570 thousand tonnes of meat and meat products in 2021. Production of meat and meat products has almost doubled over the past 15 years. The processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans, and molluscs amounted to 156 thousand tonnes in 2021 and has more than doubled during the last decade. The processing and preserving of potatoes, fruit, and vegetables amounted to 51 thousand tonnes in 2021. Production of potatoes, fruit, and vegetable products increased by 2.3 times over the past 15 years. There were 247 thousand tonnes produced animal or vegetable fats and oils in Lithuania in 2021. Fats and oils production have increased by 60% during the last decade.

Lithuania produced 1082 thousand tonnes of milk products in 2014. In volume terms, the growth of the manufacture of milk products was very slow. More than 1 476 thousand tonnes of products of the milling industry as well as malt, and starches were produced in 2021. In the last fifteen years, the production of these food products has not changed much - it has decreased by a few percent.

In Lithuania, the food processing employed 40.3 thousand persons which accounts for 3% of total domestic employment (in 2020) or approximately 22% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy (in 2019). This industry experienced a decline of employment by a compound average annual change rate of -0.4% during the 2010-2020 period.

In 2019, turnover of food processing reached 3 620.6 million euro in Lithuania. In the same year, the food processing was the largest bioeconomy turnover generator, more than a third (36%) of overall bioeconomy turnover came from the food processing industry in Lithuania.

During the 2010-2019 period, a real growth of turnover was observed in this industry (compound average annual growth rate of +1.8%).

4.2.6.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

Forestry and logging

In 2020, the area of forest land was 2201 thousand hectares and occupied 33.7% of Lithuania's territory. Since 2000, this area has increased by 181 thousand hectares. In 2020, about half of all forests in Lithuania were private forests, which occupied 923.8 thousand hectares (» *Lietuvos Miškai*, n.d.). Based on the data of January 1, 2020, private forest holdings in Lithuania occupied 857 518 hectares. In total, 255408 owners of forest land in Lithuania were identified in 2020. In 2020, 87.1% of private forest holdings were smaller than 5 hectares in Lithuania, and this percent is almost stable from 2010 (85%) (*Atviri Duomenys | Valstybinė Miškų Tarnyba, 2010,2020*).

There was 6.7 million cubic meters of roundwood prepared in Lithuania in 2020. The State Forest Enterprise prepared 3.7 million cubic meters of roundwood in the forests under its management. In private forests, there was 2.9 million cubic meters of roundwood prepared in the same year (*Miškų ūkio statistika, 2021*). The amount of prepared merchantable roundwood was 5.3 million cubic meters in 2000 in Lithuania. State forest enterprises and other state forest managers harvested almost 4 million cubic meters roundwood in 2000. In the same year, the felling rate in private forests was about 1.5 million cubic meters (*Miškų ūkio statistika, 2009*).

In Lithuania, forestry and logging employed 8.6 thousand persons which accounts for 0,6% of total domestic employment (in 2020) and more than 6% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy (in 2019). In forestry and logging, employment rate showed an upward trend during the 2010-2020 period, by a compound average annual growth rate of +1%. In 2019, the turnover of Lithuania's forestry and logging was 451.4 million euro. In 2019, about 4.5% of the overall bioeconomy turnover came from forestry and logging in Lithuania. A real growth of turnover was observed in this industry compound average annual growth rate of +7.5% during the 2010-2019 period.

Wood based industries

Lithuania produced 47.845 thousand cubic meters of plywood and plates in 2021. This manufacture increased almost 7 times in volume terms over the past 15 years. The manufacture of wood in 2021 amounted to 1 562 thousand cubic meters. In volume terms, this manufacture increased by 47% during the last decade. In Lithuania, the manufacture of other wood products in 2021 amounted to 2 503 thousand tonnes. The manufacture increased more than 9 times in volume terms over the past 15 years. In Lithuania, the wood-based industries (i.e., manufacture of wood, wood products and furniture) employed 39 thousand persons which accounts for 2.8% of total domestic employment and almost 21% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy (in 2019). In wood-based industries, employment rate showed an upward trend during the 2010-2019 period, by a compound average annual growth rate of +2.1%. In 2019, the turnover of Lithuania's wood-based industries exceeded 2000 million euro. In Lithuania, the wood-based industries are the third largest bioeconomy turnover generators, more than 20% of overall bioeconomy turnover came from the wood-based industries in 2019. During the 2010-2019 period, a real growth of turnover was observed in these industries (compound average annual growth rate of +5.8%).

4.2.6.1.3 Aquatic & water systems

Traditional water-based activities

In 2020, the area of land used for aquaculture was 10.2 thousand hectares and occupied 3.8% of Lithuania's inland waters territory. Over the past decade, this area has changed slightly (increased by only 731 hectares). Closed aquaculture systems with a volume of 14.3 thousand cubic meters have been introduced in Lithuania. This aquaculture is a relatively new and rapidly growing kind of aquaculture business in Lithuania. In Lithuania, the commercial fishing gradually decreased over the last decade. About 98.3 thousand tonnes of fish were caught from the sea in 2021. There is no commercial fishing in inland waters.

In Lithuania, traditional water-based activities (fishing and aquaculture) employed 0.88 thousand persons which accounts for only 0.06% of total domestic employment (in 2020) or 0.5% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy (in 2019). Among the bioeconomy industries, fishing and aquaculture experienced the highest decline of employment by a compound average annual change rate of -9% during the 2010-2020 period in Lithuania. In 2019, about 1% of the overall bioeconomy turnover came from traditional water-based activities in Lithuania. In absolute terms, the turnover in fishing and aquaculture was 95.4 million euro in Lithuania in 2019. During the 2010-2019 period, a real growth of turnover was observed in this industry (compound average annual growth rate of +6.2%). Innovative water-based activities. Algae production and other innovative water-based production are not cultivated in Lithuania.

4.2.6.1.4 Bioenergy

Biofuels

In 2021, the biofuel production in Lithuania reached 178.1 thousand tonnes. 88% was biodiesel production and the rest share was bioethanol. In almost two decades since production began (in 2004) in Lithuania, biofuel production has increased 43 times. There are three main producers operating in Lithuanian biofuels sector: "Rapsoila", "Mestilla" and "Kurana". Two of these companies operate in rural areas. In 2019, "Kurana" started to produce the advanced biofuels and plans to produce 1.2 thousand cubic meters of advanced bioethanol from by-products, and eventually increase its production capacity to 5 000 cubic meters (Jakšto, n.d.) In Lithuania, the manufacture of biofuels employed 231 persons (in 2019) which accounts for only slightly more than 0.1% of the overall people

employed in the bioeconomy. In this industry, employment rate showed a downward trend during the 2010-2019 period, by a compound average annual change rate of -4.9%.

On the 1st of October, 156 employees worked in Lithuanian biofuels companies operating in rural areas (72% of all employees working in biofuels sector) (*Rekvizitai.Lt. Įmonių Katalogas, Įmonės, n.d.*). In 2019, about 1% (97 million euro) of the overall bioeconomy turnover came from the manufacture of biofuels in Lithuania. During the 2010-2019 period, a real growth of turnover was observed in this industry (compound average annual growth rate of +2.4%). In 2021, turnover of two Lithuanian biofuels companies that operate in rural areas, amounted for almost 55% of the total turnover of the three biofuels companies in Lithuania (*Rekvizitai.Lt. Įmonių Katalogas, Įmonės, n.d.*).

Biogas

84.2 million cubic metres of biogas were produced in Lithuania in 2021. Biogas production has increased four times over the last decade. In Lithuania, production of biogas has started in 2002. "Green Genius" is a renewable energy group developing 9 biogas plants in Lithuania. For biogas generation the company uses energy biomass (corn or grass silage) which buy from farmers, food waste (from households and food or feed producers), manure from farms, and sewage sludge. Suppliers of raw materials receive income from selling manure or other types of waste and residues. The company has innovative installations for the pre-treatment of animal waste (from slaughterhouses, retail, and restaurants etc.). The company has economic benefits from selling green electricity to the national grid and from selling the digestate. The company is planning diversification of a few biogases plans to biomethane production.

Heat

In Lithuania, 551.1 thousand TOE of heat was produced from biofuels which accounts for 51.8% of total domestic gross heat production in 2021. In the 2000-2021 period, total heat production from biofuels has increased 19 times. The district heating sector in Lithuania occupies more than 50 percent of the total heat market, in cities this ratio is higher – about 70-80 percent of all buildings (*Lietuvos Šilumos Tiekėjų Asociacija, n.d.*). In September 2022, in the district heating sector the National Energy Regulatory Council was regulating 41 independent heat producers which sell heat to heat suppliers operating district heating systems (*VERT Pagrindinis Puslapis, n.d.*).

In 2020, the percentage share of RES in primary fuel structure in Lithuanian district heating sector was 74.7%. The share of RES in district heating sharply increased in 2014 (46.4%) while in 2000 it was only 2%. Lithuania's strategic goal is to use only renewable energy resources for heat production. In most Lithuanian cities, all heat is already produced exclusively from renewable resources, without using any polluting fossil fuels (*Lietuvos Šilumos Tiekėjų Asociacija, n.d.*).

Changes in the fuel structure in the district heating market were directly influenced by increased environmental protection requirements, increased prices of natural gas and fuel oil, the opening of the heat market to independent producers, the development of the biofuel production sector and the creation of the biofuel exchange. The replacement of fossil fuels with local biofuels has made it possible to reduce heat prices for consumers in many municipalities (*Valstybės Kontrolė | Lietuvos Respublikos Valstybės Kontrolė, n.d.*).

In Lithuania's district heating sector, employment rate showed a downward trend during the 2010-2019 period, by a compound average annual change rate of -3.3%. Over the past decade, the number of employees in the district heating sector decreased. Due to automation and digitization processes fewer workers are needed and more operational and production services are purchased in the market (*Lietuvos Šilumos Tiekėjų Asociacija, n.d.*). During the 2010-2019 period, a downward trend of turnover was observed in Lithuanian district heating sector (compound average annual change rate of -4.1%).

Bio-based electricity

In Lithuania, 41.1 thousand TOE electricity was produced from biological resources which accounts for 9.4% of total domestic gross electricity production in 2021. In the last decade, bio-based electricity production has increased

more than 2 times. In Lithuania, the bio-based electricity employed 411 persons (in 2019) which accounts for about 0.2% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy. In Lithuania's bioeconomy, the most rapid increase in the number of people employed was observed in bio-based electricity during the 2010-2019 period (compound average annual growth rate of +20.6%). In 2019, about 0.5% (45.4 million euro) of the overall bioeconomy turnover came from the bio-based electricity in Lithuania. The most rapid growth of turnover was observed in this industry compared to the other bioeconomy industries in Lithuania during the 2010-2019 period (compound average annual growth rate of +19.1%).

4.2.6.1.5 Biomaterials & bio-based products

In Lithuania, the manufacture of bio-based products (bio-based textiles, paper, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber (excl. biofuels)) employed 16.4 thousand persons which accounts for only 11.8% of total domestic employment or 8.8% of the overall people employed in the bioeconomy in 2019. In this industry, employment rate showed an upward trend during the 2010-2019 period, by a compound average annual growth rate of +1%. In 2019, about 10.8% (1084 million euro) of the overall bioeconomy turnover came from the manufacture of bio-based products in Lithuania during the 2010-2019 period, a real growth of turnover was observed in this industry (compound average annual growth rate of +6.1%).

While the company "Kanapiniai sprendimai" processes hemp, it separates short and long fibre, which can be used for overlay warming and animal litter. The company also extracts the hemp chaff suitable for animal bedding, construction and further processing. In addition, the company produces pellets for plastic products that manufacture by injection molding method. In the hemp stalks processing factory "Natūralus Pluoštas", all parts of the hemp stalks are used in the factory and the production process takes place without waste. The dust and crushed chips generated in the production process are collected and biofuel pellets are produced from them.

4.2.6.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

The potential of the development of the bioenergy sector has been increased by the EU provision that bioenergy will remain the main renewable energy source in the pursuit of climate and energy goals of 2020–2030. Bioenergy resources should remain the principal fuel in Lithuanian district heating systems. This has a potential for increase, even though it is limited (*Lithuanian Bioeconomy Development Feasibility Study*, (2017)). In Lithuania, one of the biofuels producers "Kurana" which operates in rural area, started to produce the advanced biofuels.

Currently, the contribution of manufacture of bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber products using bioresources and biotechnology into the Lithuanian bioeconomy is poor. However, business expectations till 2030 show that the growth of this subsector should be the greatest. The rapidly growing biotechnology sector is one of the main driving forces of this potential of manufacture of pharmaceutical products and chemicals. Most of the production of this sector is concentrated in cities, with the exception of a couple of biofuel companies.

The food sector is the largest share of Lithuanian bioeconomy (more than 36% of total bioeconomy turnover in 2019), just like in the majority of other EU member states. The development of the Lithuanian food sector has been encouraged by rapidly increasing food demand in the world as a result of a rapid growth of population and their purchasing power (food demand has been forecasted to increase by about 50% by 2050). Most enterprises of the food sector operate in urban areas in Lithuania.

In the 2010-2019 period, Lithuania's real bioeconomy growth (at constant 2010 prices) was faster than the growth of the whole economy (compound annual growth rate of value added of bioeconomy was 4.8%, compared to the growth of GDP at 3.8% per year). The share of bioeconomy in GDP increased from 6.8% to 7.5%, and the share of bioeconomy in the labour market decreased from 16% to 13% in the same period.

In Lithuania's domestic market, the supply of biomass flows has been growing over the 2010-2019 period by a compound annual growth rate of +2.32%. However, the domestic production of biomass flows was almost stable in the same period (compound annual growth rate is +0.73%): from 2010 to 2019 agricultural biomass production increased by a compound annual growth rate of +1.26%, while the production of forestry and fisheries and

aquaculture biomass decreased by a compound annual rate of -0.48% and -3.34%, respectively. The importance of net biomass flows imports has been growing (compound annual growth rate is +8.12%) in the 2010-2019 period.

In the 2010-2018 period, waste disposal from food has been decreasing by a compound annual change rate of -5%, while food waste anaerobic digestion and composting increased by +14% per year each. Other waste from food was constant during the same period. In Lithuania, biogas from agricultural and food industry waste as well as landfill waste is produced.

4.2.6.3 Policies and national strategies

Bioeconomy is identified as one of the priority areas of development in the **National CAP Strategic Plan (2022)** of Lithuania. The plan stipulates that it is necessary to pay great attention to the production of goods with high added value using biomass in Lithuania (*National CAP Strategic Plan ,2022*).

Comprehensive Plan of the Territory of the Republic of Lithuania (2021) emphasizes sustainable economy, efficient and sustainable use of resources, renewable energy sources, mitigation of climate change and other topics. In this plan, a coherent and energy-independent state is a strategic priority for energy systems for the years 2030-2050 (*Lietuva 2030 - Bendrasis Planas | Comprehensive Plan of the Territory of the Republic of Lithuania*).

The aim set out in the **National Energy and Climate Action Plan of the Republic of Lithuania for 2021-2030 (2019)** is to reduce the extent of organic soils tillage by 2025, encouraging the restoration, conservation and regular maintenance of green beds of organic soils and using the resulting product in the value chain of the bioeconomy and circular economy. It is also planned to promote the use of biomass for energy production in the period 2021-2030 in this plan (*National Energy and Climate Action Plan of the Republic of Lithuania for 2021-2030 ,2019*).

The **Concept of Scientific Research and Experimental Development and Innovation (Smart Specialization) (2022)** includes specializations in agricultural innovation and food technology and health technology and biotechnology. This document covers the topics such as harmonious agro-biological resources; safe food; development of wind, solar, biomass, biofuel, biogas, hydrogen, geothermal energy; etc (*Concept of Scientific Research and Experimental Development and Innovation (Smart Specialization) ,2022*).

The goal provided in the **National Energy Independence Strategy (2018)** is to increase energy efficiency and RES use as part of the daily life of each consumer, business or industry that purchases electricity, gas, biofuels or other fuels/raw materials. (*National Energy Independence Strategy ,2018*).

The **White Paper on Lithuanian Regional Policy (2017)** envisages sustainable, harmonious and geographically balanced economic growth (*Lithuanian Regional Policy: White Paper for Harmonious and Sustainable Development 2017–2030 ,2017*).

The **Programme of the Eighteenth Government of the Republic of Lithuania (2020)** emphasizes the stable provision of wood supplied to the market to meet the needs of the bioeconomy. The development of maximum added value of biomass in the heating, construction and bioeconomy sectors is also encouraged through the application of regulatory mechanisms (*Program of the Eighteenth Government of the Republic of Lithuania ,2020*).

4.2.7 France

4.2.7.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

France is one of the biggest European countries and one of the biggest suppliers of biomass available. France accounts 18% of the European agriculture production which is the 1st European grower. 36% of the France's land area is natural environment with a woodland area covering about 17 million hectares.

Agriculture: Covers about 28 million hectares which is about 51% of the total land area. Field crops like cereal, oilseed, protein crops, beet, etc. Additionally, is the biggest EU cattle herd with 19 million head of cattle including 3.6 million dairy cows. This sector numbers about 936,000 jobs on 450,000 holdings with 72.8 billion in annual

revenue. The agrifood business numbers 16,200 firms employing 435,000 people (not including craft enterprises) with a €169bn in annual revenue.

Forestry: Covers more than 16 million hectares with 3,3 million forest owners. The main business activities around forestry are pulp, paper, board, lumber, furnishings, woodworking, and wood construction accounting about 440,000 jobs in the forest-wood industry as a whole.

Fisheries and aquaculture: Cover around 10.2million square km and is an exclusive economic zone. This sector numbers about 7,200 ships and 3,300 aquaculture firms and 37,000 headcounts. The annual revenue of the sector is about 1.8 billion.

French fisheries and aquaculture "production" amounts to approximately 690,000 tons, including:

- 485,000 t for fishing
- 155,000 t for shellfish farming
- 50,000 t for fish farming (marine and freshwater)
- 190,000 t for fish co-products
- 160,000 for Shellfish co-products

France, Full trade

Figure 46. Biomass flows in France. Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b)

Biobased chemicals & Materials: This sectors numbers approximately 25,000 25,000 direct jobs, and the 5-10% of supplies to the chemicals and materials industry are biobased.

Bioenergy: Around 60% of renewable energy production.

- Methanisation: 694 biogas production facilities. (Including 267 farm and local area methanisers) representing installed capacity of 355MW and injecting over 80GWh/year of renewable gas.
- Biofuels (not including biogas): around a dozen operators and an estimated 16,000 direct jobs.
- Energy wood & solid biofuels: almost 10Mtoe consumed per year.

Waste management: The waste management industry employs 120,000 people in France and generates approximately €17bn in annual revenue (ADEME 2015). Of these, around 15,000 workers are employed specifically for bioresource related activities (by-products, biogas, etc.).

In France, biomass is mainly produced locally for heating and electricity. In 2019, the bioenergy sector had reached 2.1 GW (3.7% increase compared to 2018) by classifying its production into four categories:

- Household waste with 2.4
- Paper industry waste with 42.3%
- Biogas with 23.5%; and
- Wood energy and other solid components with 31.8%.

Four regions share almost half (49.7%) of the national production in 2019:

- Nouvelle Aquitaine (1 602 GWh)
- Ile de France (2 082 GWh)
- Les Hauts de France (1 071 GWh)
- Auvergne Rhône-Alpes (1 060 GWh).

As an indication, this production covered, on average, 1.6% of the electricity consumption in 2019. However, the connected capacity per region is somewhat different and therefore four regions also share the use of more than half (56%) of the installed capacity:

- Ile-de-France (317 MW)
- Nouvelle-Aquitaine (326 MW)
- Région PACA (293 MW)
- Grand Est (236 MW).

Bioénergies : puissance raccordée par région en 2019
Source RTE - Bilan électrique 2019 © EDF

Figure 47. Bioenergy use, 2019

Bioénergies : production par région en 2019
Source RTE - Bilan électrique 2019 © EDF

Figure 48. Bioenergy production, 2019

4.2.7.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

In the next 20 years, more than 90,000 direct and indirect jobs could be created by the new bio sourced sectors. This is one of the major challenges in France and agricultural education, along with engineering schools and agronomy or similar schools, is obviously in the best position to open up to new recruitment and bioeconomic innovation. Agricultural education has 800 establishments throughout the country, including student classes, educational sites, continuing education platforms and higher education institutions. The training infrastructure is therefore easily adaptable.

This is what will be needed by 2030 to provide the majority of the 90,000 additional jobs that will be created in the future, at a time when the diversification of these educational institutions is essential to ensure their future.

The bio-economic sectors thus represent nearly two million direct jobs in France. The traditional activities of food agriculture, agro-industry and the forestry-wood industry account for the essential part. However, as we have seen, about 100,000 of these jobs were created only recently, over the last 20 years, and in new professions, precisely those of a new bioeconomy. These jobs logically replaced the traditional jobs in the "petro-sourced" or fossil economies, in the main new sectors of the bioeconomy (new materials, plant-based chemistry, biofuels).

4.2.7.3 Policies and national strategies

In 2015, the fundamentals of a global French bioeconomy strategy were put in place in order to set out the topic, the challenges and the vision of a bioeconomic future in a concerted manner. As a result, the following four ministries were consulted:

- The Ministry of Ecology, Sustainable Development and Energy
- The Ministry of National Education, Higher Education and Research
- The Ministry of the Economy, Industry, and the Digital Economy
- The Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry

Table 11. The major concerns of the bioeconomy in France.

Objective	Explication
Making the products of the bioeconomy a market reality	Identify the markets where the bioeconomy can provide solutions and activate the levers (fiscal, regulatory, normative...) to promote market penetration.
Support the transition to an innovative and sustainable biobased	Promote the sustainable deployment of innovative industrial tools in the territories.
Sustainable produce BioSource to meet the needs of all value chains	Produce and mobilise more bioresources, without compromising future production capacity.
Ensure a sustainable bioeconomy	Thinking about assessment frameworks for the bioeconomy and promoting best practice.
Ensuring dialogue with society for a shared bioeconomy	Set up a dedicated strategy to make the bioeconomy known to as many people as possible, based on the actors involved, and initiate a societal debate on what it can bring.
Innovate for an efficient bioeconomy	Consolidate support for innovation in favour of the bioeconomy, open up cross-cutting work and make the link with training.

In addition to addressing the specific issues identified above, the French strategy for the bioeconomy will be based on four major cross-cutting projects:

- Bringing together, overcoming barriers, and building a systems approach

- Accompanying stakeholders on the path of transition
- Identify, organise, and enhance the relevant scales of the territory.
- Measuring, analysing, and improving the implementation of the bioeconomy.

4.2.8 Spain

4.2.8.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

Spain area covers a total of 505 944 km². Land distribution is principally divided into forestry and shrub land (50.1 %) and agricultural area (47.1 %). Forestry land comprises 29% of dense forest land and rest 21 % are shrub lands, and open natural areas. Land cover is complemented with circa 2% of artificial surface and the remaining 0.9 % as wetlands and water bodies. From the agricultural land (not counting pastures) the distribution is: arable: 52.8%; idle land: 18.0 %; permanent crops: 27.6%; other uses: 1.6%). Land managed under irrigation represents 26% of the agricultural land, and 74% correspond to rainfed crops. The bioeconomy in Spain employed around 1.44 million people in 2019. This represented 8.0% of total workplaces in the country. The shares are as next:

- 49.6% in the Agricultural sector (715 thousand people)
- 31.7% in the Food, beverage and tobacco sector (457 thousand people)
- 5.2% in the Wood products and furniture sector (75 thousand employees) + 1.2% in the Forestry sector (17.7 thousand persons)
- 3.5% in the Bio-based textile industry (50 thousand persons)
- 3.2% in the paper industry sector (46 thousand persons)
- 2.8% in the Biobased chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber, (37 thousand persons)
- 2.6% fishing and aquiculture (38 thousand employees)

Employment by sector in Spain (2019)
(number of people employed)

Figure 49. Employment in bioeconomy sector in Spain, 2019, Source: (JRC)

The total turnover of bioeconomy in Spain reached 236 billion euros, meaning 10% of the total Spanish turnover. The principal contributors were the manufacture of food, beverage and tobacco (131 M€; 55.8%) and agriculture (55 M€; 23.5%). Rest of sectors contributed with less than 6% each one: paper (14 M€; 5.9%), the Biobased chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber (12.8 M€; 5.4%); wood and furniture (9.9 M€; 4.2%); textile (5.8 M€; 2.5%), aquaculture and fisheries (2.6 M€; 1.1 %), forestry (1.7 M€; 0.8%), liquid biofuels (1.1; 0.5%) and bioelectricity (0.48 M€; 0.2%).

Turnover by sector in Spain (2019)

(million €)

Figure 50. Turnover in bioeconomy sector, Spain 2019.

Source: (JRC)

The total added value by bioeconomy in Spain sums 69 M€, representing total 11% of the total added value of the Spanish economy. Differently to the turnover, the added value is larger for agriculture sector with 29.9 M€ (43.3%), being the food and beverage sector in second position with 24.4 M€ added value (35.3%). Biobased chemicals take the third position with 3.9 M€ (5.7%) and in fourth position wood and furniture sector with 3.7 M€ (5.4% added value). Rest of the bioeconomy sectors keep same position as for the turnover.

Value added by sector in Spain (2019)

(million €)

Figure 51. Value added in bioeconomy sector, Spain 2019.

Source: (JRC)

According to the data available at 2022 (latest available data provided by JRC data service on Biomass Flows in Europe) (JRC, 2022) the total supply of biomass in Spain added up to approximately 77,6 million tons of dry matter (tdm). The agriculture sector is the biggest producer of domestic biomass (68.5 Mt dm) representing with 88% of the total, followed by forestry (8.8 Mt dm) contributing 11.4% to the share, being the rest 0.6% biomass from aquatic ecosystems.

Figure 52. Biomass flows in Spain. Source: (JRC)

4.2.8.1.1 Food & agriculture

In 2018, In the total agricultural biomass supply (in net trade figures) amounted to approximately 68.5 million tons of dry vegetal biomass equivalents.

Figure 53. Agricultural biomass flows, Spain. Source: (JRC)

This biomass is sourced in the form of crop production (43 Mt dm; eq. 49%), grazing (15.8 Mt dm; eq. 19%), harvested crop residues (8.1 Mt dm; eq. 9%), and imports of agricultural products (19.8 Mt dm; eq.22%). It must be noted that biomass produced in grasslands is not harvested but used only for grazing directly by cattle.

Flows going out from Production
Spain, latest available data

Biomass by source type going into Biomass supply
Spain, latest available data

Figure 54. Biomass sourcing for Spain 2019. Source: (JRC)

Almost 32% of the crop production (in dry matter) produced in 2018 were cereals, followed by agricultural biomass with 19% and imports of plant products with 18%. Other relevant contributions are olive trees (10%), fodder crops (7%) and fruits (4%). Due to the high volume of agricultural activity and the context of mild Mediterranean climate favorable for multiple types of crops, multiple and varied agriculture production is worth mentioning, as oil crop, vegetables, pulses or roots.

Flows going into Biomass supply
Spain, latest available data

Figure 55. Biomass sourcing, Spain 2019 Source: JRC

4.2.8.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

The supply of roundwood was estimated at approximately 8.8 Mt dm in 2017 (last available data). A volume of 2.29 Mt dm is considered being extracted (estimated, unreported, including imports). As such at least 79% is domestic wood. This supply was complemented with 0.3 Mt dm of post-consumer wood.

Figure 56. Biomass flows in forestry in Spain. Source: BIOMASS project: JRC

Figure 57. Biomass final use, Spain. Source: JRC

Food and feed are the most important category in terms of biomass use, adding up to 49% of the biomass. From this share, 78% is utilized for animal feeding and bedding, given the relevant animal-based food production in Spain. A total of 21% is utilized for human food-based products, whereas circa 1% is waste (previous to its use in the breeding and food industry).

Prior to the biomass destination to breeding, plant-based food, energy i, etc. it is estimated 39% of losses. Only a small share of the bioeconomy supply is orientated to biomaterials (6.1 Mt dm; eq. 6%) and bioenergy (5.6 Mt dm; eq. 6%).

In respect the principal feedstock for biomaterials, 99% of current biomaterials are based on wood, being only 1% on agricultural biomass. In respect energy the EU biomass flows estimates 100% is based on wood. This data is required to be updated. A recent work carried by AVEBIOM on the strategic plan for agrobiomass in Spain, shows a relevant use of agrobiomass for heating in Spain: especially olive stone, olive cake and dry fruit shells, adding 585 ktoe of energy utilized in 2018 (equivalent to 1.38 Mt dm of biomass). In the power generation sector an estimation of 1.13 Mt dm of agrobiomass is estimated by AVEBIOM to be under use, comprising fuels like olive cake, pruning and plantation removal wood from permanent crops (vineyard, fruit plantations and olive) and straw. According to that, sourcing for energy would not be 99% from wood, but circa 60% instead.

4.2.8.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

According to the JRC national biomass flows, a total of up to 30 Mt dm of not harvested residues plus additional 32 Mt of losses or unknown utilization of residues, build a large potential for Spain to develop bioenergy strategies based on agricultural residues. The potentials estimated by other works range 12 to 18 Mt dm of agricultural residues without use.

Growing new herbaceous or woody species in agricultural land could contribute to further widen the biomass supply in Spain. The official estimations provided by IDEEA, considering available land and no interaction with food

markets, points out a potential of 17 Mt dm from herbaceous crops in agricultural land, and extra 6 Mt dm from woody crops in agricultural land. The prevailing role of herbaceous crops in respect woody, is derived from a better adaptation of herbaceous species to climate and droughts in Spain, in respect the pluriannual woody species.

According to the JRC national biomass flows, wastes from food and feed sector could add 4 Mt dm of resource for the bioeconomy with next distribution by origin: 1.9 Mt dm from plant based food (48%), 0.77 Mt from Feed and Bedding (19%), 0.69 Mt dm from food and feed products (17%), 0.33 Mt dm from plant based food supply (8%) and 0.3 Mt dm from animal-based food (7%).

Forestry: The forestry surface has increased in Spain 65% from 1980 as result of abandoning agricultural land and the programs of afforestation. Forestry annual growth more than 30 million cubic meters, with an exploitation rate of 40%. Both figures suggest that forestry potential can be expanded and suffice a relevant fraction of the bioeconomy growth. However, there are some structural problems, related with rural areas ageing, recession of the sector (less and less companies available for forest works) and the difficulties of the operations: with scattered parcels, lower productions per hectare and need to apply silvicultural treatments, usually resulting uneconomic in short term (as a piece of a very simplified analysis).

In terms of an implementable potential, estimations suggest achievable potential of 10 Mt dm from forestry residues. If afforestation for producing lignocellulose is considered, the potential could add additional 15 Mt dm.

Moist degradable organic residues

The resource from breeding farms (slurry), municipal sewage plants (sewage sludge), municipal waste separation and landfills, and agroindustry organic residues, is estimated to be able to provide potential energy equivalent to 5.3 Mtoe. However still available and implementable resources for further growing the bioeconomy applications are limited to 2.5 Mt dm/yr. This is equivalent to (estimated in average) more than 20 M m³ of moist organic residues.

Evolution 2008-2019

Spanish Bioeconomy market represented, in 2015, near 6,5% GDP, and 9% of total national employment. In fact, agrifood industry takes itself 2,5% GDP whereas food industry occupies 2.7% GDP share. Further, fishing and wood, pulp & paper industries take an overall of 0,2% and 0,56% GDP share, respectively.

The evolution from 2008 to 2019 of the bioeconomy sectors can be described as a growing sector, even though in Spain a small deceleration occurred after 2008 (due to the Global Financial Crisis – GFC). As observed in the graphs, there was a recession after 2008, which recovered rapidly (turnover, right side), even though the employments rates sunk and for most of sub-sectors have not recovered the levels of 2008 (left side of graph).

Figure 58. Evolution of employment (left) and turnover (right) in bioeconomy from 2008 to 2019 in Spain. Source: JRC

Interpretation of the flows 2018-2019

Observing the graphs together, it is evidenced that the GFC caused a severe destruction of work, still not recovered. The number of employees in the bioeconomy sector has decreased in 110.000 persons from 2008 to 2019.

However, in terms of turnover and GDP, the sector continued growing shortly afterwards, which talks of an important improvement in terms of productivity and added value.

A very important descent occurred from 2008 till 2013, principally dragged by the effect of the financial crisis of 2007–2008 (also known as Global Financial Crisis - GFC). The crisis impacted very severely to Spain. As observed in next graphs the destruction of employment between 2008 and 2013 reached 3.7 million persons (whole sectors), meaning a sink of 17%. Similarly, bioeconomy dropped 230.000 employments, a reduction of 15% in the mentioned period. The after GFC crisis and pre-COVID period (2013-2019) has led to a recovery in the employment, though the figures of 2008 have not been reached. In total the employment on 2019 in bioeconomy is 1.44 M persons, approximately 110.000 persons less than in 2008. Notwithstanding the reasons behind include:

- Firstly, the effect of the crisis, which caused construction sector to destroy 2 M employments (reduction 60%) between 2008 and 2013, and which currently is at a level of about 50% in respect 2008. This affects the wood demand, and this partially explains the descent in the wood and furniture sector (loss of circa 70,000 employments) and forestry (circa 6,000 employments lost).
- A second reason is the trends in agriculture and agri-food industry, reducing the employees as result of: (i) modernization of agriculture and industry; (ii) increase of scales, especially in agriculture, with a need of larger land by holder to provide viability to farming. As such circa 29,000 employments were lost from 2008 till 2019.
- Finally, the fact that that rural population is ageing, being the primary sectors less attractive work for young and entrepreneurs.

Other sectors losing relevant amounts of employees are fisheries (15,000 employments) derived from intensity, scales, and reduction of the sector volume. Similarly, textiles lost 27,000 employments, in this case because of the GFC effect and the general crisis in the sector, with textile production and manufacturing relocated in countries out of the EU.

In contrast other sectors have developed well like the agri-food sector, with an increase of 54,000 employments from 2008 to 2019. A reason behind is the important programs for involving secondary and tertiary activities in the primary sector, to support farmers, fishers, breeders, to have higher added value in their activities. Another sector in growth is the biobased chemicals, which growth from 2008 till 2019 is sized in 6,000 employments. Sectors on biofuels and bioelectricity have also expanded in last 20 years. The variations can be observed in next graph as percentage.

Figure 59. Rates of employment (left) and turnover (right) in bioeconomy from 2008 to 2019 in Spain. Source: JRC

Evolution during last years: 2015-2019

The evolution of the bioeconomy sectors during last years can be observed in next graph. As observed the food and beverage sector, biobased chemicals and agriculture are growing both in turnover and employment. Those sectors indicate to be the most promising in terms of established trends.

On the other hand, sectors like wood products are recovering from the severe effects of the GFC, and particularly, from the deep crisis of the construction sector. Still sectors like liquid biofuels and bioelectricity are growing steadily. In terms of bioheat (not presented in the graphs) it has been stated that Spain is growing at important rates reaching a growth of 25% by 2030.

Forestry is still a sector under shrinkage, not recovering after the crisis. With less companies operating in rural areas, and with a forest stock under continued growth since 1990, mobilization of the large potential is a challenge for the coming period. The production of wood, however, has remained at a similar level, due to the improvement in the productivity, the increase of foreign companies operating in Spain (Portugal mainly, as well as from France) and the expansion of a public model for performing forestry maintenance trough public companies or by means of a public forestry crew.

Bioeconomy and biomass flows changes.

The biomass flows evolution base on the Annual reports released by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) in 2019 for agriculture and fisheries and for forestry sector. The figures provided are on fresh mass (not in dry basis), and sourcing and data classification may vary in respect the values provided by the Biomass Flows methodology provided by the EC.

Table 12. Biomass trends. Source: (Biomass Flows)

Sector	Sub-sector	Detected trends 2008-2019
Agriculture	Total	Permanent crops production has remained in total stable with slight increase.
	Permanent crops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pome fruits stable, with annual productions averaging 0.9 to 1 M ton. • Stone fruits underwent an expansion from 2009 (1.6 Mton) till 2017 reaching 2.2 Mton, when a continued decrease started due to difficulties in international markets, especially for peaches. • Subtropical fruits are a market in expansion, with a constant ramp up 300 Mton from 2015 to 2019. • Berries have expanded as well in last years, with threefold production from 2015 to 2019, reaching 0.12 Mton production. • Nuts has continuously expanded, especially almond, given the good market conditions and expanding demand of international markets. Productions have been object of intensification, irrigation, leading to doubling the production from 2009 to 2019 (reaching 0.57 Mton) • Citrus, stable in production, with slight tendency for increased productivity. Fresh production fluctuating around 6 Mton. • Grape production dependent on seasons, with average productions around 6 Mtons of year production (with ranges of ±0.8 Mton). • Olive production, very dependent on annual weather and the character of fluctuating productions among years. Average in 7 Mton with ranges of ±2 Mton.

	Annual crops	<p>General stability as a whole. Tendency to intensification and to increase the share of irrigated land.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cereal stable in around 22 Mt/yr. with interannual variations (principally due to weather and productivity). • Pulses relevant growth from 250 to 671 kton. Tubers stabilized in 2 Mt/yr. • Industrial crops under relevant growth (larger production are sugar beet, sunflower, line, rapeseed and cotton) • Fodder growing trend with stable production of green grain (2 Mt) and Maize (stable around 4 Mt/yr) as principal resources. Vegetable from orchards in slow growth from 13 Mt to 15 Mt in 2018. • Contraction of the flower production from 120 kton in 2008 to 20 kton in 2018.
Livestock	Total	<p>In general, the breeding activity for meat and animal derived food is a growing sector in Spain. It grew steadily from 5.6 Mton meat production in 2008 till 7.2 Mton in 2019, with no evidence of the effect of GFC.</p>

	Per species	<p>Pigs are by far the largest production sector, under constant growth (3.2 Mton in 2009 to 4.6 Mton in 2019). Poultry sector second in terms of production with a steady growth from 1.3 to 1.7 Mton. Cattle sector production is second varying from 598 in 2009 to 695 kton in 2019. Sheeps and goats' production stabilized in circa 130 kton in the period. Other relevant are equine cattle (stable in 9.5 kton) and rabbit (constant decay 20% in 12 years till 50 kton).</p>
Forestry	Roundwood	<p>The total volume of wood (Over-Bark-Volume) produced in Spain varied from 17.05 M m³ to 17,68 M m³ in 2017. According to the statistical series of forestry extractions the volumes differ, reaching 17.98 M m³ in 2019. The production series shows a small descent after the GFC in 2008, with a recovery from 2013 onwards.</p>
	Firewood	<p>Firewood adds extra 3.5 M m³ eq. per year. Interactions are large, as firewood extraction also depends on previous winter season and the access to firewood batches under procurement procedures.</p>
Fisheries	Maritime	<p>Approximately half of the captures of Spanish fisheries are in international waters. Interannual variations depends on sector trends, quite subjected to bilateral and international treaties on fishing. From 2008 till 2019 it is observed a variation from 880 kton to 787 kton of fresh captures. The captures in the period have fluctuated with minimum in 2009 (727kton) and a maximum in 2013 (1012 kton).</p>
	Aquacul-ture	<p>Aquaculture has in Spain a very relevant production of maritime seafood (mussels) and tuna among others. In continental water the principal species is trout. Quantities are object of fluctuations. In general, the trend is growing, reaching mussels more than 250 kton in 2018 and fish (both maritime and continental water) more than 60 kton.</p>

4.2.8.3 Policies and national strategies

Bioeconomy

In Spain there is a National Bioeconomy Strategy published in 2015, with 2 action plans in documents published in 2016 and 2018. It is a vision and framework document, in line with the rest of the major political packages (agriculture, climate, energy), although with a function rather of positioning and joint vision, and of setting guidelines, but without constituting a binding element for the development of new mechanisms or instruments. This Strategy recognizes the role of biomass for multiple functions and uses. Likewise, it emphasizes the high potential of biomass from agricultural and agro-industrial residues and by-products, and the need to be exploited for the growth of new biological-based activities. At the regional level there are more specific plans that mark the evolution of some instruments, such as the Andalusian Strategy for Circular Bioeconomy, or the Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia 2021-2030.

Circularity

In contrast to bioeconomy strategy, which remained to be a positioning paper or declaration, circularity is the path followed in Spain to define binding objectives and to point out the instruments to be put into operation by the Spanish government. Bioeconomy is included implicitly in this strategy, in the effects applied to the materials of organic origin.

The Spanish Circular Economy Strategy, Spain Circular 2030, lays the foundations for promoting a new production and consumption model in which the value of products, materials and resources are maintained in the economy for as long as possible, in which reduce the generation of waste to a minimum and take advantage of those that cannot be avoided to the greatest extent possible.

This strategy is aligned with the objectives of the two circular economy action plans of the European Union, "Closing the circle: an EU action plan for the circular economy" of 2015 and "A new Circular Economy Action Plan for a cleaner and more competitive Europe" of 2020, in addition to the European Green Deal and the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development. The Strategy has a long-term vision and include successive three-year action plans to be developed.

The Strategy establishes strategic guidelines as a Decalogue and sets a series of quantitative objectives to be achieved by 2030. It identifies six priority sectors of activity: all of them producers or potential consumers of biobased products and services: construction, agri-food, fishing, and forestry, industrial, consumer goods, tourism and textile and clothing sectors.

Some relevant targets to be mentioned are:

- Reduce by 30% the national consumption of materials in relation to GDP, taking 2010 as the reference year.
- Reduce the generation of food waste throughout the food chain: 50% reduction per capita at the household level and retail consumption and 20% in the production and supply chains from the year 2020.
- Increase reuse and preparation for reuse up to 10% of municipal waste generated.
- Improve efficiency in water use by 10%.
- Reduce the emission of greenhouse gases below 10 million tons of CO₂ equivalent.

Among the proposed paths towards circularity, it is mentioned: economic support, taxation, employment programs, R&D&i, consumer policies, industrial growth and transformation, water, agricultural and development policies for rural areas as key policies to advance the circular economy.

Bioenergy

Bioenergy is a sector with specific plans and measures, as being part of the renewable energies action plans of previous periods (2001-2010 and 2011-2020). In the framework towards 2030, bioenergy plans for growth are included under the Spanish National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP). In respect the biogas and renewable gases, the NECP sets the target for bioelectricity.

However, due to the imminent growth of this sector which stayed stuck for years, the Ministry of Industry published a strategic document, the Spanish Biogas Roadmap, which better defines targets and propose a x4 growth by 2030. The targets for bioenergy set there are as next:

- Solid biomass (from NECP):
 - + 411 ktoe increase of biomass for bioheat.
 - + 1.600 ktoe for bioelectricity
 - +1.000 ktoe for new advanced biofuels
- Liquid biofuels for transport (from NECP): maintaining the current quota, phasing out a relevant share from first generation biofuels to new advanced biofuels.
- Renewable gases (from NECP and the SBR):
 - + 96 ktoe new yearly biogas generation (on annual basis in 2030, increase respect 2020), to produce newly 391 GWh bioelectricity per year.
 - + 243 ktoe for injection of biomethane in the network
 - + 60 ktoe of biogas for heating
 - + 260 ktoe biogas for transport

Consequently, under the occurrence of the plan a large increase in the biomass deployment for bioenergy is expected. To reach the targets will be necessary, according to AVEBIOM estimations, the mobilization of more than 7 Mt dm of solid biomass.

Furthermore, the recent geopolitical crisis, and the rise of RE targets towards 2030 to reduce EU energy dependency, makes necessary a review of the plans and instruments in place. Therefore, the expansion towards 2030 is expected to go beyond of the projected targets.

4.2.9 Portugal

4.2.9.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

Portugal has a diverse bioeconomy sector due to the different climates and landscapes that constitute its territory. Portugal has a high potential for the transition to a circular and sustainable bioeconomy, due to its strong primary sector in forestry, agriculture, fisheries, and aquaculture, and its sovereignty and jurisdiction over an extensive maritime territory.

The Norte and Centro regions are widely forested, and therefore, forestry is the main primary activity in these areas and the pulp and paper industries are very important to the national economy. Agriculture also has a significant contribution to the Norte and Centro economy, particularly the one related with dairy and wine production. Agriculture is the main activity in the region of Alentejo, contributing with 80% of the olive oil produced in the country, 60% of the cereals and 50% of the livestock. It is also there where most of the cork is produced, of which Portugal is the world leading producer. Algarve region in the south has perfect conditions for the production of citrus fruits. Fisheries industry occur along the whole continental coast, and in Madeira and Azores, with the areas of Lisbon and Oporto being the most important. The chemical industry is also mainly present in the areas of Lisbon and Oporto and the textiles and leather industries occur in the north region, between Oporto, Guimarães and Braga.

4.2.9.1.1 Food & agriculture

Portugal's Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) is about 3.6 million hectares, which is 39% of its land surface. It is constituted by 258 980 farms, of which 71% are small farms (less than 5 hectares). 19% of the UAA is occupied by permanent crops and 52% by permanent grasslands. Alentejo is largely agricultural and, as such, produces the majority of cereals, olives and berries in the country. Tomatoes for the industry are almost exclusively produced in the southern Centro and northern Alentejo. This region is also the biggest producer of fresh fruits and potatoes. Vineyards are distributed between Norte, Centro and Alentejo. Algarve is the leader region at producing citrus fruits as is Madeira in the case of tropical fruits.

Table 13. Cultivated area and feedstocks produced of the main crops in 2021. Source: (AFIA, 2021)

Crop	Cultivated area (ha)	Feedstocks produced (t)
Winter cereals (wheat, barley, triticale, oat and rye)	100 000	200 000
Corn	80 000	752 000
Rice	30 000	175 000
Tomatoes for the industry	16 000	1 600 000
Potatoes	20 000	413 000
Apples	14 000	368 000
Pears	12 000	225 000
Peaches	4 000	42 000
Kiwis	n.a.	55 000
Cherries	6 500	24 000
Oranges	17 500	370 000
Almonds	58 000	41 000
Chestnuts	50 000	37 000
Vineyards	175 000	978 000
Olives	380 000	1 376 000

Animal Production

Of the 258 980 farms existing in Portugal, 172,350 have livestock, (Eurostat). In 2021, there were 1,680,000 bovine animals, 2,221,000 pigs 2,293,000 sheep and 364,000 goats.

Table 14. Meat produced in 2021. Source: (AFIA, 2021)

. Animal	Production (t)
Bovine	103 000
Pig	377 000
Sheep	15 900
Goat	1 300
Chicken	313 000
Turkey	55 000
Duck	10 400
Others (game meat, pigeon, rabbit, quail)	15 400

and ostrich)	
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Table 15. Products derived from animals produced in 2021. Source: (AFIA, 2021)

Product	Production
Chicken eggs	142 000 t
Sheep milk	71 200 000 L
Goat milk	29 700 000 L
Cow milk	1928 000 000 L
Butter	31 000 t
Powdered milk	38 000 t
Cheese	88 000 t
Acidified milks (includes yogurt)	117 000 t
Honey	10 441 t
Wax	291 t
Wool	5 026 t

Food, Beverage, and tobacco industry

Although there is not a source available with information on the quantities produced by these industries, there is instead information on the production sales value of each sector. In 2020, the food industries generated 11 700 million euros (Table 16), the beverages industry generated 2 800 million euros and the tobacco industry generated 676 million euros.

Table 16. Production sales value of the food industries in 2020. Source: INE, 2021

Industry	Sales value (million euros)
Animal slaughter, preparation and conservation of meat and meat-based products	2 450
Bakery products and other flour-based products	1 490
Dairy products	1 410
Animal feed	1 310
Preparation and conservation of fish, crustaceans and mollusks	1 250
Preparation and conservation of fruits and vegetables	1 100
Other food products	1 100

79,1% of the food industries sales value was generated in the national market, 16,9% in the EU market and 4,1% in the extra-EU market.

Table 17. Production sales value of the beverages industries in 2020. Source: INE,2021

Industry	Sales value (million euros)
Wine	1 560
Beer	590
Soft drinks, natural mineral waters and other bottled waters	524
Distilled drinks	~100
Cider and other fermented fruit drinks	~26

67,9% of the beverages industries sales value was generated in the national market, 18,6% in the EU market and 13,5% in the extra-EU market. The **tobacco industry** generated 676,3 million euros in sales value, 7,5% of which was generated in the national market, 90,8% in the EU market and 1,7% in the extra-EU market. Crop and animal production and hunting employed 257 000 workers and generated 3 265 million euros of Gross Value Added (GVA) in 2020. In 2019, the food, beverages and tobacco industries generated 3 920 million euros of GVA. In 2020, the food industries employed 98 600 workers and the beverages industries employed 13 900 [142]. There was not information available about the employment in the tobacco industry.

4.2.9.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

36% of Portugal's territory is occupied by forest, with eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus globulus*), maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*) and cork oak (*Quercus suber*) being the predominant species (PABS). In 2019, the forestry sector generated 885 million euros of GVA. Available production figures include:

- The paper, pulp and paper products value chain produced 923 000 tons.
- The cork value chain produced 397 000 tons.
- The wood value chain (sawmill, carpentry for construction, wood packaging, furniture and other wood products) produced 271 000 tons.
- The pine natural resin sector has been showing signs of recovery, despite the decrease in production for the past 20 years, manifesting an upward trend in the quantity of colophony and turpentine produced [136].

Table 18. Employment and production sales value of forestry and wood-based industries in 2020. Source: (Eurostat.)

Sector	Employment (nr. of workers)	Production sales value (thousand €)
Forestry	12 600	n.a.
Wood and cork products (except furniture), articles of straw and plaiting materials	36 100	2 894 179
Paper, pulp and paper products	17 700	3 534 610
Furniture and mattresses	42 000	1 625 180

Table 19. Final consumption destination of the wood-based industries in 2020. Source: (Lima, 2020)

Sector	National market (%)	EU market (%)	Extra-EU market (%)
Wood and cork products (except furniture), articles of straw and plaiting materials	46	37	17
Paper, pulp and paper products	70	25	5
Furniture and mattresses	39	49	12

4.2.9.1.3 Aquatic & water systems

Portugal's coast extends for 942 km and its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) is the third biggest in the EU (1,7 million km²) (PABS). In 2020, the fisheries and aquaculture sectors generated 307 and 98 million euros, respectively. In 2021, fisheries captured 185 417 tons of fish and seafood, of which 140 562 tons were sold fresh or refrigerated, in fish markets, generating 335 044 million euros. The majority of the fish was captured by the seventeen existing Organizations of Fish Producers.

Table 20. Distribution of fisheries captures by NUTS2.

NUTS2	Quantity captured (%)	Sales value (%)
Norte	17,9	14,8
Centro	29,2	28,9
A. M. Lisboa	20,8	15,2
Alentejo	5,1	3,5
Algarve	14,9	22,5
R. A. Açores	8,4	11,0
R. A. Madeira	3,7	4,2

In 2020, aquaculture produced 17 000 tons of fish and mollusks and generated 100 million euros in sales. 94,7% of the production occurred in marine or transition waters and 5,3% occurred in interior waters. There are 1272 licensed aquaculture establishments (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2022). In 2020, the fisheries and aquaculture sectors employed 8 000 workers.

4.2.9.1.4 Bioenergy

According to data from the Directorate General of Energy and Geology, the installed capacity of forest biomass power plants in Portugal (mainly located in the Central region) is currently (April 2022) 679 MW (440 MW in cogeneration), with an annual electricity production of more than 3200 GWh and a monthly production in the order of 246-281 GWh. In 2020, the share of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in primary energy consumption was 30%, with 45% of which resulting from the biomass contribution.

It is also highlighted that in the heating and cooling sector and according to the report "European Bioenergy Outlook 2019 - Biomass for heat", 96% of heat of renewable origin comes from biomass, with the industrial sector being the

main responsible for the final consumption of heat from biomass (56% of the total), followed by the residential sector (44%).

In Portugal, there are 26 wood pellets plants. It is estimated that, in 2021, 815.000 tons of wood pellets have been produced, of which 510.000 tons were exported. These were mostly sold to four countries, United Kingdom, Spain, Denmark and Netherlands. Nowadays, the total installed capacity is over 1,7 million tons per year. Although the production of wood pellets has decreased slightly in 2021 comparatively to 2020, three new wood pellets plants and the reopening of another one is going to allow a production growth in 2022, which will increase Portugal's production capacity by 50%.

4.2.9.1.5 Biomaterials & bio-based products

For this topic, four industrial sectors were selected as biological resources users. However, it is not possible to distinguish between bio-based and non-bio-based contributions in these sectors. Table 21 shows the production sales value, employment and final consumption destination of the selected sectors, in 2020 (Eurostat).

Table 21. Production sales value, employment and final consumption destination of four selected sectors in 2020.

Source: (Eurostat)

Sector	Production sales value (thousand €)	Employment (nr. of workers)	Final consumption destination		
			National market (%)	EU market (%)	Extra-EU market (%)
Chemical products and synthetic fibers, except pharmaceuticals	3 852 733	13 200	45	42	13
Pharmaceutical products and preparations	1 035 970	13 800	30	41	29
Textiles	2 712 368	49 800	36	44	20
Leather and leather products	1 926 380	57 300	26	66	8

4.2.9.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

Portugal has many key actors that are relevant for bioeconomy. The country has a growing economy with very strong primary sectors (agriculture, forestry, and fishing and aquaculture sectors). Chemical and biotech industries, wood products, pulp and paper and textile are very important secondary sectors to the national economy.

The different residual biomass streams in Portugal are sufficient to produce biochemicals on commercial levels. However, there are still just a few biorefineries located in Portugal and those that exist mainly use forestry-based feedstock to produce chemicals, composites and fibers, and liquid biofuels. Most of the attractive feedstock for bio-based operations and valorization into added-value products and services are either unused, incinerated, landfilled or achieve relatively low value [131].

Portugal has, currently, a **Sustainable Biomass Action Plan** (SBAP) within the scope of the Horizon 2025 program, published in December 2021. This Plan underlines that the residues resultant from the wood-based industry ascend to 5,3 million tons/year, especially from the pulp and paper industry, and residual biomass from agriculture may ascend to 3 million tons/year, with 59% of this biomass being resultant from the pruning of vineyards, olives and

orchards and the remaining 41% resultant from temporary crops such as corn, rice and sunflower (*Plano de Ação Para a Bioeconomia Sustentável, 2025*).

SBAP also highlights the potential use of biological resources to produce high added value products, as presented below.

Chemical products

- **Lignin** Although most lignin available in the country is used in energy production, it has the potential, due to its chemical properties, to be used in the production of aromatic compounds, and because of the large forest-covered area, it exists abundantly in Portugal (PABS).
- **Biopolymers** A number of studies are currently in motion in order to develop the production of biopolymers from agro-industrial residues, microorganisms and marine algae. These have the potential to replace fossil resources in various applications and allow for a much faster decomposition (PABS)
- **Biomaterials**
- **Fibers** The strong textile industry existing in Portugal represents a great potential for the bioeconomy development. Textiles produced from traditional fibers (linen, cotton, hemp) or from wood, fungi or algae can replace synthetic textiles produced from fossil resources or unsustainable natural fibers. These fibers can also be used to produce biocomposites that, in turn, can be used in construction materials, thermal and acoustic isolation materials, packaging and in the automobile industry.

The olive production has been increasing significantly since 2007, with a production that year of 211 000 tons and, in 2021, the production has reached 1 375 000 tons. Citrus fruits and berries productions have also been increasing steadily for the past decade. Aquaculture production of fish more than doubled in the past two decades [9].

In recent years, biotechnology became a sector of significant importance in Portugal, mostly due to a growing start-up ecosystem, consisting of technology parks and incubators often located near universities, such as Coimbra, Oporto, Lisbon, Braga, Aveiro and Faro [133]. These advancements in biotech industry will certainly lead to changes in the utilization of biological resources due to the forthcoming of new bio-based products and processes.

4.2.9.3 Policies and national strategies

The **Sustainable Biomass Action Plan** (SBAP) identifies as line of actions the following:

- **Encourage the sustainable production** and the smart utilization of regional biological resources.
- **Promote Research & Innovation** and value the excellent national scientific and technological capacity.
- **Develop the bioindustry** in a circular and sustainable viewpoint: innovation in the value chains and processes.
- Promote knowledge, education and competences.
- **Monitor the bioeconomy:** evaluate its evolution, understand the limits of the ecosystems, and promote certification.

SBAP identified three economic sectors, because of their socioeconomic importance, the nature of their activities and their potential for development, that are key to the implementation of bio-based business models at a wider level - textiles and clothing, footwear and natural resin sectors.

- **Textile/clothing and footwear sectors** show great knowledge and quick response capacity to deliver innovative products and services of high added value. Additionally, these sectors traditionally consume a great amount of raw materials and water;

Natural resin sector is a traditional one that Portugal intends to revitalize, and it is expected to contribute to the development of rural areas, based on natural resources exploitation, (*Plano de Ação Para a Bioeconomia Sustentável, 2025*).

4.2.9.4 Small scale biobased solutions

- **Recycling forest residues at a community level** - The municipality of Viseu has installed, since 2019, sites for forest residues in two localities, allowing the populations to deposit forest residues extracted from their properties, and thus, avoiding its burning on site. These sites have already collected 770 tons of forest residues since 2019, which have been consumed at the Biomass Power Plant of Viseu.
- **BioCombus – Pellets production from olive oil industries residues** - The University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD) developed an innovative process of increasing the value of the olive oil industries residues by producing a solid biofuel with high heating value (pellets). A pilot-scale installation was successfully implemented with a production capacity of 30 to 40 kg/h, in association with the Agricultural Collective of Olive Growers of Murça. Arcen Engenharia and UTAD are currently studying the possibility of implementing this technology at the industrial scale (*Projetos*).
- **ALGAVALOR – Micro ALGAs**
- **CMP – Cimentos Maceira e Pataias S.A.** (cement industry), in association with 19 other entities, is leading ALGAVALOR project, which main goal is the integrated production of microalgae and the valorization of its biomass and extracts to various applications. These are human and animal nutrition, cosmetic and biofertilizers. Additionally, the project aims to make use of agroindustrial residues as inputs for the algae production.

4.2.10 Denmark

4.2.10.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

Biological resources from agricultural and forest areas are primary bio resources, which may be utilized for food, feed, materials, chemicals, and energy. Overall, Denmark has a yearly bio resource production of 25 mill. ton dry matter plus 10 mill ton biomass imported.

Denmark, Full trade

Figure 60. Biomass flows in Denmark, (Gurría et al., 2017).

4.2.10.1.1 Food & agriculture

Figure 61. Agricultural biomass flow in Denmark. Source: BIOMASS project: JRC

The sector of agriculture and food numbers about 125.000 employed in agriculture and associated businesses, whereof 63.000 in primary production, contributing to the GDP in percentage of 5.4%.

4.2.10.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

Figure 62. Forestry biomass flows in Denmark. Source: JRC.

The total timber sector contributes a total of 32 billion in direct GDP contributions and 51,400 employees. The timber sector consists of companies working with wood across many industries, including forestry, paper industry, furniture industry, construction, trade, energy production, and wood industry. This sector values about DKK 4.1 billion.

4.2.10.1.3 Aquatic & water systems

Figure 63. Aquaculture biomass flows. Source: JRC

A total of 16,000 jobs in the fishery industry. 7,000 engaged in fishing. (Of these 2,500 vessels, 2,700 employed in the fishing industry and 1,800 engaged in wholesale trade in fishery products). Besides there are 9,000 jobs indirectly related to the fishery. The value of blue economy counts about 23 million euros and the value of fishery counts about 2,5 million euros.

4.2.10.1.4 Bioenergy

Total Danish energy consumption amount to 656 Petajoules (PJ) in 2020 (Energy Agency, 2021), including 148 PJ from biomass (wooden pellets, tile, wood, wood waste, straw, and biodegradable waste), equalling 7.8 mill. ton dry matter). Straw made up 19 PJ, biodegradable waste 23 PJ and the rest was wood biomass, the majority of which was wood pellets. In 2020, approx. 65 PJ of wood fuel (equivalent to approx. 3.4 million tons of dry wood) was imported of the total energy production, biogas accounted to 21.4 PJ in 2020 and the share has been increasing from 4.3 PJ in 2010 (Energy Agency, 2021). Biogas is an important player in the circular bioeconomy via the technology's contribution to the recycling of nutrients for agriculture. Other forms of bioenergy usually do not contribute to circularity because nutrients are lost in the process. Ash from combustion can in principle be recirculated and contains phosphorus, potassium, and micronutrients, while nitrogen is lost with the flue gas. But recirculation of ash only takes place to a very limited extent, e.g., because the content of heavy metals is often too high. Fuels for the transport sector also consume bioresources. In 2020, 10.9 PJ of biodiesel and ethanol were used.

Key processes:

1. Combustion: Danish cogeneration plants and private combustion plants burn processed and unprocessed biomass in large boilers to produce electricity, heat or both.
2. Gasification: Thermal gasification is the heating of biomass in the absence of oxygen. The biomass is converted into combustible gases that can be burned or upgraded.
3. Biogas: Biogas is produced during oxygen-free decomposition of organic residues and waste products and is a methane-containing gas that can be upgraded and replace the use of fossil natural gas.
4. Liquid biofuels: Biomass can be used to produce liquid biofuels, which can be mixed with petrol and diesel. Bioethanol is produced through fermentation/distillation of biomass, and biodiesel is produced from vegetable oils.

The amount of available biomass in Denmark is only partially utilized today, and this means that there is still a potential to use more Danish biomass in the energy supply. At the same time, large quantities of biomass are imported, especially in the form of wood pellets.

4.2.10.1.5 Biomaterials & bio-based products

Wood products is a significant market either as utilization for furniture, construction, interiors, etc. The construction business and its usage of biomaterials can be expanded considerably (Rasmussen et al., 2022). The usage of paper and cardboards have an energy value of 20 PJ; however, references are uncertain. Other materials, currently fossil-based, are under development, e.g., packaging, bioplastic, etc., however currently in limited amount.

4.2.10.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

Denmark has unique possibilities for developing the Bioeconomy. The feedstock basis in the form of biomass from agriculture, forest, and fisheries is large, and the necessary processing technologies are available. Furthermore, the competences within agriculture, fisheries, enzymes, technologies, logistics, IT, services, research, development and advisory are present. Table 22 show key high potential biomass value chains selected by the National Bioeconomy Panel.

Table 22. Selected biomass value chains.

Type of biomass	Biomass	Value chain
1. Blue biomass	Discard-fish	Human consum
2. Blue biomass	Macroalgies	Feedstuff and health products
3. Green biomass	Grass, clover, other plant parts	Raw protein for feed
4. Yellow biomass	Straw from grain	Biofuels
5. Brown biomass	Energy as tile	Gas for the nature gas
6. Red biomass	Residual products from meat production	Feeds and protein flour
7. White biomass	Whey protein	Protein in human food
8. Residual products	Wastes	Biogas for energy

Key numbers

1. Discard-fish amount (2013): 21.277 tons, amount suitable for consume (2013): 18.319 tons, required amount for sustainable value chain: 14.655 tons. Job creation: For every mil kr. invested, 1,25 jobs will be created. Innovation: Discard amounts are a new type of biomass, earlier not commercialized.
2. Danish produced alger (Makroalger). End product: Feed for use in the antioxidant Fucoidan for the pharmaceutical industry. Job creation: Limited as existing production systems are used. Innovation: Current value chain new as shift in biomass input and large-scale production. For the pharmaceutical industry more innovation potential. Overall medium innovation potential.
3. Current production of Danish green protein crops: Green biomass (Rape cakes): 241.000 tons; Green biomass (clover grass in cropping system): 3.270.000 tons (dry matter). Job creation: For every mill kr. Invested, 1,99 new jobs are created in the whole value chain. Innovation potential: High potential when all necessary technologies (processing, transport, digital management, etc.) are developed.
4. In 2013, 5.8 mio. tons of straw in Denmark, of which 2,6 mio. ton was not utilized (too expensive to collect). 78% of the produced straw comes from the growing of winter wheat and spring barley. There is a large unused amount of straw resource in Denmark, which means that biorefining will not displace other uses of biomass, or other jobs (potential 1000-2000 jobs). Innovation and innovation: The technology used is new, but not unproven.
5. Harvesting of energy wood as chips (2012): 1,092,000 m³, corresponding to 2.4 million GJ. Product: Gas for sale on the natural gas grid. Forestry and the wood industry are the primary producers of the unprocessed

biomass. Potential to upgrade the gas and supply it to the natural gas network. For every million DKK generated in the industry, 2.14 new jobs will be generated, incl. in derivative industries, such as the transport industry. Gasification of brown biomass as well as upgrading and distribution to the natural gas network is very innovative. The gasification itself is already in production in Denmark, while the innovative and innovative part is that it has not yet been possible to upgrade the gas to natural gas quality, so that it can be supplied to the natural gas network.

6. The products are residual products and waste from meat, intestines, bones, fat, and blood from slaughterhouses. Total: 240,000 tons/year. The actual use of meat residues from slaughterhouses for feed is not new, but the processing of the biomasses, so that this can be used for meat protein and feed, is innovative and will lead to a much greater degree of utilization and value of the biomass resource. For every mill kr. Invested, 1,7 new jobs are created in the whole value chain.
7. Whey is a product from cheese production and may be converted to protein as ingredients in different foods. Current whey production: 4,2 mio. tons which generate 28.000 ton of protein. For every mill kr. Invested, 1,6 new jobs are created in the whole value chain. Whey has been processed to protein for 20 years in DK, 95% of all whey in DK is processed for protein. The innovation potential is the extraction of lactose and proteins from the unstable part of the whey.
8. Residual products in the form of biomass from household waste (food waste), End product: Biogas for energy and digestate for fertilizer purposes. Yearly amount: 1 mio. ton. The organic part of the waste is already processed as combusting, biogas treatment, or source sorting, and therefore no new jobs are created as the value chain already exists. This technology is well known. The enzymatic processing is innovative, like using the digestate for the production of bio chemicals and biomaterials.

Key biomass value chains include 3) Green biomass, and 8) Residual waste (yearly generated additional production value in 2030 of more than 20 billion Dkk.

4.2.10.3 Policies and national strategies

The Advisory Board for Circular Economy's Recommendations to the Government June 2017 Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark has recommended that by 2030: Denmark gains greater economic value from materials by boosting resource productivity by 40% based on amount of materials, and by 15% based on their value. Denmark increasing circularity by boosting overall recycling to 80% and reducing the amount of waste generated by 15%. Denmark retaining its leading position in Europe by developing circular technologies and solutions and increasing the exports of both. Denmark utilising surplus capacity better by 50% of the population becoming active in the 'sharing economy'. Denmark boosting circular consumption by quadrupling overall turnover of eco-labelled products and services.

Forecasts show the effect of introducing the circular economic principles to the Danish economy will Increase GDP by 0.8 – 1.4 %, reduce consumption of selected resources by up to 50 %, reduce Danish carbon footprint by 3-7 %, and Create 7 000 – 13 000 jobs by 2035.

4.2.10.4 Small scale biobased solutions

- Small farm biogas plants (60 with a production <100 Kw).
- Small farm windmills. Total in DK 4000 on private farms
- Small local power plants for straw or woodchips, 70 being fueled by straw.
- Solar cells for farmland or supplier for small local power plants. In 2020, there is overall 106.461 solar cell installations, including all types of solar cells connected to private or public installations.
- Windmills: 558 sea based and 6.429 land based wind mills, including 1.336 private household windmills.

4.2.11 Poland

4.2.11.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

As the second largest country in Central and Eastern Europe, Poland has diverse biomass resources. In particular, such primary sectors of the economy as agriculture and forestry provide a diverse range of biomass that is consumed locally in the form of agricultural products, processed or exported outside the country. In 2021, for example, the value of agri-food exports increased by 9% to €37.4 billion (with imports of this product category at €24.7 billion). The largest export value of agri-food products was meat, meat preparations and livestock (19%), cereal grains and preparations (13%), tobacco and tobacco products (11%), sugar and confectionery (7%), dairy products (7%), vegetables (including mushrooms) and preparations (5%), fruits (including nuts) and preparations (5%), oilseeds, vegetable fats (2%) and coffee, tea, cocoa (2%). Most of the exported products are produced from local agricultural biomass, except for coffee, tea, and cocoa, which are imported and then repackaged and exported. Approximately 73% of export revenues from agri-food products were generated by sales to European Union countries.

According to JRC data, the highest turnover (billion EUR, 2019) is generated by such bioeconomy sectors for Poland as: food (63), agriculture (29), paper (11), wood products (10), beverage (8), wooden furniture (6) and tobacco (6). The highest employment (million) was estimated for such sectors as: agriculture (1.42), food (0.439) and wood products (0.134). The highest value added (billion EUR) was observed in sectors such as: food, agriculture (both 11), wood products, paper (both 3), forestry, beverage, wooden furniture (every accounted for 3), (JRC, 2022).

4.2.11.1.1 Food & agriculture

Biomass from agriculture is processed in Poland in particular by the 'food production' sector, which accounts for about 6% of the gross value added of the Polish economy. The food industry with tobacco, in terms of value of sold production, is the largest branch of Polish industrial processing (20% of Polish GDP). Poland is the sixth largest food producer and exporter in the EU with > 2.8 million employees in agriculture, food processing, beverage and tobacco production (*Eurostat*). Another sector of the economy that processes products from agriculture is the tobacco sector, which has a centuries-old tradition in Poland dating back to the 18th century. For this industrial production, most of the feedstock is imported. An important industry linked to agricultural production is the beverage sector, which is closely linked to consumer preferences. Other sectors or economic activities that are closely related to agricultural production in Poland are the biogas and biofuel sectors (Loizou et al., 2019).

4.2.11.1.2 Forestry & natural habitats

Another important primary sector supplying biomass is the forestry sector. About 80 percent of Poland's forest area is managed by the State Forests - National Forest Holding. Harvesting and processing of timber in Poland takes place with a balance in the forest ecosystem and boundaries that ensure the sustainable evaluation of forests and the increase of their resources. The forestry biomass produced is partly processed in Poland and partly exported (*Statistics Poland*). Due to the price set by the State Forests, it is increasingly common for the timber industry to import raw materials, for example, for furniture production. Approximately 55,000 people in Poland are employed in silviculture and logging and perform various forestry work (*Statistics Poland 2021*, n.d.). Poland's wood-processing sector of the economy (mainly the furniture industry, the manufacture of wood products, and paper products) employs as many as 460,000 people, accounting for 2.5 percent of employment in the overall economy. The furniture, timber (wood products), paper, printing industries account for about 3% of the gross value added of the Polish economy - (*Eurostat*). Poland is the EU's largest producer of wood flooring, HDF/MDF and garden equipment, the fourth largest producer of furniture, the second largest producer of particleboard, and the eighth largest producer of lumber.

The forestry biomass (2019, Removals in the State Forests National Forest Holding, Statistics Poland) was equal to (thousand m³): timber (38 905), coniferous (30 313), non-coniferous (8592), stump wood (11.5). The value of sold timber in The State Forests National Forest Holding (2019) was (million euro): 1444 (coniferous wood), 408 (non-coniferous) and 17 (slash).

4.2.11.1.3 Aquatic & water systems

The last primary sector (fisheries) which delivers biomass to (mainly) manufacturing sectors can be divided into (1) fishing and (2) fish farming - inland aquaculture. Both fishing in the sea (mainly the Baltic Sea) and inland waters is not significant (numbers). Inland aquaculture production compared to fishing is more significant. Inland aquaculture can be divided into two segments: low-intensity and intensive (notional division). Low-intensity (extensive) aquaculture mainly comprises so-called traditional fish farming methods, with carp farming dominating in earthen ponds with standing water, with areas of up to several hundred hectares and a large package of ecosystem services for the environment. The groups of species most commonly used in polyculture are predatory (pike, pikeperch, European catfish, asp, burbot), herbivorous (white amur, white and spotted pollock), rheophilous (ide, mumps, chub, barbel), other (tench, crucian carp, whitefish, pelugas), decorative (koi carp, crucian carp, tench, golden orfa). Intensive aquaculture mainly involves the rearing and farming of salmonids, sturgeon and African catfish and the production of stocking material. Fish farming facilities are characterised by smaller land areas and greater technical and technological commitment. The aquaculture sector in Poland consists primarily of carp and salmonid fish rearing facilities, with carp and rainbow trout dominating as the main species.

Poland is the leader of carp production in UE. Almost all of the biomass from inland aquaculture, in the form of fish, is consumed in Poland. The largest share of exports from Poland is processed, mainly smoked, salmon, which is harvested by Polish companies or purchased from abroad and processed. In 2020, 371 thousand tons of fish and fish products (worth €2.3 billion) were exported from Poland, 90% to European Union countries. The industry sector that processes this type of biomass in Poland is mainly 'food production'.

Due to its highly developed primary sectors of the economy and food processing, as well as its large population, Poland produces a huge amount of bio-waste, which has great potential for use, both to create innovative products and to produce bioenergy.

Poland, Full trade

Figure 64. Biomass flows in Poland.

(Gurria et al., 2017b)

According to fishery and aquaculture data for Poland 2020, (*Statistics Poland*) catches (in tons) of marine fishes were estimated at – 188 097, and of freshwater estimated at – 1557. Production volume of consumer fish from

domestic aquaculture for main species was equal to (thousand tons): 21.15 (carp) and 21.02 (trout), (*Statistics Poland*).

4.2.11.1.4 Bioenergy

Biogas production, despite untapped resource potential (waste, agricultural production), is currently in an upward trend [6]. Despite the fact that the biofuel production sector in Poland is not strongly developed, it has, especially in the context of the current conditions arising from the RED II directive, a large development potential (Borowski et al., 2021). The biofuels market is mainly focused on the supply of biocomponents, which are produced based on products or waste from the agro-food industry, (Jurga et al., 2021).

4.2.11.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

Financing institutions in Poland focused on innovative, competitive solutions are rather not oriented towards the specific area of bioeconomy. Activities in this area are focused on sectors or elements that can contribute to the development of the bioeconomy. Start-ups are seeking funding mainly from Venture Capital (VC) funds. Despite the fact that the Venture Capital market in Poland is growing incredibly fast (almost 2300% increase in investments from 2018 to 2021), existing companies which belong to bioeconomy sectors are growing mainly by utilizing funds received from banks or subsidies (Kuchar & Analytics Team, 2021). VC-funded companies (2021) are mainly associated with such economic activities as health, finance, IT / internet services, commerce / retail / shopping, transportation / delivery, real estate, data analytics. However, it is worth noting that activities related to the production of food and beverages, as well as energy (sectors important for the development of the bioeconomy in Poland) accounted for an aggregate share of about 9% of the total number of transactions of VC in 2021. According to currently prepared documents called 'Concept Papers' for bioeconomy strategy development - niche economic activities related to bioeconomy were proposed: biogas production, organic agriculture and aquaculture. Based on the research and analysis, the abovementioned activities have a great potential for bioeconomy development [paragraph based on draft concept paper elaborated in H2020 project - Advancing Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Central and Eastern European countries: BIOEASTsUP / prepared by IUNG].

About two decades ago, Poland joined the European Union, and as a result, the period since 2004 has been a time of rapid changes. Systematically, since 2004, Poland has experienced economic growth, strengthening its position and implementing innovative solutions in many sectors related to the bioeconomy. The agri-food sector has become more competitive and efficient (agriculture, food and beverage production, inland fishing). Manufacturing and logging (forestry) associated with the production of wood products, furniture, printing or paper industries have grown in strength, increasing their importance in foreign and domestic markets. The groundwork has been established for the bioenergy market (biofuels, biogas), which will grow strongly given the current situation.

Ongoing climate change, greater consumer awareness, the geopolitical situation and demographic concerns are forcing the search for innovation in every sector of the bioeconomy. Discussions on possible trends and changes are currently underway. Autonomous robots will be implemented in primary sectors due to demographic issues. More drought-tolerant varieties of species will also be explored. Current situation in Poland (shifting away from coal, energy self-sufficiency, large biomass resources) envisage strong development of the biogas and biomethane market in Poland. The increasing use of innovative solutions in product development introduces greater use of biomass, including waste biomass. Increasing consumer awareness, as well as the food passportization planned for implementation, increases the chances of developing better quality food that could have an interest on the market in Poland (the increase in importance of organic farming).

The circular economy is now one of the most important global trends (especially from entrepreneurship perspective), and doing business responsibly gives a competitive advantage. Therefore, more and more companies are recognizing the need to change the economic model from linear to circular, including Poland. The trends in Poland are consistent with those in other countries in the European Union. Some of the solutions selected in the "Stena Circular Economy Award - Leader of the Closed-Circuit Economy" competition from the Polish market (2019-2021):

- Orange Polska S.A. (the "Multimedia Device Renewal" project, under which used routers and modems returned by customers at the end of a contract are renewed and made available to subsequent subscribers),
- Carrefour Polska Sp. z o.o. ("Shopping in customers' own packages" campaign),
- STU ERGO Hestia SA ("Upcycling waste and organizing upcycling workshops"),
- Barry Callebaut Manufacturing Polska Sp. z o.o. (use of waste generated in chocolate production to produce mash, which is then processed into bioethanol),
- Nowy Styl Sp. z o.o. (introduction of additional services for repairing and redistribution of unused furniture and processing of elements unfit for further use),
- IKEA Retail (customers were given a chance to give a second life to their furniture by reselling it in IKEA stores or deciding to buy used furniture in the circular hub departments available in the chain's stores),
- Kaufland (in order to reduce its negative impact on the environment, it relies on solutions involving the use of material already in circulation to produce valuable products. The chain has introduced, among other things, bags made in 80% of foil from its own stores, and uses 50% to 100% recycled materials in the manufacture of private label products (K-Classic, Newcential, Spice&Soul),
- EcoBean (the company offers a solution based on the service of collecting grounds, which are then processed into raw materials and products: biorefinery (coffee oil, lignin, polylactide, feed additives) or biofabrication (briquettes, biodegradable pots),
- WoshWosh (organization of shoe collections, which were then reconditioned and refurbished for reuse - more than 50,000. pairs of shoes),
- Allegro.pl (introducing more than 571,000 eco-packages, 100% recycled and FSC-certified).

The roadmap for the "Transformation to a Closed Economy" published in 2019 by the Polish Council of Ministers highlights elements such as sustainable industrial production, sustainable consumption, bioeconomy, new business models, implementation, monitoring and financing of the circular economy. It is a standard document, unfortunately not distinguished by anything specific.

4.2.11.3 Policies and national strategies

Table 23. Current national Bioeconomy related strategies in Poland. Source: (BIOEAST,)

Existing national Bioeconomy related strategy document	Bioeconomy related goals* addressed				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
BIOSTRATEG Strategic and Research program "Environment, Agriculture and Forestry 2013+		+	+	+	+
(2019) National Energy and Climate Plan for the years 2021-2030		+	+		
National Smart Specialisation Strategy 2014	+	+			+
Plan for Rural Areas (bioeconomy as one of the priority projects named Agriculture for Ecology) 2014	+	+	+	+	+
(2019) Roadmap on circular economy (GOZ), government document	+	+			+
(2013) Polish National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (NAS2020) with the perspective by 2030.			+	+	+

(2019) Strategy for Sustainable Rural Development, Agriculture and Fisheries 2030 (SZRWRiR 2030)	+	+	+	+	+
(2019) 2030 National Environmental Policy (PEP2030)	+	+	+		+
Energy Policy of Poland until 2030 (draft);		+	+		
<p><i>* Is one of the EU bioeconomy strategies (2018) objectives covered by the bioeconomy related strategy at national level? Creating jobs and maintaining competitiveness in bioeconomy sectors (1); Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources (2); Mitigating and adapting climate change (3); Ensuring food security (4); Managing natural resources sustainably (5);</i></p>					

Table 24. Current status of national bioeconomy strategy actors involved Source: (BIOEAST).

Status of national bioeconomy strategy		Dedicated Bioeconomy Strategy at national level under development In Poland there is no decision on national strategy development! Bioeconomy is named part of Circular economy Road map, Agricultural Policy and Smart Specialization Strategy
Actor/institution		Institutions' role related to the bioeconomy
Ministries, other Government institutions involved in strategy setting / policy formulation		I. Role in (forthcoming) national bioeconomy strategies II. Role in national strategies / policies relating to bioeconomy (focus on post-2020!)
Lead ministries	Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Technology	I. Ministry responsible for three administrative sectors: the economy, construction and housing, and tourism. The strategic goal of the Ministry is modernisation of Polish economy in technological and ecological terms (industry 4.0, digitisation and automation, green technologies, closed-loop economy). In Road Map towards the transition to Circular Economy – GOZ) responsible for: (1) Establishing a permanent teams of department directors at government agencies responsible for individual areas, supervising the implementation of GOZ tasks (2) Identification of local value chains; (3) Feasibility study on the creation and development of local biorefineries; (4) Information campaign on biomass products; (5) Drawing up norms and standards for particular categories of products made from biomass, (6) Working group with entrepreneurs to develop the concept and creation of a cluster for bio-economic development. II. Responsible for national strategies: National Smart specializations (new list adopted 01.01.2021). Road Map towards the transition to Circular Economy – GOZ (adopted 10.09.2021).
	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	I. Responsible for agricultural sector and fisheries, agricultural markets, research and innovation in agriculture and food production. In GOZ responsible for: (1) Analysis of biomass supply potential at the national and regional level; (2) Information campaign aimed at educating farmers and targeting their activities on CE and the principle of cascading use of biomass; (3) Developing a concept for an

		<p>information platform on current quantity, quality, place and source (agriculture, forestry, fisheries, bio-waste) of biomass: level, preceded by the development of an appropriate methodology.</p> <p>II. Responsible for national strategies: "Strategy for sustainable rural, agricultural and fisheries development 2030" (adopted 15.10.2020); National Strategic CAP Plan post. 2021.</p>
	Ministry of Education and Science	<p>I. Supporting Research & Development Institutions in Poland. Responsible for Innovation Incubators programs - The subject of these programs is to support entities of the higher education and science system in the implementation of projects aimed at applying the results of scientific research and development work in the economic or social sphere by technology transfer and commercialization (with EU funds). In GOZ responsible for: Identification of research, development and innovation (R&D&I) priorities for the development of bioeconomy in Poland.</p> <p>II. Responsible for implementation of The Law on Higher Education and Science (adopted 20.07.2018); Polish Roadmap for Research Infrastructures BIOSTRATEG. Strategic and Research Program "Environment, Agriculture and Forestry"; Strategy for Scientific Excellence, Modern Higher Education, Partnership with Business and Responsible Research.</p>
Support ministry	Ministry of Development Funds and Regional Policy	<p>I. Ministry provides services in the field of government administration for regional development.</p> <p>II. Responsible for coordination and monitoring the main intersectoral strategy in Poland: The Strategy for Responsible Development for the period up to 2020 (including the perspective up to 2030) – SRD (adopted 14.02 2017); National Recovery Plan.</p>

4.2.11.4 Small scale biobased solutions

- **REBREAD:** (*REBREAD*) the company uses unsold bread before it becomes waste and transforms it into valuable products - distillate, beer, bread-based foods and beverages, natural cosmetics, utensils and packaging, substrates for growing edible mushrooms, 3D printing, natural fertilizers.
- **Planeat:** production of plant-based products for those looking for interesting alternatives to meat - such as plant-based minced meat and Greek-style vege Gyros.
- **Dynamic Biogas:** a company with investments involving the construction of an innovative third-generation biogas plant, processing bio-waste efficiently, among other things.
- **BIOCONT:** manufactures and distributes more than 70 biological and biotech products for crop protection and production.
- **VERTIGO FARMS:** ultimately clean plant extracts for the cosmetics, pharmaceutical and food industries, are obtained from herbs grown indoors in a strictly controlled environment.
- **BELLA:** eco-friendly ultra-thin sanitary napkins covered with skin-soft bamboo non-woven fabric
- **MIRA Natural Cosmetics:** [cosmetics with good and simple compositions, 100% natural.
- **SURWIN Ltd** - processing waste into distillate and bioethanol, which is a biocomponent for fuel.
- **GWDA Sp. z o.o:** a company that produces compost-based biofertilizer KOMPROL, similar in effect to manure.

4.2.12 Latvia

4.2.12.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

The country of Latvia was included in the reports of JRC through the years about biomass flows, (Gurria et al., 2017b)(2020).
Latvia, Full trade

Figure 65. Biomass flows in Latvia.

Source: (Gurria et al., 2017c)

As we can see from this graph Latvia has an important amount of biomass flows in the agriculture sector and in the forestry sector. Latvia has a total area of 64,559 km² and the forest land counts about 34.964 km², and that is the reason why there is a massive forestry biomass flow, and the country's main export products is wood.

Figure 66. Biomass Flows

Source: (Biomass Flows)

Employment by sector in Latvia (2019)

(number of people employed)

Figure 67. Employment by sector.

Source: (Biomass Flows)

Also, apart from the forestry sector the agricultural sector has an important role in the bioeconomy status of the country, and we can understand this from the number of employees and how it is divided on the sectors.

Table 25. Employment by sector. Source: (Biomass Flows.)

NACE2	People employed
Agriculture	45 430
Wood products and furniture	24 257
Food, beverage and tobacco	23 213
Forestry	18 680
Bio-based textiles	4 064
Bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber (excl. biofuels)	1 567
Fishing and Aquaculture	1 490
Paper	1 419
Bio-based electricity	336
Liquid biofuels	0

Value added by sector in Latvia (2019)

(million €)

Figure 68. Value added by sector.

Source: (Biomass Flows)

From the following table, from the latest data available about the value added of its sector we can see that in the first position is the wood products and the sector of agriculture.

Table 26. Value added by sector. Source:(Biomass Flows)

NACE2	Value added (miln EUR)
Wood products and furniture	630
Agriculture	616
Forestry	563
Food, beverage and tobacco	473
Bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics and rubber (excl. biofuels)	67
Fishing and Aquaculture	46
Bio-based textiles	42
Paper	36
Bio-based electricity	33
Liquid biofuels	0

4.2.12.2 Bioeconomy Potentials and national strategies

The last two decades there is a gradual increase in the bioeconomy in Latvia, after the huge drop that was faced in the 1990's and the sector has shown signs of improvement. Biomass productions will be quite stabile, but it is probable that due to environmental and climate policies there will be some reduction in the biomass production. However, the country developed a strategy about 5 years ago in order to face these difficulties and there is ongoing work for releasing a new bioeconomy strategy. The current strategy is prepared under the ministry of agriculture but the new one will be cross ministerial in order to combine more sectors. As for the small-scale solutions there is some innovative work from the wood constructions (wooden houses, wood bridges) and insulation material. Additionally, there some novel food products, organic and sustainable food production as well as packaging and IT solutions for bioeconomy companies.

4.2.13 Germany

4.2.13.1 Biomass flows and bioeconomy data.

Szarska et. al ,(2021b) investigated biomass flows for Germany scientifically. Baseline is 2015 and the investigated sectors include agriculture, forest and biogenic residues and waste as biomass producing and generating sectors, and food, feed, material, and energy as biomass use sectors. Further, the net trade of biomass was considered. The information and results are based on extensive collection and processing of available official data and its harmonization was carried out and validated with experts. The results showed that:

- Amount of agricultural biomass for the food (human) and feed (agricultural and leisure) livestock sector is 95 Mio. t DM in 2015, where off 66% are for the feed sector!
- The forest sector produced around 33 Mio. t DM of woody biomass, of which around 20 Mio. t DM was used as solid fuel.
- Biogenic residues and wastes are up to 32 Mio. t DM of which 22 Mio t DM were used by the energy sector.

In agriculture, wheat and maize are main crops with > 8 Mio t/a. The established Sankey Diagram visualized the biomasses flows in Germany.

**Biomass flow in Bioeconomy:
Overview for Germany 2015**

Figure 69. Biomass Flow Overview for Germany. Source: by Szarska et. al. 2021

Germany, Full trade

Figure 70. Sankey Diagram of main biomass flows in Germany.

Source: (Gurria et al., 2017b)

The stated sources display detailed figures for different biomasses in comprehensive tables for further evaluation. The following chapter details the biomass flow figures by application of the 5 requested topics of Bioeconomy.

The term bioeconomy refers to a modern and sustainable form of economic activity based on the efficient use of biological resources such as plants, animals and microorganisms. This requires highly innovative approaches to utilization.

The bioeconomy covers all industrial and economic sectors that use renewable biological resources to manufacture products and provide services using innovative biological and technological knowledge and processes. This includes all industries that produce, process or use biological resources in any form, such as agriculture and forestry, energy, fisheries and aquaculture, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, food, industrial biotechnology, cosmetics, paper and textiles, and environmental protection (*About the Bioeconomy | Bioökonomie.De*, n.d.).

The following tables are based on different sources, giving a general overview of feedstocks:

Table 27. Overview Of Feedstock. Source: (Szarka et al., 2021a)

Sector	Figures (year)
Food produced in t	15.5 Mio t DM (2015)
Food waste produced in t	11 Mio t (2020)
Livestock in amount	11 Mio. cattles, 26 Mio. Pigs, 1.8 Mio. sheeps, 173 Mio. Poultry
Agriculture/forest/residual wastes	64 Mio. t DM (2015)
Agriculture in ha	17 Mio. ha (2015)
Arable area in ha	11 Mio. ha (2015)
Grass land in ha	4.7 Mio. ha (2015)
Cropland in ha	0.2 Mio. ha (2015)
GHG-emissions agriculture	+56.1 Mio t CO ₂ -eq
Forest in ha	14 Mio. ha (2015)
Logging in t	Pine logging: 44.5 Mio m ³ (2021)
GHG-Emission wood products	-8.65 Mio. t (2020)
Waste wood for recycling	1.7 Mio t (2020)
Waste wood for thermal recovery	5.4 Mio t (2020)
GHG-Emission forestry	-45.84 Mio. t (2020) reduction!
Fishery/Aquaculture in t	0.3 Mio. t (2018) with 29% aquaculture, 71% fishery
Algea in t	None
Woody fuels total	13. Mio t DM (2015)
Briquettes/Pellets	1.8 Mio. t DM (2015)
Charcoal	0.2 t DM (2015)
Sawing by products	0.9 Mio t DM (2015)
Black liquor	2 Mio. t DM (2015)
Industrial wood	2.2 Mio t DM (2015)
Heat from biogas/Biomethan	16.9 TWh (2015 [^])
Heat from biomass total	147 TWh (2018)
Power from bioenergy in MWh	51.3 TWh (2018)
GHG-Emissions	-64.3 Mio. t (2018)
Biomaterials/bio-based products	Not applicable, as very differing, details please see link on the right

As for the employment in the current situation in Germany we can see in together with the value of each sector in the following table.

Table 28. Value of each sector. Source: (Bundestag,)

Sector	Employees (year)
Biobased industry in Total	ca. 1.2 Mio. (2014)
Food/baverage systems	555,000
Forestry/natural habitats systems,	45.800 (2021)
Agriculture	528.00 (2014)
Forestry Based industry	236.625 (2014)
Forestry/agriculture total	1 Mio. (2015)
Industrial wood processing industry (panels, wood fuels, etc.)	13.500 (2020)
fisheries, aquaculture, aquatic biomass production	2.424 (2018)
Bioenergy	220.157 (2015)
Biofuels	15.706 (2014)
Biobased chemical industry	101.102 (2014)
Biobased Textile	60.382 (2014)
Paper Industry	236.625 (2014)

Sector	Value (year)
Bioeconomy in total	196.9 Bill. € (2104)
Food/beverage systems	170 Bill € (2015)
Agriculture/forestry	32 Bill. € (2015)
Forestry	1.3 Bill. € (2020) revenue
Wood processing industry	26 Bill. € (2021)
fisheries, aquaculture, aquatic biomass production	467 Mio. US-Dollar (2018)
Bioenergy	466 Bill. € (2015)
Textile	11 Bill. € (2014)
Biobased chemical and pharmaceutical sector	33.5 Bill. € (2014)
Paper Industry	39.8 Bill. € (2014)
Biorefineries in pieces	59 refineries, mainly lignin-based chemicals, biggest factory in LEUNA, operation from 2023, capacity 300.000 t wood/y

4.2.13.2 Bioeconomy potentials and trends

Biomasses:

- Fresh Wood and Wood wastes
- Agri industry wastes
- Food wastes

Related Innovation areas

- Establishment of biobased industry: Bio-refineries to produce chemical base products from organic instead of fossil resources ,Germany Biorefinery strategy 2012 (*Roadmap Bioraffinerien Im Rahmen Der*

Aktionspläne Der Bundesregierung Zur Stofflichen Und Energetischen Nutzung Nachwachsender Rohstoffe, n.d.). Currently in LEUNA a biorefinery to produce chemicals out of lignin (wood based) is built and shall come to operation in 2023 (*Bioraffinerie Leuna | UPM Biochemicals, n.d.*).

- The NBS focus with policies and legislation on two main options:
 - Harnessing biological knowledge and responsible innovation for sustainable, climate-neutral development, meaning research in biological understanding and application within the biobased industry by maintenance societal acceptance and no harm to the environment.
 - Using biogenic raw materials for a sustainable, circular economy, meaning activation of organic wastes, residues, fresh organic matter to replace fossil-based resources such as oil mainly to produce commodities as well as biobased energy (thermal recycling/recover).

In general waste reduction in the biobased sector are sufficient strategies but also lead to decreasing quantities for biobased applications, which has to be considered, if zero-waste strategies are implemented on national level.

4.2.13.3 Policies and national strategies

The current Bioeconomy Strategy, (für Bildung, n.d.) centers on “sustainability” and “climate actions” as the key issues of economic action to avoid considerable damage to the biosphere ending all live on earth. The Bioeconomy ‘Strategy has the illusory and unrealistic ambition to combine ecologically sustainable consumption of natural resources, current economic prosperity and the right to future development future generations.

“The Federal Government of Germany defines the bioeconomy as the production, exploitation and use of biological resources, processes and systems to provide products, processes and services across all economic sectors within the framework of a future-oriented economy.”

The Strategy, (Federal Government of Germany, n.d.) builds on the National Research Strategy BioEconomy 2030, (Ministry of Education, n.d.) and the National Policy Strategy on Bioeconomy, (*Bioeconomy*) to pool the various political strands together into a coherent framework. The National Bioeconomy Strategy shall foster Germany’s role as a self-declared bioeconomy leader and to create the technology and jobs of tomorrow. With the Strategy, the German Federal Government wants to mirror global responsibility for future generations. Biological knowledge and advanced technology are main pillars of the National Research Strategy BioEconomy 2030. Essential part of research is technical innovations in combination with social, political and economic research to accompany the profound societal transformation process. The research focus is on diverse organism and biological processes.

The National Policy Strategy on Bioeconomy relates to the raw materials used by industry and the need for a sustainable and circular economy based on the use of biogenic resources. It can be summarized in six common strategic goals:

- 1) Develop bioeconomy solutions for the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development
- 2) Recognize and harness the potential of the bioeconomy within ecological boundaries
- 3) Enhance and apply biological knowledge
- 4) Establish a sustainable raw material base for industry
- 5) Promote Germany as the leading location for innovation in the bioeconomy
- 6) Involve society and strengthen national and international collaboration

For each of these strategic goals, research is the key issue for state funding, which will focus on:

- Enhancement of biological knowledge
- converging technologies and transdisciplinary cooperation
- boundaries and potentials
- translation to real-life application
- bioeconomy and society and

- International research collaboration.

The Strategy describes the policy areas as well which are affected:

- reducing pressure on land use
- ensuring the sustainable production and supply of biogenic raw materials
- expanding and developing the supply chains and networks of the bioeconomy
- designing instruments to establish and bring bio-based products, processes and services to the market.
- ensuring policy coherence
- making use of the opportunities offered by the bioeconomy for the development of rural areas and
- taking advantage of digital technology for the bioeconomy.

The strategy involves cross-cutting approaches such as:

- establishment of an advisory committee
- cooperation between the Federal and Länder levels of government and at European and international level
- measures to foster communication and open dialogue with various groups of society.
- initiatives to promote training and skills development and setting up a bioeconomy monitoring system.

Currently a new biomass strategy, as part of the bioeconomy strategy is currently under revise. The strategy, which will be presented next year and cover the biomass approach until 2030.

Main information source for bioeconomy Germany

The [national bioeconomy homepage](#) is hosted by the German Ministry of Research and Education. This homepage should be consulted for latest development and information about bioeconomy in Germany.

Clusters/Initiatives on Bioeconomy

Beside the databases, to promote and to implement the bioeconomy strategies, several bioeconomy clusters and private/public initiatives have been established on regional level. Overview of specific clusters in Germany can be found here on the [cluster platform](#). The following table states selected clusters and initiatives in the field of bioeconomy in Germany.

Table 29. Cluster and Initiatives. Source: (Clusterplattform Deutschland)

Clusters/Initiatives	Region	Tasks
Cluster Bioeconomy	Sachsen and Sachsen Anhalt as key regions	Networking, Funding, nutrients recovery (Phosphor, lignin), consultation
Nachhaltige Bioökonomie Baden-Württemberg	Baden-Württemberg	Biobased industry, funding, consultation
Polykum	Sachsen-Anhalt	Biobased plastics research, consultation
Bayrische Bioökonomiestrategie 2020	Bayern	Funding, consultation
CLuster Bayern Initiative	Bayern	Networking, funding, biobased research and development, consultation
Biosaxony	Sachsen	Biobased pharma, health, nutrients, consultation
Bioökonomiestrategie Hessen	Hessen	Biofuels, bioenergy, consultation
Masterplan Bioökonomie 2020	Niedersachsen	Agri-based products, residual management, food security, biobased fertilizer, consultation

Kompetenznetzwerk Holz	Niedersachsen	Wood based products and bioenergy, consultation
Bioeconomy Science Center	Nordrhein-Westfalen	Agriculture, research, networking, consultation
National Bioeconomy Strategy	Nordrhein-Westfalen	Networking, research, information exchange, stakeholder cooperation, consultation
Kompetenzzentrum Erneuerbare Energien und Klimaschutz Schleswig-Holstein - Bioökonomie	Schleswig-Holstein	Competence network, research, funding, consultation
Cluster Biopolymere/Biowerkstoffe	Baden-Württemberg	Competence network, research, funding, consultation
Spitzencluster BioEconomy	Sachsen-Anhalt	Competence network, research, funding, consultation

4.2.13.4 Small scale biobased solutions

- Biogas from solid organic residuals such as horse manure, green cut, harvest residues in the city of Kerkel/Germany
- biochar from organic residues, especially sewage sludges from municipal waste treatment plant of Homburg
- biomaterials, such as polyphenols or other extracts from organic matter for nutrient, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, bio-chemical sector

4.2.14 The Netherlands

The Netherlands have not yet developed a national strategy develop for the bioeconomy, but they already have other policies and initiatives dedicated to the bioeconomy at national level. Although the Netherlands is not at the forefront of the green economy, the structure and strengths of its economy lend itself for the transition to a bioeconomy. Also, the bioeconomy is highly developed in agro-food industry sector which makes up almost 10% of GDP. A disadvantage of the country is due to the lack of biomass potentials, there no forest biomass and the only potential available is agricultural biomass. The Dutch bioeconomy is made up of the economic top sectors chemistry, energy, water and agro food that work together with the government on strengthening the already strong positions. An ambitious sector that works as an exception is the chemistry one and leads the bioeconomy process, partly forced by the strong global competition.

Figure 71. Biomass flows in The Netherlands.

(Gurria et al., 2017b)

The ambition for the next years for this country is to have an important role in the global bioeconomy. More specific the target is until 2050 to become the worldwide leader of the bioeconomy and to be on the top three global producers of smart biomaterials, which is an important sector for the country. Key part to this development is searching, learning and experimenting in the following sector.

- Biobased materials
- Bioenergy, biomaterials
- Integrated biorefineries
- Plant cultivation, biomass production
- Recycling water, nutrients, soil
- Policy, sustainability

For this purpose, the 'national bio raw materials roadmap' has been drawn up. In addition to focusing on more square value (using everything from vegetable production, without residual flows), it will also be necessary to invest in cultivation for organic raw materials. Since 2014, Experimental Farm Rusthoeve has been extensively experimenting with different crops. Roughly speaking, a classification can be made into, on the one hand, ingredients that can be converted into value via refining (e.g. sugar, starch, inulin with subsequent steps in the chemical industry or food industry, but one can also think of vegetable latex for rubber, bioplastics, dyes, etc. These possibilities are very large but still in its infancy. The other track that offers opportunities here are fibre applications. In fibre applications, not a molecule from the plant is refined, but a large part of the plant is used as fibre. We can roughly distinguish three markets for fibre applications: construction, packaging (paper and cardboard) and textiles. The construction and paper industry in particular seem to be shaking off the pioneering stage and steps are being taken here towards larger-scale application. The current coalition agreement also includes biobased building materials as a spearhead. The challenge that surrounds the housing industry would make this a huge opportunity can be to sustainability. Not only does this use less fossil input, but these crops also capture CO₂ in the construction products. An ambitious program has been drawn up through an interdepartmental program (Building Balance) that

would require 50,000 ha of fibre crops spread across the Netherlands. Fibre crops that are eligible for this include hemp, miscanthus, flax, but possibly also bulrush, sun crown and sorghum. An example of bioeconomy is the Green Chemistry Campus which use its facilities to experiment with and develop radical biobased innovations like biopolymers, biobased building materials and biobased colour pigments.

4.2.14.1 Policies and national strategies

Although they don't have a national strategy and policy dedicated to the bioeconomy, they followed some existing strategies of the previous years.

Circular Economy	2017
National program on Circular Economy	2016
Biomass Vision 2030	2016
Agenda for the food policy	2016
Main line notes Biobased Economy	2012
Green Growth for a strong, sustainable economy	2013
National biobased research agenda 2015-2017	2015
Draft integrated National Energy and Climate Plan 2021-2030 for the Netherlands	2018

5 Discussion/Analysis

This report provides an overview of the current bioeconomy status in the EU with a particular focus on 13 EU member states and North Macedonia, regional and national trends and policies and small-scale biobased solutions. There are a number of important trends occurring in the EU bioeconomy overall. On the one hand overall employment is decreasing while the overall value of the bioeconomy is increasing. The decrease in employment can be attributed to a number of trends, there is a notable decline in the agricultural sector which is driven by demographic changes and a consolidation of farm holdings. On the other hand, large increases in employment are observed in the bioenergy sector and the biomaterials and bioindustry sectors (JRC & Novo-Institute, 2022). These trends are expected to continue as the transition towards a more circular European economy is heavily dependent on the replacement of fossil energy and fossil-based products.

Regarding biomass flows, the JRC provides detailed overviews of biomass flows within countries, per sector and for the EU as a whole (JRC, 2022). The continued update and effective dissemination of this knowledge, across all main primary and secondary sectors, is crucial for our understanding of the development of the bioeconomy. It is clear that current biomass flows are dominated by agricultural production for supply and food and feed for use/consumption. It is unlikely that the importance of the food and agricultural sector will diminish, but it is clear that for a sustainable transition and to achieve EU climate goals, both supply and use in other sectors that replace fossil fuels and fossil-based products will need to expand rapidly.

In this sense, there are important considerations around the availability of sufficient biomass supply. On the one hand feedstocks that do not compete with land for food and feed need to continue to be developed. Multiple studies have shown for instance that Perennial biomass crops (PBC) are a crucial feedstock for the development of biomass supply that is not in competition for land used for food production. (Choi et al., 2019). Other sources such as algal feedstocks have been shown to also have considerable potential. On the other hand, biomass supply can be improved by increases in the efficiency of biomass production but also the reuse of bio-waste into productive sectors. Improvements in productive efficiency output for biomass grown on land currently under production is a complex issue with important environmental considerations. In the past considerable production efficiency improvements have been achieved through the increased application of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides in combination with fossil energy. It is now well documented that increased production efficiencies will need to be combined with decreases in synthetic and fertiliser use as well as fossil fuels and that this will require a transformation of the production of EU biomass supply. Alternative approaches that can support such a transition include practices based on conservation agriculture or agroforestry (Paris et al., 2022).

The EU is often considered as a leader in the recovery and reuse of biowaste. Despite this and considerable policy efforts considerable amounts of bio-waste are not or under-utilised. Numerous studies have indicated that the effective use of this bio-waste could provide large amounts of sustainable feedstocks for the wider EU bioeconomy (EEA, 2020). The total potential capture of biowaste per kilogram per person per year in the EU is 222, while currently only 77kg is collected (Favoino et al., 2020). The development of effective value chains that collect and process this waste into functional raw materials is especially important for certain agricultural wastes and urban-bio waste. For instance, large amounts of bio-waste from urban areas are currently landfilled in the EU, the development of effective biowaste optimisation processes are required (Favoino et al., 2020). In particular, Fava et al. (2015) highlight that there are also many opportunities' for integrating biowaste feedstocks into biorefineries (Fava et al., 2015).

One of the key goals of the Updated EU bioeconomy strategy is to 'strengthen and scale-up the bio-based sectors' (European Commission, 2018a). The overview presented in this report indicates that the development of a circular bioeconomy is still in its relatively infant stages but that important initiatives towards circularity exist throughout the biobased economy. In this sense, small scale biobased solutions, which have the potential to scale rapidly are crucial to the transformation of the EU economy. This report clearly documents a large number of small-scale biobased solutions and initiatives relevant to the circular transition and in order to accelerate their impact these

need to be supported through relevant policy mechanisms and continued access to significant research and innovation funding.

The production of bioenergy in the EU has experienced a transformation in the past decade currently accounting for the majority of renewable energy produced. This has happened in tandem with considerable developments in feedstock supply and conversion methods. Mandley et al (2020) investigate the potential of bioenergy development in the EU until 2050 highlighting that despite large uncertainties EU biomass production has the potential to facilitate future bioenergy demand while also experiencing large increases in the import of biomass (Mandley et al., 2020).

There are a number of important niche sectors that have the potential to considerably scale in the future. The development of biobased industries and biorefineries supported by biobased innovation processes are a key priority for the EC. The 2022 EU blue economy report highlights the importance of preserving and enhancing the natural capital of water bodies in the EU while also the importance of the 'blue biotechnology' sector as one of the key emerging sectors within water systems. Particularly promising is the development of the algae sector as well as related biorefineries, offshore aquaculture, the use of fish by-products and cellular mariculture and cell-based seafood (European Commission, 2022). The 2021 EU Forest Strategy for 2030 highlights the importance of supporting the socio-economic functions of forest while enhancing the forest based bio-economy within sustainable boundaries, key to this is the development of sustainable raw wood biomass supply, the sustainable use of wood products in particular for bioenergy, promoting the non-wood bioeconomy and services for instance through eco-tourism, whilst simultaneously protecting, restoring and enlarging EU forests ensuring climate resilience and biodiversity (European Commission, 2021).

This study identifies a number of key areas for future research including more detailed overviews of the bioeconomy for all EU member states; an in-depth analyses of specific bio-based value chains; the relationship between economy, society and the environment; the relationship between the bioeconomy, other sectors and the circular economy; indicators that measure the impact and potentials of the bioeconomy and its sectors are being developed and need to be strengthened further; and future research providing projections and scenario analyses on the future state of the bioeconomy in the medium and long-term. In addition, the conceptual understanding of the bioeconomy by relevant stakeholders appears limited, for instance, at times the terms bioeconomy and bio-based economy as well as biorefineries and bio-based industries appear mislabelled. Important steps are being made by the EC to correct this and continued policy efforts need to be implemented through for instance the development of unified national bioeconomy strategies for all member states. Furthermore, on a geographical and regional level, it is clear that the bioeconomy plays a crucial role in economies across the EU but that recent developments are unequal. For instance, the development of biorefineries is more prevalent in north western Europe. More research into these geographical variations and research that distinguishes the linear bioeconomy with a circular bioeconomy and how its value chains differ are needed.

6 Conclusions

This study provides a review of the current status of the European Bioeconomy, containing all the main 5 themes (agriculture, water systems, forestry, bioenergy, biomaterials), as well as the existing bioeconomy national strategies, trends and opportunities that exist in the EU together with successful small-scale biobased solutions.

The information presented in this report illustrates the diversity and complexity of the EU bioeconomy. There are a number of important trends occurring in the EU bioeconomy: overall employment in the bioeconomy is decreasing while the overall value of the bioeconomy is increasing. Certain sectors, including the bioenergy and biomaterials sectors that are still relatively small as compared to their fossil-based equivalents, are experiencing rapid growth, these sectors are expected to continue to grow rapidly in the medium and long-term supporting sustainable transitions across the economy.

Data indicates that most of the feedstocks are produced within the EU, in particular the agricultural sector with a relative weight of approximately 65% followed by forestry at 34% of dry matter with considerable variations on a country level. On the other hand, biomass supply from water systems is still relatively limited but shows considerable potential, especially in the biotechnology sector. Across the EU the largest consumption of biomass is for food and feed, followed by bioenergy and biomaterials. It is clear that a sustainable transition away from an economy based on fossil resources will require the significant growth in the bioenergy and biomaterials sector while maintaining the food and feed sector. In this context, it is important to consider trade-offs and to highlight that biomass is a finite resource and it is important that ongoing efforts directed at shifting existing biomass supply production systems transition towards more sustainable production methods are continued, that bio-waste collection and use systems are optimized and that new value chains for the sustainable production of biomass, such as BPC, are developed.

The EU economy is transforming from an economy based on linear economic models to circular economic models however, this transformation is still at its early stages and will require the transformation of existing production systems and value chains as well as the creation of new innovative value chains. This report illustrates the potential of small-scale biobased solutions on a country level across the EU and that these have the potential to scale and support a sustainable transformation across the entire EU economy. In this context, it is crucial that significant funds continue to support research and innovation in this sector.

In recent years EU policy has become very supportive of the development of a sustainable EU bioeconomy and the updated EU bioeconomy strategy operates in parallel to multiple other policy initiatives such as the new CAP, Green Deal, Farm to Fork strategy and circular economy action plan. In the short term, the further development of national strategies dedicated to the bioeconomy will strengthen the policy environment. In addition, the development of the bioeconomy has a crucial environmental dimension and current policy is supportive of efforts that support and strengthen environmental services and biodiversity.

This study identifies a number of key areas for future research including more detailed overviews of the bioeconomy for all EU member states; an in-depth analyses of specific bio-based value chains; the relationship between economy, society and the environment; the relationship between the bioeconomy, other sectors and the circular economy; indicators that measure the impact and potentials of the bioeconomy and its sectors are being developed and need to be strengthened further; and future research providing projections and scenario analyses on the future state of the bioeconomy in the medium and long-term.

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8 Annex

BioRural: Data Request for T.1.1

Bioeconomy definition: The production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value-added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy. Its sectors and industries have strong innovation potential due to their use of a wide range of sciences, enabling and industrial technologies, along with local and tacit knowledge.

5 Themes:

- **Food/agriculture systems** which encompass all value chains related to farming, the production of food and biological feedstocks within the 10.5 million farms in the EU.
 - Food waste management
 - Agriculture (openfield, livestock, greenhouses, specific crops, etc)
 - Food processing
- **Forestry/natural habitats systems**, which are a source of environmental public goods, raw materials and services, and refer to processes of managing and utilizing the EU's 182 million ha of forests.
 - Forest management
 - Logging
 - Wood based industries
- **Water systems** which refer to all aquatic systems and respective economic activities (such as fisheries, aquaculture, aquatic biomass production, etc.).
 - Traditional water based activities (fisheries, etc)
 - Innovative water based activities (algae production, etc)
 - Blue economy
- **Bioenergy** which refers to all energy derived from organic sources, being the largest RES in the EU (12% of total energy demand).
 - Biofuels
 - Heat
 - Electricity
- **Biomaterials/bio-based products** which are derived from renewable biological feedstocks and are processed creating conventional products (e.g. timber and textiles) and advanced products (bio-plastics and pharmaceuticals).
 - Bi-products
 - Biorefineries

What we are looking for:

A two to three page summary of the bioeconomy in your country including the following points:

- An overview of Biomass flows, so more than just data on this much biomass is created, we want to understand/have an overview of the main flows from production, processing to consumption in your country. (2-3 paragraphs).
 - For example, in your country agriculture and forestry may be dominant. We want to understand the picture of where it gets produced, how much, where it gets processed and where does it go after? We are looking for bullets or a number of paragraphs summarizing this in your country.
- General data on the bioeconomy for each theme
 - Data on amount of feedstocks produced (tons of production) (bullet points)
 - Employment per sector (bullet points)
 - Value of the various sectors (bullet points)
- Bioeconomy Potential and trends
 - Identify what parts of the bioeconomy has the most potential in your country (especially innovative areas)
 - How have the bioeconomy and biomass flows changed in your country in the past 2 decades, how are they expected to change (1-2 paragraphs or list of bullet points)
 - Anything particular on circular trends
- Key information from your national strategies
 - Main points from the national strategies (1-2 paragraphs, or a list of bullet points)
- Small scale biobased solutions
 - what are the main small scale biobased solutions in your country
- Anything else you consider important

Requests

- Studies/reports/LCA's/national databases
- Data on each bioeconomy sector
- Legal documents
- Policies